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Particulate Matter and Potential Health Impacts in a Remote Environment

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Border and Regions REgions Airways Training Hub (BREATH)

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for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

Declaration

I hereby declare that this thesis has been composed by myself and that it has not been submitted for a DBA, Dprof, EngD, PhD or comparable academic degree. The work contained within this thesis has been carried out independently at the University of the West of Scotland and University of Glasgow.

Carly Woods, March 2023

Dedication

For my mum and dad, Jennifer & Gerard Woods, and my partner, Graeme Buttle.

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Abstract

Air pollution is one of the most important environmental factors affecting health, with vulnerable populations facing the greatest burden of negative impacts. Among these populations are those with respiratory conditions such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), a chronic inflammatory condition currently the third leading cause of death globally. There have been a number of legislative efforts introduced to reduce levels of air pollution, however, these have been ineffective and current monitoring strategies have distinct limitations. For this reason, the introduction of low-cost, mobile and accurate airborne pollutant monitoring systems has been a growing area of focus. Evidence indicates that solely monitoring air pollution levels may not be the optimal approach for mitigating morbidity and mortality, as studies have revealed varied effects of different components within ambient particulate matter (PM). However, monitoring methods often fail to identify the composition of PM and are insufficient to determine specific biological impacts. Identifying harmful components and mechanisms of action may ultimately serve to inform and improve current remediation strategies.

In this study, data obtained from an 'AQMesh' low cost monitor showed that gaseous pollutant measurements correlated well with that of the reference monitoring sites. However, PM₁₀ was only indicative of pollutant concentrations and showed potential variation with differing environmental conditions. Concentrations above legislative and / or guideline limitations were identified in all areas studied. Additionally, the AQMesh identified significantly higher NO_x values inside an internal combustion engine vehicle when compared with that of an electric vehicle highlighting the importance of considering personal air pollution exposure.

A separate investigation was undertaken to observe the effects of a common pollutant, diesel engine particulates (DEP) on inflammation and oxidative stress in lung epithelia models. These models included cell line and healthy & COPD patient cells grown submerged and at the air-liquid interface. The impact of the particulates was examined as whole particulates and components. Additionally, the role of protease activated receptor 2 (PAR2), which has links to chronic inflammatory diseases, was investigated with relevance to particulate induced inflammation. This was assessed by comparing DEP stimulation and PAR2 activation mechanisms in the presence and absence of a PAR2 antagonist. Stimulation of PAR2 was determined by measuring indicators such as calcium (Ca²⁺) mobilisation, cytokine release and phosphorylation of protein kinases.

The work in this thesis shows potential evidence for air pollution to contribute to pathogenesis of COPD as diesel particulates have the capability to induce inflammation in human lung epithelia via a mechanism that is, at least partially, dependant on PAR2. The notable impact

of DEP on inflammation in human bronchial epithelial cells was especially apparent when patient cells were differentiated at the air-liquid interface, underscoring the necessity of investigating the effects of airborne xenobiotics in physiologically relevant models of airway epithelia. Particulate fractions demonstrated differential action on lung epithelia, emphasising the importance of composition of particulates as a contributory factor in observed particulate induced effects. This work also shows that air pollution guideline values were breached in COPD hotspot areas. Alongside this, personal exposure was highlighted as an important factor in the consideration of exposure / effect studies.

Future investigations should focus on (i) gaining a better understanding of the efficacy of low-cost monitoring systems, (ii) identification of the action of singular and multiple pollution component action and (iii) understanding how air pollution exposure contributes to COPD development.

Keywords: Air pollution, COPD, PAR2, Monitoring, Particulate matter, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, O₃, NO_x.

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List of Abbreviations

AAT	Alpha-1 anti-trypsin
AATD	Alpha-1 anti-trypsin deficiency
Ad12SV40	Adenovirus 12-simian virus 40
AhR	Aryl hydrocarbon receptor
AKT	Protein kinase B
ALI	Air liquid interface
AQMA	Air Quality Management Area
AQS	Air Quality Strategy
AURN	Automatic Urban and Rural Network
B[a]P	Benzo[a]pyrene
BALF	Bronchoalveolar lavage fluid
BVOC	Biogenic volatile organic compound
C57BL/6	C57 black 6
cAMP	Cyclic Adenosine Monophosphate
CD8+	Cluster of differentiation 8
CH₄	Methane
CHO	Chinese Hamster Ovary Cells
CHRNA	Cholinergic Receptor Nicotinic Alpha (subunit)
CO	Carbon monoxide
COPD	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
CRAC	Calcium release-activated channels
CSC	Cigarette Smoke Condensate
CSE	Cigarette Smoke extract
CYP	Cytochrome P450
DAG	Diacylglycerol
DEFRA	Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs
DEP	Diesel engine particulate
ECL	Extracellular loop
EDT	Electronic diffusion tube
ELF	Epithelial lining fluid
ERK	Extracellular signal-regulated kinase
ETS	Environmental tobacco smoke
EV	Electric Vehicle
FBS	Foetal Bovine Serum
FDMS	Filter Dynamics Measurement System
FeNO	Fractional exhaled nitric oxide
FEV	Forced expiratory volume
FLIGRLO	2-Furoyl-LIGRLO-NH ₂
FOXJ	Forkhead box J
FVC	Forced vital capacity
GM-CSF	Granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor
GOLD	Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease
GPCR	G protein-coupled receptor
H₂S	Hydrogen sulphide
HMOX1	Heme Oxygenase 1
HPLC	High-performance liquid chromatography
ICE	Internal combustion engine
ICL	Intracellular loop
ICS	Inhaled corticosteroids
IF	Immunofluorescence

IL	Interleukin
IP3	1,4,5-trisphosphate
LABA	Long-acting beta agonist
LAMA	Long-acting muscarinic antagonists
LAQM	Local Air Quality Management
LOD	Limit of Detection
LOC	Limit of Confidence
MAPK	Mitogen-activated protein kinase
MDA	Malondialdehyde
MHC II	Major histocompatibility complex class II
MMP	Matrix metalloproteinase
MTT	3-(4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-Diphenyltetrazolium Bromide
MUC5AC	Mucin-5AC
NAQ	National air quality
NF-κB	Nuclear factor - κ B
NH₃	Ammonia
NHBE	Normal Human Bronchial Epithelium
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NMHC	Non-methane hydrocarbons
NO	Nitric Oxide
NO₂	Nitrogen Dioxide
NO_x	Nitrogen oxides
NRF2	Nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2
O₃	Ozone
PAH	Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon
PAR2	Protease activated receptor 2
PEF	Peak expiratory flow
PI3K	Phosphatidylinositol-3-kinase
PKC	Protein kinase C
PLC	Phospholipase C
PLCB3	1-Phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphate phosphodiesterase beta-3
PM	Particulate matter
POP	Persistent organic pollutants
ppb	Parts per billion
ppm	Parts per million
PVDF	Polyvinylidene difluoride
RANTES	Regulated on activation, normal T cell expressed and secreted
RhoA	Ras homolog family member A
ROS	Reactive oxygen species
SABA	Short-acting beta agonist
SAMA	Short-acting muscarinic antagonist
SAPK	Stress-activated protein kinases
SERPINA1	Serpin Family A Member 1
SIMD	Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation
SNP	Single nucleotide polymorphisms
SO₂	Sulfur Dioxide
SOD-1	Superoxide dismutase-1
SPL	Sound Pressure Level
SRM	Standard reference material
TEER	Trans epithelial/transendothelial electrical resistance
TEOM	Tapered element oscillating microbalance
TGFβ2	Transforming growth factor-beta 2
Th	T-helper

TM	Transmembrane
TNFα	Tumour necrosis factor alpha
TRPV	Transient receptor potential cation channel subfamily V
TVOC	Total volatile organic compounds
UFP	Ultrafine particles
VOC	Volatile organic compound
WHO	World Health Organisation
WT	Wild Type
ZO-1	Zonula occludens-1

1 Chapter 1- Literature Review

1.1 Introduction

Air pollution is one of the greatest environmental threats facing the global population, having been linked to 40,000 deaths with associated costs to the economy of £20 billion per annum in the UK alone (RCP, 2016). WHO has estimated that global harm attributable to ambient PM_{2.5} was equivalent to 4.2 million deaths in 2016 (Pérez Velasco and Jarosińska, 2022). Air pollution can also indirectly negatively impact populations via contribution to climate change (WHO, 2024). For instance, black carbon absorbs solar energy and emits heat, thereby warming the atmosphere additionally, air quality focus pollutants are often co-emitted with greenhouse gases (Zhang and Wang, 2011; Pinho-Gomes *et al.*, 2023). Processes such as these can lead to an increase in the number of climate change associated fatalities per annum (Amirkhani *et al.*, 2022). Usually, heightened levels of airborne pollutants leads to a direct impact on some of the most vulnerable members of populations first; namely those in early and late life stages, and those with respiratory disorders such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) (RCP, 2016).

Although improvements have been made to reduce air pollution in recent times due to legislative efforts, current monitoring system networks are insufficient to provide accurate pollutant profiles of their local authority areas. Furthermore, as these monitoring stations are expensive to develop and maintain, their use is usually limited to that of statutory bodies (Borrego *et al.*, 2016). For these reasons, there have been a number of developments in low-cost monitoring solutions which are mobile, accurate and relatively cost effective.

Recent studies have suggested that air pollution concentration measurements alone are not sufficient to gain a full insight into its detrimental effects as pollutant composition can play a role (Dergham *et al.*, 2015; Yang *et al.*, 2017). It is therefore important to investigate further the negative impacts of pollution (particularly particulate matter) components and mechanisms of action as important contributory factors. This is investigated here by considering the effects of diesel engine particulates (DEPs) (whole and aqueous / organic fractions) on lung epithelia, particularly with regard to protease activated receptor 2 (PAR2), an inflammatory modulator thought to have roles in COPD pathogenesis.

The objectives of this study are to determine the efficacy and reliability of a low-cost air pollution monitoring system and to use this system to draw conclusions about air quality in focussed remote regions where Automatic Urban and Rural Network (AURN) monitoring is sparse. Additionally, to garner conclusions regarding the effect of pollution components on cell function by studying effects of DEP on *in vitro* healthy and COPD disease models.

1.2 Historical Context and Legislative Framework of Air Pollution Control

It is thought that during the years of the industrial revolution, air pollution was first identified as a nationwide concern in the UK. Industrialisation during this period amplified coal consumption roughly six-fold and therefore release of particulate and gaseous pollutants also drastically increased, resulting in thousands of deaths due to exacerbated respiratory disease (Akatsu, 2015). After the British government officially recognised smoke as a ‘public nuisance’ in 1819, a committee was established to investigate smoke pollution and control measures; thereafter the Smoke Nuisance Abatement Act of 1821 was passed. This was likely the first air pollution control act to be applied to the entirety of the UK (Akatsu, 2015).

Following this, in response to the Great London Smog in 1952 which claimed the lives of 4,000 to 12,000 people and increased respiratory disease hospital admissions by 163% over five short days, the UK parliament passed the first Clean Air Act in 1956 ((Bell, Davis and Fletcher, 2004; Polivka, 2018). This introduced a number of measures including the implementation of Smoke Control Areas and the shift of heat source in homes to cleaner coals, electricity, and gas (Polivka, 2018).

This act was last updated in 1993 and contains definitions of pollutants which deviate from those used to define pollution control concentrations today. For instance, PM size separation categories, i.e. PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ (Legislation.gov.uk, 1993).

In 1961, shortly after the implementation of the Clean Air Act, the UK established the National Survey, the first co-ordinated network formed to monitor national levels of air pollution (DEFRA, 2011).

1.3 Overview of Automatic Urban and Rural Air Quality Monitoring Networks

It was not until the early 1970s that air pollution levels were measured using automatic analysers, then just over a decade later in 1987, the Statutory Urban

Network was established as the UK's first automatic air pollution network (DEFRA, 2006). The role of this network was to monitor air pollution levels in compliance with the European Commission Directive air quality limit values¹ (DEFRA, 2011). The Enhanced Urban Network was established in 1992 and combined with the Statutory Urban Network in 1995 forming the Automatic Urban Network (DEFRA, 2012). In 1998 this network expanded, combining 103 sites from both urban and rural monitoring networks to form the AURN. This is the largest automatic monitoring network in the UK and the current network used for reporting ambient air quality in compliance with national guidelines and EU directives (DEFRA, 2012). Alongside this there are a number of locally-managed monitoring stations (Scotland: 329 for CO, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO₂, SO₂ & O₃) (DEFRA, 2022b). These sites differ from the AURN network in that they are not bound by the criteria of the air quality directives and do not constitute part of the Defra national monitoring strategy (DEFRA, 2022b). These sites are operated by local authorities and other organisations such as airports and industrial sites and, as they do not have to align with EU regulatory site specifications, utilise a wide variety of monitoring and data handling techniques (DEFRA, 2022b). Much of the data provided from these sites is made publicly available; however, the sites are subject to many of the same limitations observed of AURN stations (static / expensive etc.) (DEFRA, 2022b).

The World Health Organisation (WHO) has developed recommended maximum limitations for a number of pollutants which have been decided based upon observed impact upon the environment and human health (WHO, 2021). Unlike the EU directives for maximum pollutant concentrations, these objectives are not legally binding. However, the Scottish Government has integrated some of the WHO guidelines into the country's air quality strategy including the PM_{2.5} objective (EEA, 2017). Limitations for Nitrogen Oxides (NO_x), Sulphur Dioxide (SO₂), Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), Carbon monoxide (CO), Lead, Benzene, 1,3-butadiene, benzo[a]pyrene (B[a]P), Particulate Matter and Ozone (O₃) have been outlined in the air quality strategy (AQS) for England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland (DEFRA, 2007). EU, WHO and National AQS limits are outlined in Table 1.1.

¹ 2008 Ambient Air Quality Directive (2008/50/EC).

To assist local authorities in carrying out their roles in controlling the pollutants stated in the AQS, the Local Air Quality Management (LAQM) regime was published as required in Part IV of the Environment Act 1995 (Scottish Government, 2023). This document states that any area which is not on course to meet the national air quality objectives by the relevant deadlines is to be designated an air quality management area (AQMA). Once an AQMA has been created, a Local Air Quality Management (LAQM) plan must be devised to counteract excessive pollutant concentrations (Scottish Government, 2023). Success in this system has been limited as there are currently 37 active AQMA areas (SO₂ n= 1, PM₁₀ n = 25, NO₂ n = 26), with only 6 revoked since 1995 (Ricardo Energy & Environment, 2022). Current AQMAs in Scotland are highlighted in Table 1.2². It is clear that more comprehensive measures must be adopted in an attempt to identify and control high levels of pollutants.

² Correct as of March 2023.

WHO Guidelines, EU Directives, and National Air Quality Objectives for Pollutant Limits**Table 1.1 – WHO guidelines, EU directives, and National Air Quality objectives for pollutant limits (WHO, 2006; WHO, 2021; DEFRA, 2007).**

Pollutant	WHO Guidelines 2005			WHO Guidelines 2021			European Directive Limit			National Air Quality Objectives		
	Objective	Maximum allowed exceedances per year	Concentration measured as	Objective	Maximum allowed exceedances per year	Concentration measured as	Objective	Maximum allowed exceedances per year	Concentration measured as	Objective	Maximum allowed exceedances per year	Concentration measured as
Particles (PM ₁₀)	50 µg/m ³	99 th percentile (3 days/year)	24 hr mean	45 µg/m ³	99 th percentile (3 days/year)	24 hr mean	50 µg/m ³	35	24 hr mean	50 µg/m ³ *	7	24 hr mean
	20 µg/m ³	n/a	Annual mean	15 µg/m ³	n/a	Annual mean	40 µg/m ³	n/a	Annual mean	18 µg/m ³ *	n/a	Annual mean
Particles (PM _{2.5})	25 µg/m ³	99 th percentile (3 days/year)	24 hr mean	15 µg/m ³	99 th percentile (3 days/year)	24 hr mean	-	-	-	-	-	-
	10 µg/m ³	n/a	Annual mean	5 µg/m ³	n/a	Annual mean	25 µg/m ³ (limit)	n/a	Annual mean	10 µg/m ³ *	n/a	Annual mean
	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Nitrogen dioxide	200 µg/m ³	n/a	1 hr mean	200 µg/m ³	n/a	1 hr mean	200 µg/m ³	18	1 hr mean	200 µg/m ³	18	1 hr mean
	40 µg/m ³	n/a	Annual mean	10 µg/m ³	n/a	Annual mean	40 µg/m ³	n/a	Annual mean	40 µg/m ³	n/a	Annual mean
Ozone	100 µg/m ³	n/a	8 hr mean	100 µg/m ³	99 th percentile (3 days/year)	8 hr mean	120 µg/m ³	25 (averaged over 3 years)	8 hr mean	100 µg/m ³	10	8 hr mean
Sulphur Dioxide	500 µg/m ³	n/a	10 min mean	500 µg/m ³	n/a	10 min mean	-	-	-	266 µg/m ³	35	15 min mean
	-	-	-	-	-	-	350 µg/m ³	24	1 hr mean	350 µg/m ³	24	1 hr mean
	20 µg/m ³	n/a	24 hr mean	20 µg/m ³	n/a	24 hr mean	125 µg/m ³	3	24 hr mean	125 µg/m ³	3	24 hr mean
	-	-	-	-	-	-	20 µg/m ³ **	n/a	Annual mean (and winter average)	20 µg/m ³ **	n/a	Annual mean (and winter average)
Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons							1 ng/m ³	n/a	Annual average	0.25 ng/m ³ B[a]P	n/a	Annual average
Benzene							5 µg/m ³	n/a	Annual average	3.25 µg/m ³ *	n/a	Running annual mean
1,3-butadiene							-	-	-	2.25 µg/m ³	n/a	Running annual mean
Carbon monoxide							10 mg/m ³	n/a	Running 8 hr mean	10 mg/m ³	n/a	Running 8 hr mean
Lead							0.5 µg/m ³	n/a	Annual mean	0.5 µg/m ³	n/a	Annual mean
						0.25 µg/m ³				n/a	Annual mean	
Nitrogen oxides							30 µg/m ³ **	n/a	Annual mean	30 µg/m ³ **	n/a	Annual mean

* Scottish Air Quality Objective; **Target Values for the Protection of Vegetation and Ecosystems

Air Quality Management Areas Within Scotland

Table 1.2 -Air quality management areas within Scotland by council area. Council areas which were excluded did not have AQMAs. Accurate as of March 2023. (Ricardo Energy & Environment, 2022).

Council Areas	NO₂	SO₂	PM₁₀
Aberdeen City	3	0	3
City of Edinburgh	5	0	1
Dundee City	1	0	1
East Dunbartonshire	1	0	1
East Lothian	1	0	0
Falkirk	2	1	1
Fife	2	0	2
Glasgow City	2	0	2
Highland	1	0	0
North Lanarkshire	0	0	6
Perth and Kinross	2	0	2
Renfrewshire	3	0	1
South Lanarkshire	1	0	2
West Lothian	2	0	3
Total	26	1	25

1.4 Introduction to Low-cost Air Monitoring Solutions

Air pollution monitoring is an important factor underpinning the implementation of evidence based control strategies by comparing with national, European and worldwide legislation and impact orientated control limitations. For the maintenance and control of air pollutant concentrations, each local authority utilises AURN monitoring equipment. This apparatus is able to accurately determine levels of pollutants such as NO_x, CO, SO₂, O₃, and PM (DEFRA, 2012). Since the equipment used to perform these measurements is expensive to purchase and maintain, their use is often limited to that of statutory bodies (Borrego et al., 2016). Additionally, as these stations are immobile, sparse and only measure select pollutants they cannot always give an accurate portrayal of the pollutant profiles within an area. AURN and locally managed air pollution monitoring stations within Dumfries and Galloway, Ayrshire and Arran and some surrounding areas are highlighted in Figure 1.1.

There are no AURN sites within the council area of Ayrshire and Arran, this is because AURN placement is decided based on EU directive specifications (DEFRA, 2022a; DEFRA, 2009). The directive requires the UK to be divided into zones and agglomerations based on population density, these areas should have a minimum of one sampling point per fixed population or area size depending on zone / agglomeration characteristics (DEFRA, 2024; European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2008). In line with this system the area of central Scotland (which Ayrshire and Arran has been classified under) has sufficient monitoring coverage for the population (DEFRA, 2024; European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2008). Dumfries and Galloway have AURN sites, which are the designated sampling areas that cover the area of the Scottish Borders, but no locally managed air quality monitoring sites (DEFRA, 2024; DEFRA, 2022a). In accordance with Part IV of the Environment Act (1995), local authorities have to periodically review air quality levels and create AQMAs where exceedances are found or expected (Dumfries and Galloway Council, 2003). In Dumfries and Galloway this is assessed via local passive monitoring (NO₂ diffusion tubes), AURN sites and air pollution modelling (Dumfries and Galloway Council, 2016). Changes in air pollution influencing factors (such as infrastructure changes) are also considered and assessed (Dumfries and Galloway Council, 2016). Recent reports have not identified any air quality concerns and, therefore, no locally managed air quality monitoring sites have been established (Dumfries and Galloway Council, 2021).

Figure 1.1 - AURN and locally managed automatic monitoring sites within Ayrshire & Arran and Dumfries & Galloway council areas of Scotland. AURN points shown in red and locally managed sites shown in green. Numbered points indicate multiple monitors within close proximity. Created using information from: (DEFRA, 2022a). Image obtained from Digimap Ordnance Survey Collection (Map scale: 1:1600000) (Accessed July 30th 2022). Correct as of March 2023.

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There have been a number of recent advances in the world of low-cost air pollution monitoring solutions, such as the development of the electronic diffusion tube (EDT) and air quality mesh filters (AQMesh). EDTs are a newly developed version of Palmes-type passive diffusion tubes which quantify gaseous pollutants such as NO₂, H₂S, O₃, CO and NH₃ in near-real time (ILL, 2016). AQMesh are more advanced, more expensive systems which can measure a number of pollutants such as PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO_x and O₃ (Table 2.2). This equipment has a low limit of detection below 10 ppb (parts per billion) and can identify particles down to 1 µm in size (Table 2.2). Together, this equipment can be used to identify a more detailed outline of the pollutant profile of an area and also to review source apportionment of focus pollutants.

1.5 Profile of Common Ambient Air Pollutants and Associated Negative Health Impacts

The UK Air Quality Strategy is updated annually and gives an overview of pollution control within the UK regarding various pollutants including; benzene, 1,3-butadiene, CO, NO_x, O₃, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and metals such as lead, cadmium, arsenic etc. Concentration limitations set within these guidelines are generally based upon their impact on a variety of factors including observed impact upon human health (DEFRA, 2018b). The main pollutants of concern considered within this study are NO_x, O₃, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5}.

1.5.1 Nitrogen Oxides

Nitrogen oxides (NO_x) are gaseous pollutants (NO & NO₂), which play an important role in biotic and abiotic systems and enter the environment *via* various natural sources; for instance, they are produced by lightning, bacterial, and volcanic action (Martin-Pozas *et al.*, 2020; Oppenheimer *et al.*, 2005; Arndt, Aulinger and Matthias, 2019). However, the most important UK atmospheric NO_x sources are industrial processes and burning of fossil fuels in internal combustion engines (DEFRA, 2021). Nitric oxide is not considered harmful under the national air quality strategy and when present under normal conditions in ambient air, is oxidised to form the secondary pollutant NO₂. Therefore, this is the gas monitored and controlled under EU directives and the Air Quality Strategy in the UK (DEFRA, 2021).

Once NO₂ is inhaled, it has been observed to induce a multitude of effects within the lung. For instance, airway inflammation was observed in a study by Wegmann *et al* whereby C57BL/6 mice were exposed to NO₂ for 14 hr per day over a duration of 25 days. Exposure to 20 ppm was associated with a significant increase in leukocyte numbers within bronchial alveolar lavage fluid (BALF). This was accompanied by reduction in measurable lung function

(mid-expiratory airflow) and the development of lesions characteristic of emphysema (Wegmann *et al.*, 2005). This association has also been indicated at lower, more typically observed concentrations. One study by Jiang *et al.* demonstrated FeNO (fractional exhaled nitric oxide), an indicator of pulmonary inflammation, was seen to increase significantly in study subjects following an increase of 10 ppb in NO₂ (lag 1 day). Impairment of lung function was also observed at day 2 following exposure, as indicated by reductions in forced expiratory volume (FEV), forced expiratory volume in 1 second (FEV₁) and peak expiratory flow (PEF) parameters (Jiang *et al.*, 2019). Oxidative stress induction is another pathway by which NO₂ exerts deleterious effects. This was illustrated in a study on primary normal human bronchial epithelium (NHBE) cells differentiated at the air-liquid interface (ALI), performed by Mirowsky and colleagues. Significant increase in expression of Heme Oxygenase 1 (HMOX1), a redox sensitive stress protein, was observed in ALI NHBE at 1 and 4 hr following 5 ppm NO₂ (2 hr) exposure (Mirowsky, Dailey and Devlin, 2016). The negative impact of NO₂ has also previously been observed on a wider scale as a 10 µg/m³ increase in daily concentration has been associated with 0.46 and 0.47 % increase in total and respiratory associated mortality respectively (Meng *et al.*, 2021).

In high concentrations within ambient air, this toxin has also been observed to increase the likelihood of developing respiratory infections and heighten the risk of hospitalisation for people with pre-existing respiratory illnesses such as asthma and COPD (Dijkema *et al.*, 2016). However, there are difficulties in quantifying the direct health impacts of NO₂ within the ambient atmosphere as particulate matter is often emitted from the same source as NO₂ release, making it difficult to determine which pollutant is the instigator of negative biological change and associated trends in an uncontrolled environment (DEFRA, 2021).

Although it has been estimated that emissions of nitrogen oxides in the UK have fallen by 32 % between 2010 and 2019, NO₂ remains one of the main pollutants of concern within the country (DEFRA, 2021; Ricardo Energy & Environment, 2022). Guidelines set out by the LAQM state that concentrations of nitrogen dioxide should have an annual maximum mean concentration of 40 µg/m³, with 1 hour means not exceeding 200 µg/m³ more than 18 times a year (DEFRA, 2021). Most of the current AQMAs (96 %) declared for NO₂ have been created because of roads that regularly exceed permitted concentrations due to exhaust emissions (DEFRA, 2021).

1.5.2 Ozone

Ozone (O_3) is a trace gas that is a vital component of the stratosphere due to the ability of this gas to absorb UV rays, but undesirable within the troposphere because of its high oxidative potential (Salonen, Salthammer and Morawska, 2018). Ozone can enter the troposphere by passing through the tropopause from the lower stratosphere, however, the vast majority of ground-level ozone is formed as a secondary pollutant by photochemical reactions of the O_3 precursors e.g. carbon monoxide (CO), VOCs, methane (CH_4) and NO_x (Paoletti *et al.*, 2014). As both VOCs and NO_x need to be present in high concentrations, the rate of ozone formation can be regulated differently dependent on precursor levels in the atmosphere of an environment (Figure 1.2). For instance, due to the high prevalence of biogenic VOCs (BVOCs) within rural areas, O_3 formation is often regulated by the presence of NO_x production. Conversely, as NO is a common pollutant within urban environments, the production rate of O_3 correlates with the production of VOCs (Paoletti *et al.*, 2014).

Figure 1.2 - Correlation between the presence of VOC and NO_x presence and production of O_3 . NMHC: non-methane hydrocarbons. Adapted from an image included in (Finlayson-Pitts and Pitts, 2000). Image created with Biorender.com.

The most common route of ozone exposure is via inhalation, and studies suggest that the greatest dose of this gas is diffused into the epithelial lining fluid (ELF) of the terminal bronchioles. The ELF acts as the first barrier for inhaled O₃ and contains antioxidants which are depleted with high concentrations of this compound; subsequently the pollutant can react with target lipids and proteins (Muttray *et al.*, 2018). It is thought that O₃ induces lipid peroxidation of polyunsaturated fatty acids, thereby generating radical species (hydrogen peroxide, H₂O₂) and aldehydes (4-hydroxynonenal) leading to enzyme inactivation, DNA damage and protein degradation (Sticozzi *et al.*, 2018, Jacob *et al.*, 2013).

This oxidative stress response also leads to the activation of pro-inflammatory responses involving mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPK), nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 (NRF2), Nuclear factor-κB (NF-κB) and the phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase protein kinase B (PI3K-AKT) pathway (Henriquez *et al.*, 2017; Lingappan, 2018). Furthermore, mRNA levels of IL-8 have been observed to increase in NHBE (ALI) following 2 hr exposure to O₃ (0.5 – 1 ppm, at 1 and 4 hr post-exposure) (Mirowsky, Dailey and Devlin, 2016). A similar increase in IL-6 expression was not observed within the same study. However, IL-6 levels (mRNA expression in epithelia and BALF protein) did increase 2 days following exposure of Wistar-Kyoto rats to 1 ppm O₃ for 4 hr (Henriquez *et al.*, 2017). Subsequently, this activation stimulates extravasation of innate immune cells into the pulmonary tissue (Henriquez *et al.*, 2017). All of these effects can lead to damage of pulmonary and bronchial cells and tissue and consequently, the development of respiratory disease. Additionally, ozone is thought to contribute to aetiology for a number of other conditions such as diabetes, neurodegenerative diseases, and cardiovascular disease (Thomson *et al.*, 2018; Miller *et al.*, 2015; Martínez-Lazcano *et al.*, 2018).

It is difficult to control levels of O₃, as this gas can accumulate and travel a long distance from the original source. Therefore, counterintuitively, reducing the production of local O₃ precursors may not reduce local levels of this pollutant, rather nationwide strategies to counteract O₃ levels would be more effective (Moghani, Archer and Mirzakhali, 2018). Additionally, it is important to focus on the reduction of both VOCs and NO_x to control O₃ concentrations. As illustrated in Figure 1.2, lowering both precursors will lower the levels of O₃. However, lowering NO_x while VOC concentrations remain stable can increase ozone production. Currently, the air quality strategy has set an upper limit for ozone concentrations

at $100 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (8-hour mean), and the national average 8 hr mean concentration has been estimated to fall between 30 to $80 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (DEFRA, 2018b).

1.5.3 Particulate matter

Particulate matter (PM) is the name given to the assortment of solid and liquid particles suspended in the air. Naturally occurring sources include pollen, dust and sea spray and man-made sources include vehicle emissions, abrasion of vehicle tyres and industrial processes such as iron and steel production (Soleimani *et al.*, 2018; DEFRA, 2021). Particulate matter is generally classified based upon size into one of three categories; particles smaller than $10 \mu\text{m}$ in aerodynamic diameter (PM_{10} , coarse particles), particles smaller than $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ in aerodynamic diameter ($\text{PM}_{2.5}$, fine particles) and particles smaller than $0.1 \mu\text{m}$ in aerodynamic diameter ($\text{PM}_{0.1}$, ultrafine particles, UFP) (Foitzik *et al.*, 2018; Martins *et al.*, 2020). Generally, particles which fit within the different size categories originate from different sources and therefore are comprised of different substances. For instance, PM_{10} is often composed of street dust, sea salt, and metal oxides of Fe, Mg, Al & Si etc., whereas $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ is often composed of particle-bound water, Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons, ammonium, nitrates, elemental carbon, organic compounds etc. (Kim, Kabir and Kabir, 2015).

The size of PM also impacts the possible effects attributable to this pollutant, and it has been theorised that PM_{10} particles typically deposit in the upper airways, whereas $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ penetrate deep into the lungs and some of these particles are small enough to cross into the bloodstream (Du *et al.*, 2016) (Figure 1.3). Once these particles travel into interstitial space and microvasculature, then they can disperse into tissues and organs, have been found to cross the placental barrier during gestation and can potentially even disrupt the integrity of the blood-brain barrier, thereby gaining access to the central nervous system (Qiu *et al.*, 2019; Luyten *et al.*, 2018; Liu *et al.*, 2015).

Figure 1.3 – Inhalation and deposition of gaseous and airborne particulate matter pollutants. Image created with Biorender.com.

An arguably more important factor than size on the health effects of particulate matter is the composition of this heterogeneous mixture (León-Mejía *et al.*, 2018). For instance, PM with different bound PAHs can display varying effects on lung function (Mu *et al.*, 2019). However, general trends have been observed when measuring PM concentrations such as an increase in morbidity and mortality of patients with respiratory diseases such as COPD and asthma with increasing concentrations of both PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} (Kelly and Fussell, 2012). Prolonged exposure can also potentially lead or contribute to the onset of both of these conditions by impacting the development of lungs during prenatal and child development stages (Mortimer *et al.*, 2008; Grigg, 2009). Furthermore, PM exposure has been linked to the development and worsening of a number of other diseases such as diabetes, ischemic heart disease, and lung cancer (Kim, 2017; Li *et al.*, 2018).

There are many factors influencing the biologically and toxicologically effective fraction of particulate matter. Disregarding particle size and composition, another factor which influences the health effects of PM exposure is the proportion of particles that are cleared from the lungs. Initial deposition rates have previously been calculated at 2.8 - 12.1 % of inhaled dose in the bronchial, bronchiolar and alveolar ductal regions and 1 - 6.5 % in the alveoli for particles from 0.1 – 2 μm in diameter (Sturm, 2020). These particles can then be removed from the lungs through mucociliary clearance, phagocytosis by macrophages, solubilisation in airway surface liquid, exit through microvasculature, or transport to lymph nodes (Wu, Bromberg and Samet, 2013).

Previous studies have demonstrated the inflammatory potential for these particulates. Increase in $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ (per 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$; local ambient PM levels Beijing) has been observed to positively correlate with biomarkers of inflammation (IL-6 & C-reactive protein) and oxidative stress (malondialdehyde, MDA). Also, negative correlation was observed between exposure and pulmonary function (reduced FEV_1 & PEF) in a panel of 30 healthy adults, 2 days following exposure (Xu *et al.*, 2022). Similar results were obtained from murine *in vivo* exposure study assessment. $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ (ambient sampled: Puzi City, Taiwan) instillation (200 μg per animal) increased pro-inflammatory response as indicated by increased TNF α and IL-6 levels in BALF. As was observed in the previous study, IL-6 release reached a peak 2 days following exposure (Lin *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, MDA levels were again elevated following exposure, indicating an oxidative stress response. Attenuation of inflammatory indicators following pre-treatment with N-acetylcysteine has indicated that findings may have been reactive oxygen species (ROS) mediated in this case (Lin *et al.*, 2022). However this is a complex factor, as studies suggest that PM-induced inflammation does not necessarily always correlate with ROS-inducing potential, and is subject to spatio-temporal directed composition influence (Dergham *et al.*, 2015).

Unlike many pollutants that are controlled by the air quality strategy and EU directives, levels of particulate matter often surpass allowed limitations (PM_{10} – 18 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (Objective Scotland), $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ – 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (figures are per annum) (DEFRA, 2021). Even though estimated UK emissions of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ & PM_{10} fell by $\sim 10\%$ each between 2010 – 2019, 66% of AQMAs declared for Scotland are for PM, either alone or in combination with NO_2 (Ricardo Energy & Environment, 2022; DEFRA, 2021).

1.5.3.1 *Metal component of PM*

It has long been observed that the composition of particulate matter is an important factor in the associated health impacts of exposure. It is thought that the metal component (particularly with regard to transition metals) of particulate matter is toxicologically significant because of their ability to generate ROS within animal cells by direct oxidation. Additionally, metal ions can convert superoxide ions and hydrogen peroxide by Fenton-type reactions into highly reactive hydroxyl radicals which can react with DNA directly. These metals perform this action by catalysing the one-electron reductions of molecular oxygen to generate free radicals. Hydroxyl radicals are produced via the Haber-Weiss reaction:

This process is broken down into sections which are catalysed by transition metals, including Fe (most abundant), Cu, Ni, V, Zn, and Co. For example:

These free radicals (particularly hydroxyl radical ($\bullet\text{OH}$), most reactive) oxidise lipids (lipid peroxidation – disrupting the cell membrane), proteins and DNA, thereby disrupting normal cell function and causing chromosomal mutations (Valko, Morris and Cronin, 2005). Furthermore, this process can inhibit defence enzymes such as superoxide dismutase; it is for these reasons it is thought that an increase in transition metal content of PM has been linked to amount of generated ROS (Hartwig, 2002).

One of the most notable epidemiological studies comparing metal content of PM with associated risk was performed by Pope (Pope, 1989), which analysed rates of mortality and hospital admission in Utah Valley during a strike at a steel mill complex. During the time of the mill closure (and also in succeeding years after reopening), total PM and metal component of PM fell. This fall was positively correlated with incidence of hospital admissions for respiratory conditions and rates of mortality within vulnerable groups. Although lead is the only metal controlled by EU directive, four metallic elements are monitored in accordance with the EU Directive 2004/107/EC (DEFRA, 2021). This legislation is referred to as ‘the Fourth Daughter Directive’ and has set limits for cadmium, arsenic and nickel, and requires the measurement of other metals such as mercury and nine other trace metals (Cd, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, Pb, Zn and V) (DEFRA, 2018c). Currently, there is insufficient knowledge on how

compound variation within particulate matter contributes to the overall observed toxic effects. Improved understanding would allow for the identification of the most deleterious components and the implementation of stringent control measures with legislative action (Lelieveld and Poschl, 2017). Further study of the action of metals (both alone and in conjunction with other pollutants) upon *in vitro* biological systems would allow for the elucidation of their toxic effects and subsequently give a tentative indication of their ‘safe’ levels. Furthermore, within individual investigations metal analysis can give an indication to pollutant source e.g. industry (Cu / Ni / V / Zn), sea salt spray (Cl / Mg / Na), soil (Al / Ca / Fe / Si), and vehicle emissions (Cu / Ba / Fe / Zn / Pb) (Khodeir *et al.*, 2012; Viana *et al.*, 2008).

1.5.3.2 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon component of PM

Alongside the inorganic fraction, another PM fraction of concern is that of organic polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons absorbed on to the surface of these particulates. These organic compounds comprise of two or more aromatic rings and are primarily emitted from origins of petrogenic (fuel), pyrogenic (incomplete combustion) and biogenic (organic metabolism) nature (Akhbarizadeh *et al.*, 2021; Lee *et al.*, 2023). PAHs and their nitrated/oxygenated forms are thought to be an important determinant of the health outcomes observed upon PM exposure. It has been observed that the organic extract of PM_{2.5} was able to induce oxidative stress, promote the production of proinflammatory cytokines in a lung epithelial cell line and disrupt epithelial barrier dysfunction integrity (Yang *et al.*, 2017). Action of these chemicals is primarily dependent on their lipophilic characteristics, allowing them to span the cell membrane *via* their function as AhR (aryl hydrocarbon receptor) ligands (Pardo *et al.*, 2020).

1.6 Understanding Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is one of the biggest health concerns facing the world’s population today and has been identified by WHO as the third leading cause of death worldwide (WHO, 2022). The Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) states that COPD is “A common, preventable and treatable disease characterised by persistent respiratory symptoms and airflow limitation” (GOLD, 2018). It is generally recognised that COPD is defined by airflow limitation which is largely irreversible (Niewoehner, 2012).

The term COPD encompasses two distinct but commonly co-occurring disorders; emphysema and chronic bronchitis (Figure 1.4). These conditions typically arise from long-term exposure of lung epithelium to irritant gases and particles such as those which comprise cigarette smoke

and airborne xenobiotics, resulting in clinical features such as cough, dyspnea and production of sputum (Sharafkhaneh, Hanania and Kim, 2008; GOLD, 2018). Exposure to these irritants contributes to the progressive airflow limitation observed in COPD by triggering small airway disease and parenchymal destruction (GOLD, 2018).

Figure 1.4: Main physiological components of COPD. COPD comprises two main commonly occurring yet distinct conditions, chronic bronchitis and emphysema, characterised by inflammation and mucus hypersecretion and the breakdown of alveolar septa respectively. Image adapted from (Barnes et al., 2015). Image created with Biorender.com.

1.6.1 Emphysema

The alveolar air sacs function as the sites for O₂ and CO₂ gas exchange within the lungs, and in emphysema these sacs lose their elasticity and enlarge. This impairs the ability of the lungs to expel air, leading to ‘gas trapping’ and lowering of the FVC and FEV₁. Unlike chronic bronchitis, which is often defined by clinical features, emphysema is identified by structural changes and the formation of bullae (permanent air pockets). Emphysema often occurs from the inflammatory response triggered by exposure to noxious particles such as that which comprise air pollutants and cigarette smoke (Weinberger, Cockrill and Mandel, 2019). These particles initiate a pro-inflammatory reaction by stimulating epithelial cells, alveolar macrophages and airway neutrophils to release chemoattractants and pro-inflammatory cytokines (such as leukotriene B₄, IL-8 and IL-6) (Mortaz *et al.*, 2010; Stockley, 2014; Bhalla *et al.*, 2009; Brinchmann *et al.*, 2018b). These signalling molecules then attract an immune cell influx from the pulmonary microcirculation (Bhalla *et al.*, 2009; Stockley, 2014). The resulting activated native macrophages and invading neutrophils & CD8⁺ lymphocytes release proteases (including elastases and collagenases), which degrade the extracellular matrix, cause elastic fibre damage, and prompt tissue remodelling (Sharafkhaneh, Hanania and Kim, 2008). This process ultimately leads to the formation of emphysematous lesions through the breakdown of septa (Stockley, 2014).

The protein alpha-1 anti-trypsin (AAT) acts to defend the lungs by inhibiting the activity of harmful proteases (especially neutrophil elastase). This thereby maintains the protease/antiprotease balance, which, when offset is thought to be the main underlying cause of emphysema (Sharafkhaneh, Hanania and Kim, 2008; Gooptu, Ekeowa and Lomas, 2009). Examples of emphysema observed in smoking patients with AAT deficiency (AATD) is a prime example of gene-environment interaction, as the disease is usually far more progressive in such patients, with earlier onset (Miravitlles *et al.*, 2003).

In accordance with the Bernoulli principle, when air is exhaled at high velocity, this creates an environment of low pressure within the airways, pulling the alveolar walls inwards. In healthy lungs, the walls of the airways are kept open by elastin, however, in lungs where there is extensive elastin loss, this low pressure pulls the walls inwards, trapping air within the alveoli (Junhasavasdikul *et al.*, 2018; Larsson, 2007). Vice versa, the lungs are more compliant, meaning that they more easily expand and a higher volume of air is trapped, leading to hyperinflation. In extreme cases patients slowly expel air through pursed lips in an attempt

to increase pressure and avoid air trapping. It is for this reason that patients with emphysema are often colloquially termed ‘pink puffers’ (Szalontai *et al.*, 2021).

Over time the amount of energy focused on breathing can lead to weight loss, and gas trapping can cause sufferers to develop a ‘barrel-shaped’ chest (Barnes, 2014). Also, septa breakdown (decreased surface area within the acinus) and interruption of gas flow can cause the development of hypoxemia, hypoxia and clinical symptoms such as dyspnea (Weinberger, Cockrill and Mandel, 2019). Additionally, inflammation triggers goblet cells within the bronchioles to produce excess mucus, small quantities of which can be coughed up as sputum (GOLD, 2018; Ma, Rubin and Voynow, 2018).

1.6.2 Chronic Bronchitis

Chronic bronchitis is diagnosed based upon chronic productive cough (lasting longer than 3 months for more than 2 consecutive years) (GOLD, 2022). The typical paradigm of chronic bronchitis is that this condition develops after susceptible individuals are repeatedly exposed to noxious particles and/or gases (GOLD, 2018). This inflammation induces bronchiolar narrowing, fibrosis, hyperplasia of goblet cells and enlargement of the submucosal glands (and subsequently an increase in mucus discharge) (Weinberger, Cockrill and Mandel, 2019; GOLD, 2018). Additionally, the airspace epithelial barrier becomes more permeable and productive cough arises, as mucus production increases while mucociliary clearance is hindered (MacNee, 2007). Together, these changes can lead to the obstruction of the airspaces and difficulty breathing, however, evidence of airway limitation is not required to make a diagnosis of chronic bronchitis (MacNee, 2007).

Due the collective pathologies leading to hypoxemia experienced by sufferers, physical manifestations such as cyanosis and associations with obesity led to the traditional classification of chronic bronchitis phenotype presenting patients as “blue bloaters” (Flenley, 1988; Spelta *et al.*, 2018).

1.6.3 Symptoms, Diagnosis and Treatments of COPD

The most common physical symptoms of COPD are dyspnea, chronic productive cough, wheezing, chest tightness, weight loss, fatigue and ankle swelling (may be the only external indicator of *cor pulmonale*) (GOLD, 2018). When symptoms persist this condition is tested for using flow spirometry, by which a patient forcibly exhales into a spirometer, then the forced vital capacity (FVC) and forced expiratory volume after 1 second (FEV₁) are recorded. A value is obtained by performing FEV₁/FVC, and the resulting ratio is compared with expected values

based upon factors such as age, sex, height and race. The results of a spirometry trace often indicate presence and level of obstruction within the airways (Figure 1.5). Nevertheless, this process is highly non-specific and therefore these results must be considered with regard to other factors such as symptoms and exposure to risk factors to avoid the risk of misdiagnosis (GOLD, 2018). Furthermore, the presence of post-bronchodilator FEV_1/FVC ratio of <0.7 allows for the confirmation of airflow limitation which is not fully reversible. Nonetheless, it has been found that this is not an effective method to determine the degree of COPD reversibility, inform therapeutic treatment or distinguish COPD from asthma (Hansen and Porszasz, 2014).

Figure 1.5 - Healthy versus obstructive spirometry example. FEV_1/FVC ratio calculation example of healthy (left) and obstructive (right) spirometry trace results. FEV_1 : Forced expiratory volume in 1 s; FVC: Forced Vital Capacity. Image adapted from: (GOLD, 2018). Image created with BioRender.com.

Presence of AAT deficiency is identified during routine screening or when an unusually young patient develops emphysema. This is assessed via a blood test to determine circulating levels of AAT; this can be followed by further testing to determine SERPINA1 gene genotyping (e.g. MZ, SZ, ZZ etc.) to identify the deficiency severity (Hernández-Pérez *et al.*, 2022).

The most effective treatment for smoking-related COPD is smoking cessation (Koga *et al.*, 2018). Although there is no cure for COPD, proper management can ease symptoms and slow deterioration. Treatments include vaccination to prevent illness that could lead to exacerbations (influenza and pneumococcal infection), and pharmacologic therapies which act to relax constricted airway smooth muscle. These include short-acting (SABA) & long-acting beta₂-agonists (LABA), and short-acting (SAMA) & long-acting (LAMA) antimuscarinics, inhaled corticosteroids (ICS) and methylxanthines; these treatments may be used both alone and in conjunction. Furthermore, other drugs that may be administered have anti-inflammatory (oral glucocorticoids, phosphodiesterase inhibitors), antimicrobial or mucous thinning (mucolytics) actions. However, each of these medications has undesirable drawbacks and long-term use is not recommended if unavoidable (GOLD, 2018).

If it is discovered that a person is suffering from AATD then this can be treated with augmentation therapy using AAT from donated healthy human volunteer blood plasma (Sandhaus *et al.*, 2016).

1.7 Factors contributing to COPD development

1.7.1 Smoking

Most cases of COPD are smoking-related and arise from inflammatory changes induced by exposure of the pulmonary epithelium to toxic particles, particularly within the small airways (Jou *et al.*, 2019). Compared to never-smokers, smokers with COPD tend to have worse symptoms, more severe disease pathogenesis, and increased systemic inflammation (GOLD, 2018). It has been estimated that roughly 50% of all smokers will eventually develop COPD within their lifetime, and after a diagnosis is made, many do not cease smoking leading to rapid disease progression and increased risk of exacerbations (Eklund *et al.*, 2012). Worldwide, most cases of COPD are caused by smoking tobacco, however, it has been estimated that between 25-45% of sufferers have no smoking history (Salvi and Barnes, 2009).

Another method by which this practice is harmful is the presence of tobacco smoke as an indoor pollutant in the form of mainstream and sidestream smoke diluted by the air within a room,

collectively referred to as environmental tobacco smoke (ETS). Passive smoking has been associated with increased risk of low birth weight (offspring of non-smoking mothers), reduced lung function in children and adults, ischemic heart disease, and lung cancer (Khader (Khader *et al.*, 2011; Bek *et al.*, 1999; Jordan *et al.*, 2011; Law, Morris and Wald, 1997; Hackshaw, Law and Wald, 1997). All of these conditions are associated with the development of, or are common co-morbidities of COPD (GOLD, 2018). During pregnancy, smoking also affects the growing foetus by impairing the development of the lungs and modulation of the immune system (GOLD, 2018). This has been witnessed *via* increased Th2 response (differentiation and Th2-associated cytokine release) to house dust mite and ovalbumin cord from blood mononuclear cells of neonates with smoking mothers (Noakes, Holt and Prescott, 2003).

Although cigarette smoke and prepared condensates are commonly studied within the context of COPD, environmental exposures are a wholly relevant but comparatively ill-considered irritant. Further studies on the action of these pollutants are needed, especially as they commonly share chemical fingerprint similarities, often containing PAHs, CO and free-radicals (Zeglinski *et al.*, 2019; Invernizzi *et al.*, 2004).

1.7.2 Genetic Predisposition

Another contributory factor which could lead to the development of COPD is the presence of a non-conservative missense mutation (c. 1096 G>A, E³⁴²K) within the SERPINA1 gene located on the long arm of chromosome 14 (q32.13) (Wan and Silverman, 2009). This gene encodes the protein AAT, a type of serine protease inhibitor of elastase (also trypsin, thrombin and chymotrypsin) - a proteolytic enzyme which digests components of the extracellular matrix such as elastin, collagens, fibronectin and laminins (Hatipoğlu and Stoller, 2016). Unregulated activity of this protease can disrupt the function of the permeability barrier of the lung and induce the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines. Unchecked neutrophil elastase degradation activity can lead to emphysema development (Hatipoğlu and Stoller, 2016; Kawabata, Hagio and Matsuoka, 2002).

There are different types of AATD which have commonly been classified by their different alleles, M meaning normal (unaltered allele), Z meaning most severe (with a single point mutation), 85% deficiency of plasma AAT (Chang and Chu, 2014), and S meaning moderate (another point mutation, c. 863A>T, D²⁶⁴V), 40% deficiency AAT) – assuming alleles are homozygous (Hatipoğlu and Stoller, 2016). Heterozygous carriers of this deficiency (MZ/MS) are more susceptible to pulmonary dysfunction than MM individuals, however, not as severely

as Z and S allele homozygotes (Janciauskiene *et al.*, 2011). Approximately 1-2 % of the worldwide COPD population is estimated to have this predisposing genetic condition and individuals with the condition are often initially diagnosed following presentation of early onset COPD or unexplained liver disease (DeMeo and Silverman, 2004). Additionally, AAT deficient individuals may be initially tested following identification of familial genetic presence (Brode, Ling and Chapman, 2012).

A number of other genes have been identified as predisposing risk factors for the development of COPD through the use of genome-wide association studies. For instance, two single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) identified within the locus 15q25 (rs8034191 & rs1051730) were significantly associated with lung function (Pillai *et al.*, 2009). As these substitutions fall within the CHRNA3 and CHRNA5 (nicotinic cholinergic receptors) loci, it has been theorised that these mutations may be linked with either smoking behaviour susceptibility or sensitivity to tobacco smoke induced emphysematous lung damage (Pillai *et al.*, 2009; Ishii and Hagiwara, 2017). A more recent study by Routhier *et al.* also identified that non-smoking individuals with another SNP in CHRNA5 (rs1696996) indicated inflammation and remodelling, hallmarks of COPD pathology also observed in the lungs of murine models expressing human rs16969968 (Routhier *et al.*, 2021). Alterations such as these have also been demonstrated to show increased susceptibility to the negative impacts of common air pollutants. This was shown by Li *et al.* by demonstrating that the previously identified COPD-predisposing variant transient receptor potential cation channel subfamily V member 4 with P19S polymorphism (TRPV4_{P19S}) had increased calcium influx signal and matrix metalloproteinase-1 (MMP1) release following exposure with diesel engine particulates (DEP). This process is thought to involve protease activated receptor 2 (PAR2), a key inflammatory mediator and protease sensor (Li *et al.*, 2011; Zhu *et al.*, 2009). Further information on the PAR2 receptor and its relevance to COPD can be found in Section 1.8.

1.7.3 Occupational Exposure

There have been many studies identifying an association between workplace airborne exposure and incidence of COPD development, even in populations without prior susceptibility to respiratory disease development (without childhood asthma or wheezy bronchitis) (Tagiyeva *et al.*, 2017). Occupational exposure elements include chemical agents, fumes and organic and inorganic dusts, and this exposure is thought to be an under-estimated risk factor in the development of COPD (GOLD, 2018). For example, a study by Hnizdo *et al.* (2002) which analysed data from the Third National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (9,823

subjects, 30-75 y/o) estimated that approximately 19.2% of total and 31.1% of never-smokers (persons whom have never smoked tobacco) had COPD attributable to workplace exposure (Hnizdo *et al.*, 2002).

One relevant example of an occupational exposure agent is coal dust generated via mining activities (Liu and Liu, 2020). Previously it has been shown that coal particulate exposure in murine models induced the recruitment of mononuclear cells and granulocytes and increased expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-6, TNF α and IL-1 β) in lung tissue homogenates (León-Mejía *et al.*, 2018). Consistent exposure to coal dust and silica can lead to the development of a number of other conditions. Alongside COPD, these include progressive massive fibrosis, coal workers' pneumoconiosis, silicosis and dust-related diffuse fibrosis and are collectively termed coal mine dust lung disease (Perret *et al.*, 2017).

Regions with historical mining are of particular interest as these areas can become respiratory disease hotspots following condition development as compounding factors such as age drive continued pathogenesis over time (Melville *et al.*, 2010).

1.7.4 Ageing

COPD is considered an ageing disease as there is a natural gradual decline in lung function over time (starting from ~20 y/o), and this process can be accelerated based on a number of factors. These include genetic predisposition, host-specific factors during development (e.g. exposure to toxic particles), and increase in total particle burden over a lifetime (elevated air pollution, smoking, workplace exposure etc.) (GOLD, 2018; Vaz Fragoso and Gill, 2010). However, it is as yet unclear whether the normal process of ageing leads to the development of COPD or if this correlation is simply due to the effect of cumulative exposures over time (GOLD, 2018). As COPD is commonly associated with ageing, this condition is becoming a greater global burden particularly in high-income countries such as the UK, because of the growing ageing population. Furthermore, as longevity increases so too does the fraction of the population which expresses the long-term effects of exposure to COPD risk factors (Mathers and Loncar, 2006).

It has been observed that there is a negative correlation between peripheral leukocyte telomere length and COPD and/or emphysema (de-Torres *et al.*, 2017). This could be because, among other factors, accelerated ageing in the lungs of COPD sufferers can result in the production of pro-inflammatory cytokine release from senescent cells, thereby worsening the condition (Barnes, 2016). Additionally, telomere attrition has been linked with increasing ambient air

pollution concentration, most likely because airborne pollutants have the ability to trigger oxidative stress in the lungs. This process is well known to accelerate telomere loss as oxidative damage within the telomeres is not repaired as sufficiently within this area when compared with the rest of the chromosome (von Zglinicki, 2002). This accelerated ageing process has been observed in various studies, one of the most notable of which is a study by Vierkötter et al (2010) which noted a trend between signs of extrinsic skin ageing (pigment spots and wrinkles) and increased concentration of particulate matter (Vierkötter *et al.*, 2010).

1.7.5 Impact of air pollution on COPD

Air pollution is a major contributor to morbidity and mortality with this ubiquitous pollutant source being linked with the approximately 12 % of all deaths in 2019 (Brauer *et al.*, 2021). This is due, in part, to the ability of airborne pollutants to contribute to the pathogenesis of respiratory conditions such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) (van Kersen *et al.*, 2020). The action of these pollutants is incompletely understood, although composition of particulate pollutants and therefore physico-chemical properties can influence observed health effects (Dergham *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, as source apportionment dictates composition, both local and transboundary contributors are important factors in remediation focussed strategies (Kim *et al.*, 2016).

Due to high populations and structural elements such as high-rise multi-storey buildings which reduce wind clearance and increase pollution concentrations through anomalies such as the canyon effect³, urban areas are a common focus for pollution sampling and epidemiological respiratory effect studies (Adamkiewicz *et al.*, 2014; Alotaibi *et al.*, 2019). However, there is growing evidence which suggests that rural and semi-rural areas have air pollution elements present which have the potential to exacerbate or even drive COPD development. Biogenic and anthropogenic sources of common pollutants and example evidential links with COPD prevalence and exacerbation are outlined in Table 1.3.

³ The urban canyon effect is defined as the influence of street architecture on surrounding airflow. Large building obstruct the movement of air and this stagnation promotes the build up of locally released pollutants (Farrell *et al.*, 2015)

Sources of Common Pollutants and Epidemiological COPD Health Association

Table 1.3 – Typical sources of common ambient air pollutants and epidemiological evidence linking exposure to the pathogenesis of COPD.

Pollutant	Common Sources	Evidential link with COPD
PM	<p>Anthropogenic :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vehicular exhaust and non-exhaust (brake wear, tyre wear, suspended road dust particles etc.) emissions (Harrison et al., 2021) • Residential biomass burning (Daellenbach et al., 2020) • Industry (fuel burning, process emissions) • Domestic fuel burning • Unspecified sources of human origin (Karagulian et al., 2015) <p>Biogenic :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crystal dust • Sea salt (Karagulian et al., 2015) • Marine dust • Pollen • Forest fire • Volcanic activity (Mukherjee and Agrawal, 2017) • Particles formed from gaseous precursors (e.g. sulphates) <p>Secondary PM produced from anthropogenic and biogenic primary emissions.</p>	<p>Prevalence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ increase in $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ was associated with elevated COPD prevalence (OR 1.12) and lower FEV_1 (-83.13 ml) & FVC (-62.62 ml) (Doiron et al., 2019). <p>Exacerbation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ increase in $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ was associated with an increase in COPD related hospitalisations (3.1 %) and mortality (2.5%) (Li et al., 2016).
NO_2	<p>Anthropogenic :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vehicular exhaust • Industry • Heating installations <p>Biogenic :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture • Forest fires • Biogenic emissions • Photogenic destruction of nitrogen compounds within the upper atmosphere (Zoran et al., 2020) 	<p>Prevalence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ increase in NO_2 was associated with an increase in COPD development (HR 1.11) (Liu et al., 2021). <p>Exacerbation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For each inter-quartile range increase of NO_2, same-day hospitalisation for COPD exacerbation increased (RR 1.036) (Liang et al., 2019).
Tropospheric O_3	<p>Biogenic :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest fire • Stratospheric intrusion • Biogenic emissions (Zhang et al., 2017) <p>As a secondary pollutant, ozone levels can be influenced by reactions between both biogenic and anthropogenic source precursors; NO_x and VOCs (Wałaszek, Kryza and Werner, 2018)</p>	<p>Exacerbation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concentrations of ozone $>10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ were linked with 2 % of COPD related hospital admissions from 2011 - 2012 (Ghanbari Ghosikali et al., 2016)

1.7.5.1 Air pollution within semi-rural areas

Signatures of air pollution, both particulate and gaseous within remote and semi-rural areas are a growing focus as these locations contain pollutants which are commonly found within urban areas alongside a unique signature of elevated pollutants (Kundu and Stone, 2014; Hendryx, Fedorko and Halverson, 2010). Furthermore, ubiquitous pollutants such as ground-level ozone have been observed at levels higher than those observed within comparator urban areas (Finch and Palmer, 2020). This is due to long-range transboundary travel of this pollutant and its precursors alongside dynamics of air pollution formation (Finch and Palmer, 2020). This is an important factor when considering ozone exposure has been associated with a dose and duration dependent reduction in FEV₁, FVC, and total capacity, which can lead to irreversible airway remodelling (Mudway and Kelly, 2000). Additionally, it has been observed that pollutants which can occur within these areas locally or through transboundary transport, from local cities or even other continents, can react with local naturally occurring biogenic volatile organic compounds (VOCs), after which these compounds can substitute for anthropogenic VOCs in the process of ozone formation (Stefánik *et al.*, 2020; Zhao *et al.*, 2022).

It is to be noted that not all pollution concentrations observed within regions are formed through passive locally unavoidable processes and site specific anthropogenic activities can also cause concern (ApSimon *et al.*, 2021). As the demand for produce steadily increases over time so too does the need for agricultural operations, a staple characteristic of many rural areas (Garvey *et al.*, 2021), which subsequently increase the emission of unwanted compounds such as ammonia and nitrous oxides (NO_x) as by-products (Krol *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, the release of NO_x arises from sources such as fertilisers, off-road vehicles / machinery and biomass boilers (Kelleghan *et al.*, 2021; Mitchell *et al.*, 2017; DEFRA, 2019), while methane is released as an emission from livestock & grass silage and hydrogen sulphide is commonly released from animal decomposition of manure (Mehta *et al.*, 2022; Park *et al.*, 2020). As air pollution control measures lead to the reduction in majority source combustion emissions, these other sources make up an increasing percentage of UK originating nitrogen-containing compounds (DEFRA, 2018a). Another compound of interest which arises from agricultural practices are common use pesticides and fungicides, some of which are of particular concern as they are known persistent organic pollutants (POPs) (Hillocks, 2012). Further to the effects these compounds display on respiratory function, they characteristically negatively impact human health, persist for extended periods of time and their specific properties can lead to bioaccumulation (Ye *et al.*, 2013; Guo *et al.*, 2018).

Aside from gaseous pollutants, airborne particulates pose a risk to the global population (as previously described). Due to their tendency for long-range transport, particulates can be found anywhere in their primary (directly emitted) or secondary state (through nucleation of gases or formed from secondary reactions with other pollutants) (Cambra-López *et al.*, 2010). The agriculture sector is a key primary emission source of solid pollutants through the regular production of ammonium particulates, dust and bioaerosols. These originate from many of the same sources as that of the gaseous pollutants of concern (Cambra-López *et al.*, 2010). Other sources of PM include sea-salt spray, wildfires and emissions shared with other region (e.g. urban) classifications including domestic emissions such as wood burning stove particulates (Viana *et al.*, 2014; ApSimon *et al.*, 2021).

Location of aforementioned remote areas is important because this can also impact the observed pollution profile. For instance, coastal regions are subject to both marine emissions, anthropogenic activity and meteorological phenomena (Knipping and Dabdub, 2003). Chloride can react with local anthropogenic pollution and form tropospheric ozone (Knipping and Dabdub, 2003). This is additionally hazardous as many seaside remote regions can become increasingly populated in temperate conditions which drive higher concentrations of O₃ (Dueñas *et al.*, 2002). Biogenic emissions from local flora are also another important factor to consider as these can create a 'NO_x limited' environment; this is particularly important in semi-rural and remote regions with both urban and rural features. In this case, a sudden excess of NO_x emissions could lead to a large increase in O₃ concentrations under favourable conditions (Mitchell, Wiacek and Ashpole, 2021; Sicard *et al.*, 2020). This can contribute to 'weekend effect' which is commonly observed within populated cities as, in rural locations, there are not high enough levels of NO_x to maintain equilibrium between the two gases and degrade O₃ levels, which originate from local and non-local sources (Sicard *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, as with all air pollution exposures it must be considered that air pollution does not necessarily remain outdoors, and higher levels of pollutants can concentrate in closed spaces such as homes and vehicles (Panchal *et al.*, 2022b; Leung, 2015). All of these factors can influence the regional air pollution signature and potential effects on the vulnerable, including those with respiratory conditions.

The pathogenesis of many cases of COPD are driven by exposure to irritants, the most commonly observed of which is cigarette smoke. Much less studied is the effect of air pollution on this condition, especially as there are many cases of COPD which do not originate from tobacco smoke exposure (Salvi and Barnes, 2009). Additionally, much of the research which

does investigate the effect of environmental ambient pollution focusses on urban areas; however, there are some studies which have identified rural area specific exposures as a source of potential COPD pathogenesis, these are listed in Table 1.4. Many of these have a central focus of agricultural workplace exposures as opposed to collective air pollution influence in remote / semi-rural areas.

Table 1.4 - Epidemiological and panel studies with a focus on rural-related exposures and COPD outcomes. References: (van Kersen et al., 2020; Bailey et al., 2005; Rinsky et al., 2019; Rodríguez et al., 2008; Post et al., 2021; Eduard, Pearce and Douwes, 2009; Pourhassan et al., 2019).

Title	Reference	Location	Period	Participants	Ages	Pollutant(s)	Air Pollution Measurement	COPD outcome	Main COPD findings
Acute respiratory effects of livestock-related air pollution in a panel of COPD patients	Van Kersen, 2020	The Netherlands	Between February 2015 & July 2016	82 participants separated into groups by COPD definitions: (1) post-bronchodilator FEV ₁ / FVC of > 0.7; (2) pre-bronchodilator FEV ₁ / FVC of >0.7; (3) self reported clinician diagnosis of emphysema / bronchitis	Average age 61.4 years	NH ₃ & PM ₁₀	Dutch Air Quality Monitoring Network, daily levels was calculated from the mean of two measurement stations. The average distance from a participant's home address was 23 km.	During 3 month period, participant spirometry measurements were collected twice daily (morning and evening); FEV ₁ & PEF.	Decrements in FEV ₁ were associated with 12 µg/m ³ increase in NH ₃ concentration (lag 2) (OR 1.14, 95% CI)
Agricultural exposures in Patients with COPD in Health Systems Serving Rural Areas	Bailey et al, 2005	Nebraska, United States	November 2004 to March 2005	150 veterans with COPD. Patients had FEV ₁ /FVC ratio of <70% and FEV ₁ <80%	Mean age 68.2 years	Agricultural exposures	Self reported presence or absence of agricultural exposure	High percentage of patients with COPD had a history of agricultural exposure	68.2 % of participants with COPD had a history of agricultural exposure
Animal production, insecticide use and self-reported symptoms and diagnoses of COPD, including chronic bronchitis, in the Agricultural Health Study	Rinsky et al, 2019	Iowa and North Carolina, United States	1993 - 2010	24,171 agricultural workers	Median age 59 years (range: 27-97 years)	Agricultural exposures (raising and not raising animals) and insecticide use	Self reported use of insecticides and raising or non-raising animal operations	Self-reported COPD diagnosis and / or symptoms	Animal production work including insecticide use was positively correlated with self-reported chronic bronchitis symptoms
Impact of Occupational Exposure on Severity of COPD	Rodríguez et al, 2008	Barcelona, Spain	March 2002 - January 2004	185 male patients with confirmed COPD and / or emphysema that visited a specialised outpatient unit within a tertiary care hospital	Mean age, 66.2	Occupational exposures (biological dust, mineral dust, gas & fumes, Dusts or gas & fumes)	Patient self-reported in interviewer-led questionnaire	COPD diagnosed in patients according to the Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease criteria. This was performed with post-bronchodilator therapy FEV ₁ / FVC ratio of < 0.7. COPD was then classified into one of four categories depending on percentage of outcome prediction	< 30 % of predicted compared with < 70 % of predicted FEV ₁ was significantly associated with occupational exposures to mineral dusts, and exposure to dusts, gases or fumes. FEV ₁ reduction was also found more frequently in exposed patients although this correlation was not found to be statistically significant
Proximity to livestock farms and exposure to livestock-related particulate matter are associated with lower probability of medication dispensing for obstructive airway diseases	Post et al, 2021	The Netherlands	2016	7,735,491 persons in the Netherlands	6,175,717 adults, 1,228,242 children (6-17 y/o) and 25,727 children >6	Agricultural exposures	Exposures calculated as distance from home address to farming areas, modelled livestock PM ₁₀ concentrations and adjusted for PM ₁₀ concentration of non-farming related pollution	Dispensing of drugs prescribed for obstructive airway disease (Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical classification R03)	Increased concentrations of agricultural PM ₁₀ was associated with lower R03 drug dispensing probability

Title	Reference	Location	Period	Participants	Ages	Pollutant(s)	Air Pollution Measurement	COPD outcome	Main COPD findings
Chronic Bronchitis, COPD, and Lung Function in Farmers: The Role of Biological Agents	Eduard et al, 2009	Norway	1991	4735 farmers (atopy assessed in 1,213 participants)	49 y/o, mean	Agricultural exposures	Self-reported (questionnaire) exposure details of livestock, crop and dairy farming. Exposures measured from 127 farms during routine tasks (tending livestock, handling harvest and handling manure) (30 samples gathered per task, sampling time < 1 hr per task session). From physical samples measurements were obtained of: dust, fungal & actinomycete spores, bacteria, endotoxins, storage mites, organic & inorganic dusts, glucans. Values of ammonia and hydrogen sulfide personal exposure measurements were also obtained.	Respiratory symptoms and lung function assessed in participants. Spirometry was used to determine COPD (defined by 5 % LLN) FEV ₁ / FVC ratio (pre-bronchodilator). Questionnaires were administered were chronic bronchitis was defined as "cough and phlegm 3 months or more per year during the last 2 years". Asthma was defined as current (physician) diagnosed asthma	Significantly higher prevalence of chronic bronchitis and COPD (FEV ₁ defined) found in livestock farmer group when compared with crop farmers. All livestock farmers were at greater risk of chronic bronchitis, and those raising more than one type of livestock had a significantly increased risk of COPD and chronic bronchitis. Dairy farmers had significantly elevated risk of COPD. Exposure to most agents was associated with chronic bronchitis and some agents with COPD. Atopy (assessed via identification of IgE specific against a panel of common aeroallergens. Atopy was associated with a lower FEV ₁ value. Exposure and COPD positive association was mainly limited to farmers with atopy.
Risk of obstructive pulmonary diseases and occupational exposure to pesticides: a systematic review and meta-analysis	Pourhassan et al, 2019	Europe	1991 – 2012	3343 participants of the general population, 89 with COPD at follow up assessment	20-44 y/o in 1991-1993	Occupational exposure	Follow up-interview with participants included detailed list of occupations since initial study commencement. ICSO-88 occupation codes were linked with ALOHA (+) Job-Exposure Matrix to estimate exposure (3 grades, high, medium, none) to 10 agent categories including biological dusts, herbicides, insecticides and pesticides	Incidence of COPD determined with post bronchodilator lung function evaluation	COPD incidence was positively associated with exposure to biological dust, gases and fumes when compared to unexposed participants

Although there is evidence to suggest a link between COPD and air pollution within a semi-rural / remote location context, there are many studies which contrast with these findings. For instance, one study carried out by Van Kersen *et al.* found a negative correlation between a COPD related outcome (FEV₁ reduction) with an increase in livestock related air pollution (NH₃ concentration level) (van Kersen *et al.*, 2020). Conversely, another study performed within the same region, during the same period found an inverse correlation between obstructive airway disease medication dispensing and agricultural air pollution exposure (modelled livestock-related PM₁₀) (Post *et al.*, 2021). One possible reason for disparities observed between these studies could be that individual exposures of participants are difficult to determine; also the former study may have a higher percentage of vulnerable groups than the latter (van Kersen *et al.*, 2020; Post *et al.*, 2021; Nordeide Kuiper *et al.*, 2021).

Additionally, there may be confounding factors such as the synergistic action of different pollutants and varying particulate composition, which is not accounted for by merely considering PM concentration alone (Huang *et al.*, 2012; Cakmak *et al.*, 2014). Previously, studies have demonstrated that factors such as spatial and temporal variation have influenced the composition of PM and therefore pro-inflammatory and oxidative stress inducing properties in a lung epithelial cell line (Dergham *et al.*, 2015). For these reasons, it is imperative that further insight is obtained on the individual and combined action of different pollutant components observed within *in vitro* and *in vivo* systems. The current evidence suggests that there is a significant risk posed by air pollutants, however, the source and composition of this pollution has a major role in associated risks (Cakmak *et al.*, 2014). This would suggest that there are benefits to determining effects of pollutants within simple cell systems (cell culture monolayers of immortalised and primary cells), more physiologically relevant 3D cultures (e.g. bronchospheres and air-liquid interface cultures) and *in vivo* systems (model organism outcomes). In this way individual and combined pollutant action could be determined in a closed environment, thereby reducing the observed modulatory factors not accounted for within determined exposure studies (Zavala *et al.*, 2020). Although air pollution must be considered as a whole, underlying mechanisms of action is an important aspect when considering contribution to COPD pathogenesis.

1.8 Protease activated receptor 2

Protease activated receptors (PARs) are a family of ubiquitously expressed G protein-coupled seven-transmembrane domain receptors which comprise of PAR 1 – 4 (Bang, Kim and Chung, 2021; Sébert *et al.*, 2019). These receptors lack a traditional ligand and are activated by certain

serine proteases by proteolytic cleavage of the N-terminal peptide revealing a tethered ligand neopeptide. This ligand then interacts with the second extracellular loop (ECL2), leading to a conformational change in the receptor and initiating a downstream cascade (Adams *et al.*, 2011) (Figure 1.6). These sensors are recognised for their roles in modulating inflammation and therefore are of interest in diseases with characteristic chronic inflammation such as COPD (Lee *et al.*, 2018). PAR2 itself is activated by trypsin and tryptase, but other activators include tissue kallikreins, coagulation factor Xa and VIIa and transmembrane serine proteases (Shavit-Stein *et al.*, 2017). Additionally, it is understood that PAR2 can be trans-activated by PAR1 through binding of the tethered ligand of the N-terminal domain (Lin and Trejo, 2013). Also, artificially produced activation peptides such as 2-Furoyl-LIGRLO-NH₂ (FLIGRLO) and SLIGKV-NH₂ were developed to mimic the natural tethered ligand sequence (Adams *et al.*, 2011). Utilising these soluble peptides, it is possible to study downstream effects of PAR2 activation without cleavage of other PARs and/or surface proteins (Gardell *et al.*, 2008).

Figure 1.6 – PAR2 structure and site of serine protease cleavage (Ser37-Arg36 (red)). Serine proteases cleave the N-terminal sequence and the resulting tethered ligand binds with the second extracellular loop (ECL, green) inducing conformational change and downstream activation. ICL: Intracellular loop. $\alpha\beta\gamma$: PAR2 bound G proteins. Image created with BioRender.com.

Following activation induced conformational change, PAR2 initiates G-protein signalling. This recruits β -arrestin 1 and 2 that act to desensitise the receptor *via* mediation of surface receptor endocytosis. Following internalisation PAR2 is trafficked through late and early endosomes before ubiquitination and lysosome degradation (Adams *et al.*, 2011). Re-sensitisation of the receptor occurs following recycling of the naïve receptor from the Golgi apparatus and synthesis of new receptors (Böhm *et al.*, 1996).

Canonical PAR2 signalling is mediated via heterotrimeric G α protein subunits Gq, G_{12/13}, Gs (Soh *et al.*, 2010). These subunits mediate different signalling cascades upon PAR2 activation: G_{12/13} initiates the Rho signalling pathway which is involved in cytoskeletal reorganisation (Suzuki, Hajicek and Kozasa, 2009); G_q mediates activation of phospholipase C enzymes, which leads to hydrolysis of phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate to form the secondary messengers diacylglycerol (DAG), and inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate (IP₃) (Fisher *et al.*, 2020). This results in the activation of protein kinase C (PKC), the mobilisation of intracellular calcium stores and downstream activation of the transcription factor NF- κ B (Fisher *et al.*, 2020; Kanke *et al.*, 2001). Alongside this, activation has been observed in MAPK components extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK), p38 MAPK and Jun N-terminal kinase (Heuberger and Schuepbach, 2019; Zeng *et al.*, 2013). The MAPK/NF- κ B signalling pathways are central to pro-inflammatory cytokine release and therefore are pivotal in the action of PAR2 (Nakayama *et al.*, 2013).

PAR2 activation can also occur in a “biased” manner, for instance when proteases such as neutrophil elastase and macrophage cathepsin S cleave the external ligand of PAR2 at a site distinct from the activation site. The resulting tethered ligand can initiate a distinct downstream cascade which does not involve interaction with β -arrestins or subsequent endocytosis, and appears to be independent of intracellular calcium signalling whilst still triggering MAPK pathway activation (Jimenez-Vargas *et al.*, 2018). Due to the mechanism of activation the receptor remains at the cell surface, but is no longer subject to activation *via* other ligand mediated activation processes (Ramachandran *et al.*, 2011). Canonical (classical), biased and peptide mediated activation mechanisms of PAR2 are highlighted in Figure 1.7.

Figure 1.7 – Classical, biased, and peptide mediated PAR2 activation mechanisms. Canonical activation of PAR2 (left) involves the proteolytic cleavage of the external ligand revealing a tethered ligand. This ligand then binds with the second extracellular loop of the molecule initiating signalling via $G_{\alpha q}$ followed by $PLC\beta$ activation, intracellular calcium mobilisation and MAPK (ERK / SAPK) phosphorylation. This leads to pro-inflammatory cytokine release. During this process, β -arrestin recruitment leads to internalisation, trafficking and degradation of the PAR2 molecule. Peptide activation of PAR2 (middle) occurs when peptides which mimic the sequence of the tethered ligand bind with the second extracellular loop of PAR2 thereby leading to activation without the cleavage of the extracellular ligand. This process also leads activation of secondary messengers and cellular responses. Biased activation of PAR2 (right) is triggered when proteases such as neutrophil elastase or macrophage cathepsin S cleave the external ligand at a site distinct from the activation site preventing further activation by proteolytic enzymes. During this process the MAPK pathway can still be activated in a Ca^{2+} mobilisation independent manner and, as Beta arrestins are not recruited, these molecules remain on the cell surface. (Adams *et al.*, 2011; Soh *et al.*, 2010; Fisher *et al.*, 2020; Heuberger and Schuepbach, 2019; Pan *et al.*, 2008; Nakayama *et al.*, 2013; Jimenez-Vargas *et al.*, 2018; Ramachandran *et al.*, 2011). Image adapted from (Ramachandran *et al.*, 2012). Image created with BioRender.com.

PAR2 pathway activation has been observed in various studies which have indicated a role for the receptor in the pathophysiology of a number of inflammation-linked conditions including rheumatoid arthritis, asthma and COPD (McCulloch *et al.*, 2018; Palikhe *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, there are tentative links between PAR2 and COPD, warranting further investigation of the receptor in disease development and progression.

1.8.1 PAR2 in COPD

COPD and PAR2 have been linked as this protein is expressed on lung epithelia and has been observed at elevated levels in lung homogenates and epithelial cells from diseased patients (Lee *et al.*, 2018). Many studies have focussed on investigating a putative role for PAR2 in COPD as enhanced / abnormal inflammation is a hallmark of disease pathology, and PAR2 modulates inflammation *via* pro-inflammatory cytokine release (Cazzola *et al.*, 2012; Avet *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, studies suggest a role for PAR2 in mucin secretion, which could be a contributory factor in the mucus hypersecretion characteristic of chronic bronchitis (Lin *et al.*, 2008; Lee *et al.*, 2012). Aside from a suggested pathological role, other studies have suggested a protective function of PAR2. For instance, one study by Miotto *et al.* found that symptomatic smokers without airway obstruction displayed an increase in PAR2 expression within central airways when compared with smokers with COPD, suggesting a role for the receptor in prevention of chronic airway obstruction (Miotto *et al.*, 2002). Additionally, some evidence exists which has linked the disease modifiers ‘cigarette smoke’ and ‘diesel engine particulates’ (DEP) with the expression and activation of PAR2 (potentially via a transactivation method), respectively, however, further investigation is required to understand this axis (Brinchmann *et al.*, 2018b; Lee *et al.*, 2018).

It has been observed that PAR2 is expressed on the basolateral membrane of human bronchial epithelial cells differentiated at the air-liquid interface (McMahon *et al.*, 2018). In fully differentiated cultures of primary human nasal cells (ALI, 21 days), apical FLIGRLO was ineffective in stimulating a typically observed calcium influx, however, basal FLIGRLO stimulation was observed in a dose-dependent manner. Nevertheless, stimulations of PAR2 in a physiologically relevant disease model can still lead to receptor activation. Apical stimulation was confirmed when epithelial cells were cultured in the presence of a panel of disease modifying factors including IL-13, cigarette smoke condensate and retinoic acid deficiency, although this was not due to decreased epithelial barrier integrity (confirmed by transepithelial electrical resistance) but altered PAR2 polarisation. This suggests that a primary method of exogenous activation of PAR2 in the human airway acts *via* airway remodelling (Carey *et al.*, 2020). Further studies are required to understand the role of PAR2 in COPD.

1.9 Hypothesis & Aims

The central hypotheses of this study are that air pollution within remote areas can contribute to disease pathogenesis in remote COPD hotspot regions and that a common air pollutant (PM) can trigger key processes associated with COPD pathogenesis in human lung epithelia.

Specifically, this study focusses on a cell surface receptor PAR2 implicated in COPD pathogenesis and a role for diesel engine particulates (common ubiquitous pollutant) in receptor activation.

The **aims** of this study are as follows:

- Determine if a low-cost monitoring solution (AQMesh) presents a viable method of air pollution analysis in urban and remote locations.
- Identify air pollution levels within remote (non-urban) areas and determine if these could be a contributory factor to exacerbation and pathogenesis of COPD with reference to UK, Scottish, WHO, and EU guideline / regulation limits.
- Determine if diesel engine particulates and components can induce pro-inflammatory effects within immortalised, primary and pseudostratified models of human lung epithelia.
- Investigate a potential role of PAR2 in the axis of DEP induced inflammation.

2 Chapter 2 –Methodology

2.1 Specification and Calibration of AQMesh Air Quality Monitoring System

2.1.1 AQMesh specifications

Figure 2.1 – AQMesh air monitoring pod affixed to fencing post and column.

Air quality readings within this project were obtained using an AQMesh air quality measurement instrument obtained from ACOEM UK (AQMesh pod serial no. 121850). The AQMesh is a compact air quality monitoring system with the ability to measure and record air quality measurements on a real-time basis. All data from AQMesh monitoring pods was transmitted remotely from the monitor to the AQMesh secure server for data processing. Readings can be viewed and downloaded remotely via a password protected account (<https://www.airmonitors.net/>) and linear regressions can be performed for calibration easily by selecting calibration period, from this the offset can be automatically set and manual calculation is not required. AQMesh pods can be purchased to specifications and measure pollutants highlighted in Table 2.1, Table 2.2 & Table 2.3. Specifications highlighted in red are those which have been included in the unit with which this study was undertaken.

Gaseous Pollutants AQMesh specifications

Table 2.1 – Gaseous pollutants measurements and measurement specifications recreated from Environmental Instruments Ltd. Sensors which were included in the unit utilised within this study are highlighted in red (Environmental Instruments Ltd., 2022).

Sensor	Type	Units	Range	LOD ⁴	LOC ⁵	Precision ⁶	Accuracy ⁷	Sensor Serial No.
NO	Electrochemical	ppb	0 – 20,000 ppb	<1 ppb	<5 ppm	>0.9	1 ppb	160360460
NO ₂	Electrochemical	ppb	0 – 20,000 ppb	<1 ppb	<5 ppb	>0.85	4 ppb	202363402
NO _x	Electrochemical	ppb	0 – 40,000 ppb	<2 ppb	<10 ppb	>0.9	4 ppb	n/a
O ₃	Electrochemical	ppb	0 – 20,000 ppb	<1 ppb	<5 ppb	>0.9	5 ppb	245500916
CO		ppb	0 – 1,000,000 ppb	<50 ppb	<50 ppb	>0.8	20 ppb	n/a
SO ₂	Electrochemical	ppb	0 – 100,000 ppb	<5 ppb	<10 ppb	>0.7	20 ppb	n/a
H ₂ S	Electrochemical	ppb	0 – 100,000 ppb	<1 ppb	<5 ppb	>0.7	1 ppb	n/a
TVOC	Electrochemical	ppm	0 – 2.5 ppm	<0.1 ppm	<0.25 ppm	>0.95	50 ppb	n/a
CO ₂	NDIR	ppm	0 – 5,000 ppm	<1 ppm	<1 ppm	>0.9	30 ppm	n/a

⁴ Limit of detection

⁵ Limit of confidence

⁶ Reproducibility of AQMesh measurements compared with a reference-grade monitor under the same environmental conditions.

⁷ Variation between sensor measurements against that of a reference-grade air quality monitor.

Particulate Matter AQMesh specifications

Table 2.2 – Particulate pollutant measurements and measurement specifications recreated from Environmental Instruments Ltd. Sensors which were included in the unit utilised within this study are highlighted in red (Environmental Instruments Ltd., 2022).

Sensor	Type	Units	Range	LOD	Precision	Accuracy
PM ₁	Optical counter	particle µg/m ³	0-100,000 µg/m ³	0 µg/m ³	>0.9	5 µg/m ³
PM _{2.5}	Optical counter	particle µg/m ³	0-150,000 µg/m ³	0 µg/m ³	>0.9	5 µg/m ³
PM ₄	Optical counter	particle µg/m ³	0 – 225,000 µg/m ³	0 µg/m ³	>0.9	5 µg/m ³
PM ₁₀	Optical counter	particle µg/m ³	0-250,000 µg/m ³	0 µg/m ³	>0.9	5 µg/m ³
Total PM	Optical counter	particle µg/m ³	0-350,000 µg/m ³	0 µg/m ³	>0.9	5 µg/m ³

Additional Measurements

Table 2.3 – Parameter measurements obtained by standard and accessory sensors recreated from Environmental Instruments Ltd.¹ Voltage readings observed during AQMesh pod usage over duration of study. Values listed here as n/a were not included in the information provided for the AQMesh pod. Sensors which were included in the unit utilised within this study are highlighted in red (Environmental Instruments Ltd., 2022).

Sensor	Type	Units	Range	LOD	Precision / Resolution	Accuracy
Pod temperature	Solid state	°C	-20 to 100 °C	0.1 °C	>0.9	2°C
Pressure	Solid state	mb	500 to 1500 mb	1 mb	>0.9	5 mb
Humidity	Solid state	%	0 to 100 %	1% RH	>0.9	5% RH
Noise	Omnidirectional microphone	dB	35 to 100 dB SPL	20 Hz – 20 kHz	>0.8	1 dB
Wind speed	Solid state	ms ⁻²	0 to 30 ms ⁻²	n/a	0.01 ms ⁻²	2%
Wind direction	Solid state	° degrees	0 to 359 °	n/a	1	2 °
Pod voltage	n/a	V	0 to 3.6 V ¹	n/a	n/a	n/a

2.1.1.1 AQMesh Physical Parameters

The AQMesh is lightweight (<2.5 kg) and compact (160 x 220 x 180 (230 including antenna) mm) and therefore simple to transport and mount within calibration cages or onto a lighting column or pole. An image of the AQMesh is illustrated in Figure 2.1.

2.1.1.2 AQMesh Lithium Battery and Power Parameters

The lithium battery life, in the case of this unit, lasted roughly 6 months but manufacturers claim battery life can last up to 2 years. This reduction in life span in the case of this study is due to the frequency of pollution measurement obtained as highlighted in Table 2.4.

Sampling specifications of AQMesh Pod

Table 2.4 – Sampling specifications of AQMesh pod, samples and sampling frequency.

Sample	Frequency
Gas reading	10 seconds
Gas averaging	15 minutes
Gas transmission	1 hour
Particle averaging frequency	Undefined
Particle averaging	15 minutes
Particle transmission	1 hr

It is important to note that when the AQMesh monitor started to show indication of power loss (voltage reduction) we observed that particulate matter measurements were no longer sampled, whereas, gas measurements continued. This is illustrated in Figure 2.2 and Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.2 –PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ measurement traces (red) obtained during power loss from the battery within the AQMesh air quality pod monitor. Power is indicated here by the voltage (black traces) within the pod. Values shown here of PM are raw uncorrected values without offset applied

Figure 2.3 – NO and NO₂ measurement traces (green) obtained during power loss from the battery within the AQMesh air quality pod monitor. Power is indicated here by the voltage (black traces) within the pod. Values of Nox shown here are raw uncorrected values without offset applied.

Under usual circumstances the battery would have been replaced and this failure would not have been observed. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic and travel restriction limitations battery replacement at times was not possible and had to be carried out by an ACOEM engineer with a permit for essential travel. During the lead time for this the battery lost power as indicated by voltage measurements.

This observation is likely due to higher power requirement of the particulate matter sensor over the gaseous sensors. Pollution measurements were obtained via two methods. Firstly gaseous pollutants were measured using electrochemical sensors which generate an electrical output following interaction with a target gas. Secondly, particulates were measured by optical particle counters. These counters pump air samples into the monitor, where they pass through the path of an optically focussed laser.

As individual particles traverse the path of the laser it is deflected and this deflection is detected by an optical sensor. This information is then used to determine size and count of particles and measurements are recorded.

2.1.2 AQMesh Calibration

Once received from ACOEM, the AQMesh monitors show some level of calibration, however, co-location with another monitor improves the accuracy of sampling. During the sampling period from 2019 to 2022 there were 2 locations of calibration against reference monitors: Gordon St. Paisley and Irvine High St these calibration periods and other factors which influenced the monitors readings are highlighted in Figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4 – Timetable of AQMesh highlighting location, calibration periods, battery life, change of battery and irregularities in voltage (indicating battery loss) from the period of October 2019 to January 2022. CY* Courtyard Paisley campus, University of the West of Scotland. Image created with BioRender.com.

Air pollutants were measured by both the air monitor and the air monitoring reference station during this time. Then values for a period of 1 week (23.12.2019 – 30.12.2019, Gordon St. Paisley and 13.11.2020 – 20.11.2020, High St. Irvine). Both calibration sites are depicted in Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5 – AQMesh co-located with reference monitoring stations. AQMesh shown stationed within sampling cages at stationary reference monitoring stations within A) Gordon Street, Paisley and B) High Street, Irvine.

Results with associated error messages (for instance when the monitor is newly relocated) were not used in monitor calibration. Raw values were correlated together (y axis = AQMesh (candidate); x axis = Reference). The resulting calculation was used to process the raw data from the AQMesh then the raw and processed data was plotted together and the resulting equation was taken as the correction factor. This process is illustrated in Figure 2.6. As shown in this figure the calculation values were obtained from the initial correlation (B) and the slope and offset correction factor were calculated from the final linear correlation (C).

Figure 2.6 – AQMesh calibration example. A) Example of Calibration of the AQMesh (candidate) air quality monitor for nitric oxide against an air pollution reference station (High St, Irvine) (left) and example of traces of the raw NO values from the AQMesh (red), Reference station (black) and corrected AQMesh values after application of the offset (orange) (right). Data obtained from period 12.11.2020 – 13.11.2020. Image obtained from www.airmonitors.net. B) First linear regression (raw values from AQMesh and Reference station) C) Second linear regression (processed AQMesh values against raw AQMesh values) final offset value calculation outlined in red.

The offset calculation was then used as a correction factor for the raw AQMesh values. Calibration periods were selected as a 1 week period in which data sets had no associated error warnings. Offset values from calibration sites were applied to data from calibration sites and subsequent focus regions, e.g. the offset from Paisley Gordon St was applied to Paisley and Stranraer data and the offset from Irvine was applied to Irvine and Stevenston data.

2.1.3 Calibration sites

2.1.3.1 *Gordon Street, Paisley, Renfrewshire*

For calibrating the AQMesh monitor two sites were chosen, the first of which was Gordon St., Paisley (55°50'30.3"N 4°25'25.1"W). The AQMesh monitor was placed within the sampling cage of the reference monitoring station from 07.10.2021 to 28.01.2021 with help from Renfrewshire Council. The AQMesh was within 1 metre from the reference monitor and both were approximately 2 metres from the nearest road. Image of AQMesh placement and outlines of the reference station are shown in Figure 2.7 and Table 2.5.

Figure 2.7 – Details of AQMesh and Gordon St., Paisley monitoring site. A) Location of monitoring site indicated by red pinpoint. Image obtained from Digimap Ordnance Survey Collection (Map scale: 1:1250) (Accessed 31st March 2022). B&C) reference station on Gordon St. and surrounding area, highlighted with red box (© 2023 Google. Image captured September 2022).

Table 2.5 Sampling specifications of Gordon St., Paisley reference monitoring site. TEOM – Tapered Element Oscillating Microbalance; FDMS – Filter Dynamics Measurement System. Including target sample and sampling method. ¹PM₁₀ was no longer sampled at this location by the end of the sampling data acquisition period in 2022.

Sample type	Sampling device
PM ₁₀ ¹	TEOM / FDMS
NOx	Chemiluminescence monitor

2.1.3.2 High Street, Irvine, North Ayrshire

The second air quality reference station that was used to calibrate the AQMesh for placement was at High St., Irvine (55°36'51.5"N 4°39'57.3"W). The AQMesh was placed within the sampling cage of the reference monitoring station from 11th November 2020 – 20th July 2021 with help from North Ayrshire Council. The AQMesh was within 1 metre of the reference monitor and both were approximately 1 metre from the nearest road. Image of AQMesh placement and outlines of reference station measurements are shown in Figure 2.8 and Table 2.6.

Figure 2.8 – Details of AQMesh and High St., Irvine. A) Location of monitoring site indicated by red pinpoint. Image obtained from Digimap Ordnance Survey Collection (Map scale: 1:1250) (Accessed March 31st 2022). B&C) AQMesh co-location with reference station on High St., station / monitor highlighted with red box (© 2023 Google. Image captured May 2021).

Table 2.6 - Sampling specifications of High St., Irvine monitoring site. Target sample and sampling method stated.

Sample type	Sampling device
PM ₁₀	FIDAS 200 [®] fine dust measurement device
PM _{2.5}	FIDAS 200
NO _x	Chemiluminescence monitor

2.1.4 Sampling locations – Locating placement site of AQMesh monitor

2.1.4.1 Sun St, Stranraer, Dumfries and Galloway

The Stranraer selected AQMesh placement site was selected as a lighting column at a road junction on Sun St (54°54'12.9"N 5°01'40.0"W). The monitor was placed less than 1 metre from the road and 2.5 m from the ground. This location fell outside the designated conservation area boundary; was far enough from the coastline to prevent coastal wind currents from excessively disrupting airborne particles allowing accurate readings and was in an area of high footfall and vehicle usage. Site was confirmed with the Dumfries and Galloway environmental health officer as busy location and a potential air pollution hotspot due to the close proximity to the nearby supermarket (Tesco Superstore, Primary School, shops and restaurants and direct access to Stranraer through the A75) and the location fell within an area with the lowest possible score on the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD) index (decile 1, quantile 1). The monitor was transferred to the designated Stranraer site on the 17th of February 2020. Characteristics of the site are highlighted in Figure 2.9.

Figure 2.9- Details of Stranraer AQMesh site placement. A) Location of AQMesh monitoring site indicated by red pinpoint. Image obtained from Digimap Ordnance Survey Collection (Map scale: 1:1250) (Accessed March 30th 2022). B) AQMesh affixed to lighting column, highlighted by red box. C) Surrounding location of AQMesh monitor placement site.

2.1.4.2 Glencairn Street, Stevenston, North Ayrshire

The Stevenston selected AQMesh placement site was selected as a lighting column on Glencairn St. (A738) (55°38'34.7"N 4°45'22.3"W). The monitor was placed within 1 metre of the road and 2.5 m from the ground. This area was close to many amenities such as a post office and retail areas and places of worship. This road also serves as one of the main routes through Stranraer and due to proximity to

residential areas is a likely area of high footfall. As with Stranraer, this was a deprived area according to the SIMD index (decile 2, quantile 1). The monitor was transferred to the designated Stranraer site on the 20th of July 2021. Characteristics of site highlighted in Figure 2.10.

Figure 2.10 – Details of Stevenston AQMesh site placement. A&B) Location of AQMesh monitoring site indicated by red pinpoint. Image obtained from Digimap Ordnance Survey Collection (Map scale: A, 1:2500; B, 1:1250)(Accessed March 30th 2022).. B) AQMesh affixed to lighting column.

The Stevenston site was the only site which required a permit to work application for the placement of the monitor.

2.1.5 Measurement of Gaseous Pollution within Internal Combustion Engine and Electric Vehicles

The AQMesh air monitor was loaded into the rear storage compartment of two separate vehicles, one with an internal combustion engine and an electric vehicle. Gaseous pollutant measurements (NO_x & O_3) were then obtained by the AQMesh (1 hr, every 15 min) while the vehicles was in operation. Data was then collated and compared. Vehicle information is illustrated in Table 2.7 below. Over duration of sampling period windows remained closed, air conditioning was switched off and air recirculation was in operation at the lowest speed with ventilation diverted through dashboard and footwell areas. PM concentrations were not compared as part of this analysis as this parameter was not recorded by the AQMesh in January 2022.

Table 2.7 – Internal cabin air pollution sampling details. Power source, vehicle type and sampling date and time specification for analysis of air pollution (NO_x & O_3) within internal cabin environment.

Power source	Vehicle Details	Date / Time
Internal combustion engine vehicle (Petrol)	Citroen C4, 1.8 L engine (2008)	7 th November 2020 10:00 – 11:00
Electric vehicle	Nissan Leaf, 30 kW battery (2017)	10 th January 2022 15:30 – 16:30

2.2 Biological Assays – Methods and Materials

2.2.1 Materials

Special thanks to Dr Nicholas Mullins at Dundalk Institute of Technology for providing 2-Furoyl-LIGRLO-NH₂ (FLIGRLO) compound and to Prof Robin Plevin and Dr Katie McIntosh at the University of Strathclyde for providing the AZ8838 PAR2 antagonist compound, previously described (Cheng *et al.*, 2017).

Before experimental use lyophilised FLIGRLO compound was reconstituted with deionised water (di.H₂O) to give a stock concentration of 10 mM, aliquots were stored at -20°C.

Before experimental use lyophilised AZ8838 compound was reconstituted with Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) to give a final concentration of 50 mM (for use in calcium mobilisation assay) or 100 mM (for use in all other experimentation). For experiments with particulate matter the standard reference

material 2975 (SRM 2975) from the National Institute of Standards and Technology were used. This material is diesel engine particulate (DEP) matter collected from an industrial level diesel-powered forklift truck. As reported from the Certificate of analysis from NIST, the mean diameter of these particulates is $1.6 \pm 0.01 \mu\text{m}$ (NIST, 2021). All other chemicals were acquired from Sigma or ThermoFisher (unless otherwise stated) and of the highest quality commercially available. Buffers utilised within this study were prepared as indicated in Table 2.8.

Buffer and Reagent component specifications

Table 2.8 – Buffer and reagent component summary.

Buffer	Reagent components
ELISA Wash Buffer	0.01 M Phosphate Buffered Saline, 0.05 % (v/v) Tween 20
Running Buffer	25 mM Tris, 192 mM Glycine, 0.1% SDS (pH 8.3) in di.H ₂ O
Transfer Buffer	25 mM Tris, 192 mM Glycine, 0.1% SDS (pH 8.3) in di.H ₂ O
Lysis Buffer	10 % (v/v) Radioimmunoprecipitation buffer, 1 % (v/v) protease inhibitor cocktail and 1 % phosphatase inhibitor cocktail in molecular biology grade water.
Calcium Assay Buffer	1 x Hanks' Balanced Salt Solution, 20 mM HEPES
Immunofluorescence Permeabilisation Solution	0.01 M PBS, 0.1% (v/v) Triton X-100

2.2.2 Diesel engine particulate preparation

DEPs (NIST2975, Sigma) were suspended in Dulbecco's phosphate-buffered saline (DPBS) (Lonza, 17-512F) in a quartz glass cuvette. This solution was then sonicated for 10 min at 37 Hz (FB11201 ultrasonic bath, Fisherbrand), UV irradiated 254 nm for 3 hr and sonicated again for a further 10 min. Following this procedure, it was confirmed that no colony forming microbes were present in the solution

when applied to solid nutrient agar and incubated at 30 °C in constant humidity for a period of 3 days. Results from a previous study have confirmed that this sample contains negligible levels of endotoxin and therefore these components should not contribute to cell reactions upon exposure (Levesque *et al.*, 2013). Concentrations of DEP utilised within this study are 6.25 and 12.5 µg/ml in 200 µl as applied per well to a 96-well plate, where plate formats differ within assays the concentrations refer to a standard of 3.9 µg/cm² and 7.8 µg/cm² for each concentration, respectively.

2.2.2.1 Diesel engine particulate concentrations

DEP concentrations used within this research are lower than many of those utilised within a myriad of DEP exposure studies (Smyth *et al.*, 2020; Wu *et al.*, 2022; Fiorito *et al.*, 2011; Tal *et al.*, 2010). If calculations used within previous studies to convert PM concentration values into airborne concentrations were applied here, the final airborne PM concentrations for 6.25 & 12.5 µg/ml would be equivalent to 38.75 and 77.5 µg/m³ respectively for PM_{Total}. This is assuming a daily inhaled volume of 20 m³, 10 % lung deposition rate and 12.4 ml lung epithelial lining fluid volume. Assuming a PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ ratio of 0.5⁸ this may equate to PM_{2.5}: 12.9 µg/m³ & PM₁₀: 25.8 µg/m³ for 6.25 µg/ml and PM_{2.5}: 25.8 µg/m³ & PM₁₀: 51.7 µg/m³ for 12.5 µg/ml. These concentrations are slightly higher than the 2005 WHO guidelines values and given that studies on PM deposition within the lung have identified non-uniform particulate distribution with definite hotspot areas (Li *et al.*, 2019) these concentrations were deemed reasonable for use within this study.

2.2.2.2 Aqueous extract of diesel engine particulates

Particulates (2 mg) were washed with Hanks' Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS) (Thermo Fisher, 14025-092) 3 times (0.5 ml each wash) in a sterile Eppendorf. Following the addition of each wash, particulates were sonicated at 37 Hz, 100 % power (FB11201 ultrasonic bath, Fisher Scientific) for a period of 5 min then centrifuged (822 series, serial no. 98032099, Centurion Scientific Ltd) for 30 min at 17000 x g. After each wash, HBSS was removed and collated in a single sterile Eppendorf then the collated aqueous solvent extracts were repeatedly centrifuged and transferred to a fresh Eppendorf until

⁸ Annual mean PM₁₀ concentration (roadside), 2021: 15.9 µg/m³; Annual mean PM_{2.5} concentration (roadside), 2021: 8.3 µg/m³ (DEFRA, 2022 – National statistics PM10 & PM2.5).

no solid pellet remained. Resulting aqueous extract was filtered using a sterile syringe and 0.2 μ M sterile syringe filters (ThermoFisher, 15392388) prior to use.

2.2.2.3 *Organic extract of diesel engine particulates*

10mg of SRM 2975 was washed with High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) grade hexane (H/0406/17, Fisher Scientific) 3 times (2 ml each wash) in a glass test tube. Following the addition of each wash particulates were sonicated at 37Hz 100% power (FB11201 ultrasonic bath) for a period of 5 min then centrifuged (822 series, serial no. 98032099, Centurion Scientific Ltd) for 30 min at 3000 x g. After each wash extracts were removed and collated in a single glass test tube then the hexane solvent was evaporated to precipitate under nitrogen flow. Following this 0.5 ml DMSO (D2438, Sigma) was added to dissolve the organic precipitate giving a final concentration of 20 mg/ml DEP equivalent stock organic extract. Hexane control consisted of 6 ml hexane evaporated under nitrogen flow followed by addition of 0.5 ml DMSO.

2.2.3 Cell culture

2.2.3.1 *Ethical Statement*

The work conducted within this study did not involve any human or animal subjects or non-anonymised samples, and therefore did not require ethical approval from an institutional review board or animal ethics committee.

2.2.3.2 *Source of human immortalised cell line and primary bronchial epithelial cells*

BEAS-2B cell line was obtained from American Type Culture Collection (ATCC) (CRL-9609™). BEAS-2B are an immortalised human bronchial epithelial adherent adenovirus 12-SV40 virus hybrid (Ad12SV40) transformed cell line. Cells were cultured in complete medium consisting of RPMI 1640 with Gluta MAX (61870036) supplemented with 10 % (v/v) Foetal Bovine Serum (FBS) (16000044, ThermoFisher) and 100 U/ml (w/v) penicillin with 100 μ g/ml (w/v) streptomycin (15140122, ThermoFisher).

Commercial primary bronchial / tracheal epithelial cells obtained from healthy and COPD donors (HBEC and COPD-HBEC respectively) were obtained from ATCC (HBEC, ATCC® PCS-300-010™, COPD-HBEC, ATCC® PCS-300-013) and Promocell (HBEPc-c, C-12640). These cells were cultured in complete medium corresponding to cell growth requirements, either complete PneumaCultEx

medium (Stemcell Technologies) comprised of PneumaCult Ex basal medium (05009), PneumaCultEx supplement (05019) and (v/v) 0.1 % hydrocortisone (07925) or airway epithelial cell growth medium (Promocell, C-21060B) with supplement mix (C-39165).

2.2.3.3 Freezing and thawing cells

When storage of cells was required, the spent medium was removed from cells and cells were detached, suspended and pelleted as described in the preparation for experimentation method. The resulting pellet was re-suspended in a cell suitable cryopreservation medium (70 % (v/v) medium, 20 % FBS (v/v), 10 % DMSO (v/v)) to prevent cell stress during freeze. This cell solution was transferred to a cryovial, placed into a Corning® CoolCell™ LX Cell Freezing Container (Corning) and transferred to a -80 °C freezer for overnight storage. Following this, the vials were transferred to liquid nitrogen for long-term storage. To thaw cells from long-term storage vials were warmed to room temperature and suspended into complete medium and transferred to a flask for overnight incubation. The following day cell growth medium was changed and cells were cultured and prepared as previously described.

2.2.3.4 Passaging and preparation for experimentation

All cell culture including maintenance and passaging was performed under sterile conditions in a class II biosafety cabinet.

All cells were incubated at 37 °C with 5 % CO₂ in a humidified incubator and growth medium was replaced once every 48 hr period. Once cell line cells reached approximately 80 % confluence, the spent medium was removed and cells were washed twice with 5 ml of warmed DPBS (17-512F, Lonza) then incubated with 2 ml (T75 cm² flask) 0.5% Trypsin-EDTA (25300062, ThermoFisher) to detach cells from flask surface. Cells were regularly checked for detachment (1-7 minutes) under microscope and once all cells were visibly detached 3 x trypsin volume of complete medium was added to inactivate trypsin. Suspended cells were transferred to a sterile Falcon tube and centrifuged for 5 minutes at 350 x g. Supernatant was discarded and the cell pellet was re-suspended in complete RPMI medium and counted with Trypan Blue solution (0.4 % (w/v), Thermo Fisher, 15250061) using counting slides (Biorad, 1450011) and an automated cell counter (TC20, Biorad). Appropriate cell concentration was

then seeded into the required plate format for experimentation. Exposures were performed following a 24 hr growth period.

A similar procedure was followed to passage primary epithelial cells although cells were dissociated from the surface of a flask by incubating with 1 ml (T25 cm² flask) of Animal Component Free (ACF) Enzymatic Dissociation Solution (Stem Cell Technologies, 05427) which was inactivated following addition of ACF Inhibition Solution (Stem Cell Technologies, 05428). Following centrifugation (350 x g) the cell pellet was re-suspended in complete Pneumacult Ex Plus Medium. Once passaged cells were reseeded into a flask or harvested for experimentation and following 24 hr attachment phase medium was replaced and cells exposed.

2.2.3.5 *Air-liquid interface culture*

3-D monoculture of differentiated HBEC at the air-liquid interface was established as follows. HBEC (80 % confluent) were incubated with trypsin-EDTA (Merck, T3924) until detachment from the surface of the flask and passaged as previously described. Cells were then counted with Trypan Blue (Merck, T8154) and resuspended in PneumaCult-Ex Plus medium (Stemcell Technologies, 05009). Cells were then seeded at a density of 3.3×10^4 (24-well, for immunofluorescence) or 0.83×10^4 (96-well, for ELISA) cells / well onto the apical surface of a transwell insert (Stemcell Technologies 24-well, 38024; 96-well, 100-0419), pore size 0.4 μm . Pneumacult Ex-medium was added to apical (96-well: 80 μl , 24-well: 200 μl) and basal chambers (96-well: 200 μl , 24-well: 500 μl) and full medium changes were performed every 48 hr until cells reached confluence (approx. 2 – 4 days). Throughout all stages of growth cells were incubated at 37 °C with 5 % CO₂ in a humidified incubator.

Following confluence the process of differentiation was initiated. In a process known as airlifting medium from apical and basal chambers was gently aspirated and replaced with PneumaCult-ALI Maintenance Medium in the basal chamber only. Medium changes of basal PneumaCult-ALI were performed every 48 hr. Beginning in week 2 post-airlift, mucus was removed from the apical cell surface by washing once with warmed DPBS, this was repeated weekly to prevent accumulation. The processes of expansion, maintenance and differentiation are illustrated in Figure 2.11.

Figure 2.11 – ALI culture timeline and process of expansion, differentiation and maintenance. During Phase 1 and 2, cells remain submerged then beginning Phase 3 (upon reaching confluence), medium used is ALI maintenance medium and medium is henceforth removed from and not replaced to the apical surface of the transwell insert (airlift). Pseudostratified epithelium mucociliary differentiation is obtained following 21-28 days and can be maintained for up to 1 year (Stemcell Technologies, 2021b; Stemcell Technologies, 2021a). Image created with Biorender.com

2.2.4 Cell-Based Assays

2.2.4.1 MTT assay

MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl-2H-tetrazolium bromide) (M5655, Sigma) cell metabolism assay was used as a representative assessment of cell viability. After a period of exposure, spent medium was removed from the wells of a 96 well plate and serum-free fresh growth medium was added with the addition of 10% (v/v) MTT solution (stock 5 mg/ml). After a period of 4 hr this was removed, DMSO was added and the plate incubated for 10 min at 37 °C to dissolve the formed formazan crystals. The plate was subsequently analysed using a Biotech Elx800 plate reader (ThermoFisher) measuring absorbance at 570 nm. Decreased absorbance was indicative of decreased cell metabolism and therefore cell viability. MTT process was followed under low light conditions until absorbance reading was obtained due to the light sensitivity of the reagent. Cell viability was calculated as a percentage of the experimental control.

When performing MTT of diesel engine particulate treated samples wells were washed once with PBS prior to addition of MTT reagent. Following the 4 hr incubation period, 160 μ l of DMSO was added to each well to dissolve the formazan crystals and incubated for a period of 10 min at 37 °C. After the incubation period 60 μ l of solvent/solute mix was transferred to a new microplate before analysis using a Biotech Elx800 plate reader (ThermoFisher) measuring absorbance at 570 nm. Again, this process was followed under low-light conditions and cell viability was calculated as a percentage of the experimental control.

2.2.4.2 Enzyme-linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA)

Concentration levels of IL-6 and IL-8 from conditioned medium were determined as per manufacturer's instructions from commercially available kits (Invitrogen, UK; IL-6: 88-7066-88, IL-8: 88-8086-88) in 96 well plates (Greiner Bio-One, 655061). Plate wells were briefly coated with 100 μ l / well of capture antibody in coating buffer then sealed and incubated overnight at 4 °C. Following incubation, wells were aspirated and washed 3 x with >250 μ l/well of wash buffer (0.01 M PBS; sc-362299, Santa Cruz Biotechnology) with 0.05 % (v/v) Tween 20 (P1379, Sigma Aldrich); 1 min soaking step / wash) before the plate was blotted on to absorbent paper to remove residual buffer. Wells were then blocked using 1 x ELISA/ELISPOT diluent (5x stock diluted with di.H₂O) and incubated for 1 hr at room temperature. Lyophilised recombinant protein standards (supplied) were reconstituted with di.H₂O and from the stock two-fold dilutions were prepared forming an 8-point standard curve. Standards and samples were then added to wells (100 μ l) and plates were incubated at RT for 2 hr followed by another 3x wash step before 100 μ l / well of secondary biotinylated detection antibody was added to each well and incubated for 1 hr at RT. A final wash step (5 x) was performed followed by the addition of 100 μ l / well of 1x 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) chromagen substrate until blue product was formed. The reaction was stopped by the addition of 50 μ l / well of 'stop solution' (0.5 M sulphuric acid). Absorbance was read at 420 nm with a BioTek Elx800 plate reader and cytokine release assessed. Unknown concentration of samples was determined using the 8-point standard curve, an example four parameter logistic (4-PL) curve is demonstrated in Figure 2.12.

Figure 2.12 – ELISA IL-6 4-PL standard curve fit of concentration curve. Example curve, created with IL-6 concentrations ranging 2– 200 pg/ml.

2.2.4.3 Calcium assay

2.2.4.3.1 Calcium stimulation by Trypsin, FLIGRLO, DEP and AZ8838

The Fluo-4 NW calcium assay kit (F36206, Thermo Fisher) fluorescent assay was used to evaluate intracellular calcium mobilisation. BEAS-2B, COPD-HBEC and HBEC cells were seeded into 96 well black/clear bottom plates (165305, ThermoFisher) at a seeding density of 2×10^4 cells / well and incubated for 24 hr. The Fluo-4 dye was prepared by combining kit components, 10 ml of assay buffer and 100 μ l of probenecid stock solution (final concentration 2.5 mM) was added to one vial of the desiccated dye and vortexed until dissolved. Cell medium was aspirated from the cells and 90 μ l of the dye added to each well. The plate was then incubated under low light conditions (due to the light sensitive nature of the dye) at 37°C for 30 min. Stimulations of porcine pancreas trypsin (1 U/ml^{-1}), FLIGRLO (1, 10 100 μ M), DEP aqueous and organic soluble extracts (12.5 μ g/ml equivalent final concentration) or AZ8838 (0.003 – 30 μ M) were applied to cells and fluorescence readings were obtained using a Varioskan LUX Multimode Microplate Reader (VLB000GD1, ThermoFisher) SkanIT 6.0 Software (ThermoFisher). Reading time was set to 2 min, the first 9 seconds were used to establish

baseline fluorescence and stimulations were added at 10 s. Readings (bottom read optics) were obtained every second and excitation and emission wavelengths were obtained at 490 and 520 nm respectively. Relative fluorescence increase was determined by subtracting the average baseline fluorescence from the maximal fluorescence values obtained following addition of the agonist. The Varioskan settings utilised for this assay are illustrated in Table 2.9 below.

Varioskan Plate Reader Settings – Calcium Assay

Table 2.9 – Varioskan Fluorescent Microplate Reader Calcium Assay Settings. Applied with SkanIT 6.0 Software (ThermoFisher).

Parameter	Value
Temperature	37 °C
Well loop > Well count	1
Total time [hh:mm:ss]	00:02:00
Kinetic Interval [hh:mm:ss]	00:00:01
Executed no. of readings	121
Dispenser	1
Volume	10 µl
Dispense at reading	10
Excitation / Emission (nm)	490 / 520
Optics	Top
Excitation bandwidth	12 nm

2.2.4.3.2 Calcium inhibition with AZ8838

BEAS-2B, COPD-HBEC and HBEC cells were seeded into 96 well black/clear bottom plates (165305, ThermoFisher) at a seeding density of 2×10^4 cells / well and incubated for 24 hr. Cell medium was then aspirated and cells were incubated with assay buffer (component of Ca^{2+} mobilisation assay kit), loaded with a double concentration of prepared Fluo-4 dye and incubated at 37 °C for 15 min. Following this, assay buffer with DMSO (D2438, Sigma Aldrich) or concentrations of AZ8838 antagonist (3 – 300 nM, 3 – 30 µM final concentration) were added each well without removing the dye at a 1:2 dilution

and incubated for a further 30 minutes. Stimulations e.g porcine pancreas trypsin (1 U/ml^{-1}), FLIGRLO (1, 10 100 μM), DEP aqueous and organic soluble extracts ($12.5 \mu\text{g/ml}$ equivalent final concentration) were applied to cells and fluorescence readings were obtained using a Varioskan LUX Multimode Microplate Reader (VLB000GD1, ThermoFisher) and SkanIT 6.0 Software (ThermoFisher). Reading time was set to 2 min, the first 9 seconds were used to establish baseline fluorescence and stimulations were added at 10 s. Readings (bottom read optics) were obtained every second and excitation and emission wavelengths were obtained at 490 and 520 nm respectively. Relative fluorescence increase was determined by subtracting the average baseline fluorescence from the maximal fluorescence values obtained following addition of the agonist.

2.2.4.4 Reactive Oxygen Species Assay

CM- H_2DCFDA is a dye commonly used for the determination of reactive oxygen species within cells. This dye passively diffuses into cells and its acetate groups are cleaved by intracellular esterases before the chloromethyl group reacts with intracellular thiols, subsequent oxidation then produces a fluorescent adduct which remains inside the cell.

CM- H_2DCFDA lyophilised powder was reconstituted with anhydrous DMSO (Thermo Fisher, D12345) at a concentration of 10 mM and diluted to a final concentration of 10 μM with HBSS (Thermo Fisher, 14025-092). BEAS-2B cells were seeded into 96 well black/clear bottom plates (165305, ThermoFisher) at a seeding density of 2×10^4 cells / well and incubated for 24 hr.

Cells were exposed and following exposure, medium was aspirated, cells were washed once with HBSS then incubated with 100 μl of dye (in a 96-well plate) for 30 min at 37 °C under low-light conditions. Following incubation dye was removed and replaced with HBSS before fluorescence was determined using a Varioskan LUX Multimode Microplate Reader (VLB000GD1, ThermoFisher) and SkanIT 6.0 Software (ThermoFisher).

2.2.4.5 Lipid Peroxidation Assay

BODIPY 581/591 C11 is a sensor which, when oxidised, shifts the fluorescence emission peak of the dye from $\sim 610 \text{ nm}$ to $\sim 510 \text{ nm}$. The dye localises to the lipid membrane making it a suitable probe for lipid peroxidation.

BODIPY 581/591 lyophilised powder was reconstituted with anhydrous DMSO (Thermo Fisher, D12345) at a concentration of 10 mM and diluted to a final concentration of 1 μ M with growth medium (Thermo Fisher, 14025-092).

BEAS-2B cells were seeded into 96-well black/clear bottom plates (165305, ThermoFisher) at a seeding density of 2×10^4 cells / well and incubated for 24 hr. Cells were exposed and following exposure, medium was aspirated, cells were washed once with PBS then incubated with 100 μ l of dye (in a 96-well plate) for 30 min at 37 °C under low-light conditions. Following incubation dye was removed, cells were washed 3 x with PBS then incubated with HBSS before fluorescence was determined using a Varioskan LUX Multimode Microplate Reader (VLB000GD1, ThermoFisher) and SkanIT 6.0 Software (ThermoFisher). Fluorescence of C-11 BODIPY was measured by simultaneous acquisition of green (484/510) and red (581/610) signals. The green/red ratio was then calculated as a measure of lipid peroxidation levels.

2.2.4.6 Western blot

2.2.4.6.1 Cell Lysis

Cells of interest were seeded in a 6-well (BEAS-2B) or 12-well (HBEC) format. Following a period of stimulation cells were washed with ice cold DPBS (17-512F, Lonza) before the addition of 200 μ l / well of cold complete lysis buffer consisting of 1 x Radioimmunoprecipitation (RIPA) buffer (9806S, Cell Signalling Technology), 1 x protease inhibitor cocktail (5871S, Cell Signalling Technology) and 1 x phosphatase inhibitor cocktail (5870S, Cell Signalling Technology) in molecular biology grade nuclease-free water (AM9932, ThermoFisher). Cell lysates were then harvested through cell scraping and transferred into Eppendorf tubes then frozen on dry ice. Lysates then underwent a cycle of 3 x freeze / thaw stages and were centrifuged at 17000 x g before supernatant was obtained and pellet discarded.

2.2.4.6.2 Protein Quantification

To standardise loading of each sample protein concentration was determined by Bradford Assay. In a non-treated 96-well non-treated cell culture plate an 8 point standard curve was prepared (each point in triplicate, 5 μ l per well) using the Quick Start Bovine Serum Albumin Set (0.125 – 2.0 mg/ml; 5000207, Bio-Rad) and a blank sample. Samples were added to the plate in triplicate (5 μ l each) before 250 μ l of

Quick Start™ 1 x Bradford Dye Reagent (5000205, Bio-Rad) was added to all BSA standard and sample extracts. The plate was incubated for 5 min at RT under low-light conditions (due to light sensitivity of reagent) before absorbance was measured using a Biotech Elx800 plate reader at 595 nm. Sample protein concentrations were calculated from the standard curve using GEN5 1.08 Software.

2.2.4.6.3 Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate-Polyacrylamide Gel Electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE)

Protein samples were prepared for running on Mini-PROTEAN® TGX™ Precast PAGE commercial gradient gels (4 – 20 % w/v) by diluting samples to load 20 µg of protein per sample. Each protein sample was then combined with blue loading buffer pack components containing 3 x Laemmli loading buffer and 30 x DTT (dithiothreitol) (7722, Cell Signalling). Samples were then loaded into the gel alongside 7 µl of protein ladder and electrophoresed with Tris-glycine SDS running buffer at 125 v for 1 hr.

2.2.4.6.4 Protein Transfer

Following electrophoresis of samples, gels were removed from cassettes and transferred on to PVDF membrane using membrane, running buffer and transfer stacks from a Trans-Blot nitrocellulose transfer kit (1704270, Bio-Rad) and Trans-Blot Turbo System (Bio-Rad. TGX mini gel programme: 25 V, 7 min).

2.2.4.6.5 Immunoblotting & Analysis

For immunoblotting procedure, membranes were blocked with 5% (w/v) BSA-TBST (5 % BSA (5217, Biotechne), (v/v) and 0.05 % (v/v) Tween 20 (P1379, Sigma) in 1 x TBS (28358, ThermoFisher) for 1 hr at RT. Membranes were then incubated with primary antibody overnight at 4 °C. Following this, membranes were washed 3 x in TBST at RT and probed with an HRP-conjugated secondary antibody for 1 hr. Following a final 3 x wash step in TBST, membranes were incubated with an enhanced chemiluminescence substrate (ECL) for 1 min then visualised using the G:BOX Chemi XX6 gel documentation system (Syngene) and GeneSys automatic control software. Membranes were then stripped for 10 min at RT with stripping buffer (21059, ThermoFisher), washed 3 x in TBST, blocked for 1 hr in BSA-TBST and re-probed with an appropriate loading control antibody. Relative quantification of gel band intensities from images were performed with ImageJ software. This was performed by quantifying the intensity of the phosphorylated protein bands and the intensity of the total

protein loading control, the former was then normalised against the latter producing an intensity ratio. All primary and secondary antibodies used within immunoblotting procedures are illustrated in Table 2.10.

2.2.4.7 Immunofluorescence (IF)

2.2.4.7.1 Monolayer IF

Immunofluorescence of monolayer primary and immortalised cell lines was performed as follows: Epithelial cells were seeded on to sterile borosilicate glass coverslips (L46R10-15, Agar Scientific) in a 12 well plate then cells were allowed to adhere overnight. Cells were then either stimulated (specific to experiment) or directly washed 3 x with PBS before fixation by incubation with 4 % (w/v) formaldehyde in PBS solution (FB002, ThermoFisher) at RT for 30 min. Cells were then permeabilised through incubation with 0.1% (v/v) Triton X-100 (T9284, Sigma) in 0.01 M PBS for 10 min at RT before being blocked with 3 % (w/v) BSA in PBS (A14289SA, ThermoFisher) for 45 min. Primary antibody in 3 % (w/v) BSA was added to each well incubated overnight at 4 °C. Following this the primary antibody was aspirated and coverslips were washed 3 x in PBS (10 min per wash) before incubation with the appropriate secondary antibody conjugated with Alexa Fluor dye (prepared in 3 % BSA) for 1 hr at RT. Coverslips were then washed as before with the final wash containing 2 µg/ml Hoechst (H3570, ThermoFisher). Coverslips were mounted on to microscope slides (631-0108, Avantor) with Dibutylphthalate Polystyrene Xylene (DPX) resin mounting medium (SEA-1304-00A, CellPath) and allowed to set, at least overnight, at 4 °C. Slides were visualised and images obtained using the Olympus IX71 fluorescent microscope and Cellsense Dimensions software. Images were converted to TIFF as RGB files. Appropriate isotype controls were included for all experiments.

2.2.4.7.2 Air-liquid interface IF

Immunofluorescence of 3-D air-liquid interface (ALI) culture 24-well inserts was performed as follows. Apical and basal sides of ALI inserts were washed 3 x with DPBS (17-512F, Lonza) then both compartments were fixated with 4 % (w/v) formaldehyde in PBS (FB002, ThermoFisher)(500 µl apical & 1.5 ml basal) followed by another 3 x wash with DPBS. Cells were then permeabilised with 0.25 % (v/v) Triton X-100 (T9284, Sigma) in 0.01 M DPBS for 1 hr at RT and blocked with blocking solution (2.5 % (w/v) BSA (5217, Biotechne), 5 % (v/v) goat serum (Vector laboratories, S-1000) & 0.05 %

(v/v) Tween 20 (P1379, Sigma) in 0.01 M DPBS) for 30 min. Cells were then incubated with primary antibodies overnight at 4 °C. Following overnight incubation inserts were washed 3 x for 15 min at RT. To each well, 200 µl of fluorescently labelled secondary antibody in DPBS was added and the plate was incubated at 37 °C for 1 hr. DPBS was aspirated and inserts were washed 3 x with 500 µl / wash for 15 min each with the last wash containing Hoechst (2 µg/ml). The membrane was removed from the inserts and mounted on to Starfrost microscopy slides (CellPath, MBB-0302-55A) using DPX mounting media (SEA-1304-00A) and sealed with a coverglass (Cellpath, SAJ-2250-03A). The samples were stored at -20 °C and imaged using a confocal microscope.

Antibodies used in Western blot and immunofluorescence Experiments**Table 2.10– Antibodies used in western blot and immunofluorescence experiments.** Including dilutions for each experimental type and information on secondary antibodies.

Target	Primary antibody	Secondary antibody	Isotype	Source	WB dilution	IF dilution
PAR2 (F2RL1)	Rabbit polyclonal IgG	Donkey anti-Rabbit (Alexa Fluor 488, A-21206), Invitrogen 1:400	Rabbit polyclonal IgG (ab37415, Abcam)	Alomone (APR-032) (Israel)	n/a	1:500
Total MAPK (p38)	Rabbit monoclonal IgG	Anti-Rabbit HRP-linked antibody (7074S) Cell Signalling 1:3000	n/a	Cell signalling (8690)	1:1000	n/a
Phospho-MAPK (P-p38) (Thr180/Tyr182)	Rabbit Monoclonal IgG	Anti-Rabbit HRP-linked antibody (7074S) Cell Signalling 1:4000	n/a	Cell Signalling (4511S)	1:1000	n/a
Total 1 / 2 ERK (p44/42)	Mouse monoclonal IgG	Anti-mouse HRP-linked antibody (7076S) Cell Signalling 1:3000	n/a	Cell Signalling (9107S)	1:1000	n/a
Phospho-1 / 2 ERK (P-p44) (Thr202/Tyr204)	Mouse monoclonal IgG	Anti-mouse HRP-linked antibody (7076S) Cell Signalling 1:3000	n/a	Cell Signalling (9106S)	1:2000	n/a
GAPDH	Rabbit Polyclonal IgG	Anti-Rabbit HRP-linked antibody (7074S) Cell Signalling 1:4000	n/a	ProSci Inc (3783)	1:1000	n/a
ZO-1 (ZO-1-1A12) (Tight junctions)	Mouse monoclonal IgG	Goat Anti-mouse (Alexa Fluor 647, A32728) Invitrogen 1:400	Mouse monoclonal IgG (ab170190, Abcam)	ThermoFisher Scientific (UK) (33-9100)	n/a	1:200
β -Tubulin (Cilia)	Mouse monoclonal IgG	Goat anti-Mouse (Alexa Fluor 647, A32728), Invitrogen 1:400	Mouse monoclonal IgG (ab170190, Abcam)	Sigma-Aldrich (UK) (T4026)	n/a	1:200
MUC5AC (Glycoprotein, Goblet cells)	Mouse monoclonal IgG	Goat anti-mouse (Alexa Fluor 647, A32728), Invitrogen 1:400	Mouse monoclonal IgG (ab170190, Abcam)	ThermoFisher Scientific (UK) (MS-145-PI)	n/a	1:200
FOXJ1 (Cilia)	Mouse monoclonal IgG	Goat anti-mouse (Alexa Fluor 647, A32728) Invitrogen 1:400	Mouse monoclonal IgG (ab170190, Abcam)	Thermofisher Scientific (UK) (14-9965-82)	n/a	1:200

All western blot antibodies were diluted in 5% (w/v) BSA (5217, Bio-Techne) in TBST (1 x TBS (28358, ThermoFisher) in di.H₂O and 0.05 % (v/v) Tween 20 (P1379, Sigma Aldrich)) while immunofluorescence antibodies were diluted in 3% (w/v) BSA (A14289SA, ThermoFisher).

2.2.5 Confocal microscopy

Confocal microscopy of fixed air liquid interface culture samples was performed using a Zeiss LSM 880 upright microscope. Slides were imaged with immersion oil and all images were obtained at 63 x objective (plan apochromat). Laser specifications of microscope are listed in Table 2.11.

Confocal Microscopy Laser Specifications and IF Study Application

Table 2.11– Confocal microscope laser specifications. Used for the excitation of fluorescent dye conjugated secondary antibodies in air-liquid interface immunofluorescence samples.

Excitation source	Excitation lines (nm)	Fluorophore colour	Study application
Diode laser	405	Blue	Hoechst
Multiline Argon laser	458, 488 & 514	Green, cyan & yellow	PAR2, α ENaC, FOXJ bound secondary antibody (488 nm)
HeNe laser	633	Far red	ZO-1, β -tubulin, MUC5A, FOXJ bound secondary antibody (647 nm).

Images were obtained using laser excitation and a motorised stage for z-stack acquisition and tile scanning then exported as CZI files before processing using Zeiss Zen blue analysis software.

2.2.6 Statistical analysis

All statistical significance calculations were performed using Graphpad Prism 6 Software. Statistical tests were determined based independently upon data analysed. See figure legends for statistical information, t-test was used for comparison of 2 sets of data and ANOVA for comparison of 3 or more datasets. All results are displayed as mean \pm standard error of mean and statistics were considered significant where $p < 0.05$ (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$).

3 Chapter 3 – Low-cost air pollution monitoring in COPD hotspots

3.1 Introduction

3.1.1 Use of low-cost monitors for air pollution reporting

In the UK, current government air monitoring networks report on air quality values as required by European and National Air Quality air pollution control strategies. As previously discussed these monitors are expensive and immovable and are therefore unable to provide detailed spatiotemporal variability trends on air pollution within large areas (Munir *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, these monitors are often placed in areas of high population and stations within remote regions are less frequent, often used to establish background air pollution levels as a comparator for the rest of the UK. However, air pollution can vary vastly with different spatial and temporal variations and a high resolution approach to monitoring within both remote and urban areas would allow for the identification of elevated pollution source and apportionment left otherwise undetected. Low-cost portable air monitoring platforms could provide a novel solution to this issue although questions have been raised regarding the reliability of such equipment. Low accuracy of measurements can originate from alteration in ambient conditions, limited life-span, variation in measurement and variability and frequency of calibration requirement (Chojer *et al.*, 2022). Further research is required to identify the drawbacks, reliability and accuracy of these monitors to identify and develop high resolution air pollution level reporting systems.

3.2 Air monitoring in COPD hotspot regions

Air pollution is estimated by WHO to be the single greatest environmental threat currently facing the global population, therefore, it is important to identify pollution levels (WHO, 2021). This is particularly applicable when considering cohorts vulnerable to the adverse effects induced by airborne xenobiotics, such as those with respiratory conditions e.g. COPD (Chen *et al.*, 2022). As air pollution monitoring is sparser in remote locations within the UK these areas are an important focal point for air monitoring strategies as there is less data available regarding the local air pollution profile. Furthermore, the underpinning dynamics and potential source apportionment may be influenced by region specific characteristics including the presence of biogenic pollution precursors, agricultural emissions and varied topography. Remote investigation becomes even more pertinent in the case where local populations have elevated levels of respiratory conditions such as COPD when compared with national average rates, as is the case in areas considered by this study. Localities of Dumfries and Galloway & Ayrshire and Arran were reported to have COPD diagnosis rates higher than the national average (Figure 3.1 & Figure 3.2). However, this data can be influenced by complicating factors such as regional under-, over- or misdiagnosis influenced by factors such as asymptomatic patients, insufficient spirometry testing or not strictly adhering to guidelines during performance of spirometry testing procedures (Ho *et al.*, 2019). More recently figures also demonstrate that Ayrshire and Arran & Dumfries and Galloway NHS boards reported higher crude rates of hospitalisation discharges with COPD as the main diagnosis (Figure 3.3). These higher rates may not be due to air pollution but may instead be attributed to historical exposure sources e.g. through area-linked workplace characteristics (coal mining) (Coggon and Taylor, 1998; EAC, 2019) or ageing population levels (MacNee, 2016). In

the case that air pollution is not a contributory factor to initial COPD development it could still be a major contributory factor to continued pathogenesis, morbidity and mortality *via* induction of exacerbations in these vulnerable groups (Jiang, Mei and Feng, 2016). Ayrshire and Arran & Dumfries and Galloway represent COPD hotspot regions and contain a number of remote communities. Underpinning the air pollution dynamics within these areas would allow for the identification of elevated levels of pollution within these lesser-studied areas and identify source apportionment of identified pollutants and therefore inform remediation strategies.

Figure 3.1 – NHS board separated crude rates of disease prevalence (2018/19) of COPD in Scotland. Red line indicates average crude rate across Scottish resident population. Focus areas Ayrshire and Arran & Dumfries and Galloway indicated by black bars. COPD diagnosis codes J40-J44. Created from data obtained from: (PHS, 2020).

Figure 3.2 – Visual representation of COPD disease prevalence across Scotland (2018/2019). Area separated by local authority and based upon data derived from locality GP practices. Image obtained from: (PHS, 2020).

Figure 3.3 – NHS board separated crude rates of hospital discharge / 100,000 population (2020/2021) with COPD listed as main diagnosis in Scotland. Red line indicates average crude rate across Scottish resident population. Focus areas Ayrshire and Arran & Dumfries and Galloway indicated by black bars. Created from data obtained from: (PHS, 2021).

3.3 Hypothesis and Aims

The central **hypothesis** investigated within this chapter is that air pollution within COPD population hotspot focus regions represent an unidentified factor that may potentially lead to disease exacerbation and / or pathogenesis.

The **aim** of this study was to calibrate and site a low-cost monitor within four regions, Paisley (urban), Stranraer (remote), Irvine (urban) and Stevenston (remote) to measure pollutants Nox, O₃, and PM. Then to use the measurements from calibration and continuous sampling to determine the reliability of said measurements and compare air pollution values with regulatory limits set by the EU, UK and guidelines recommended by the WHO.

The main research areas addressed within this chapter are as follows:

- Does the AQMesh low-cost monitor provide a viable and reliable method of air pollution monitoring?
- How do air pollution measurements obtained from remote areas compare with that of urban areas?
- Does air pollution observed within urban and remote (COPD hotspot) regions present a viable threat to COPD pathogenesis and / or exacerbation when compared with regulatory limits?

An outline of the AQMesh location timeline alongside a timeline of major COVID-19 key milestones in Scotland are outlined in Figure 3.4 and Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.4 – AQMesh location and Scottish COVID-19 timeline (19-20). Period spanning 7th October 2019 to 25th September 2020. Red pin – AQMesh relocation; Black pin – COVID-19 key milestone. Image created with Biorender.com with information from (SPICE, 2022). See route map out of lockdown (Table 0.1).

Figure 3.5 – AQMesh location and Scottish COVID-19 timeline (20-22). Period spanning 2nd November 2020 to 10th January 2022. Red pin – AQMesh relocation; Black pin – COVID-19 key milestone. Image created with BioRender.com with information from (SPICE, 2022).

3.4 Methodology

A full detailed document of the methodology utilised are documented in Section 2.1. The AQMesh (Environmental Instruments Ltd.) air pollution monitor was field calibrated as specified by the manufacturer guidelines against two reference monitoring stations at Gordon St., Paisley, Renfrewshire and High St., Irvine, North Ayrshire. This was performed to increase the accuracy of air pollution measurements over the study period and allow for the comparison of the low-cost monitoring device against the stationary equipment. Alongside the reference monitoring sites air pollution concentrations were obtained from Stranraer and Stevenston. These sites were chosen because they fall within COPD hotspot regions and have features not usually represented in previous studies. Stranraer is a remote location which previously hosted a shipping port (now relocated to nearby Cairnryan) this port facilitates the transport of passengers and freight / heavy goods vehicles. Both Stranraer and Irvine also share urban elements such as a town with residences, retail, educational institutions public services alongside rural features such as agriculture, sparsely populated surrounding areas and other localities with remote rural classification. All site measurements were collated and compared to the guideline and regulatory limitations and breeches identified, incomplete collated annual data was created from partial data as an approximate representative measure. Additionally, this an SIMD scale deprived area and previous links have been found between these areas, COPD development and separately, air pollution. The AQMesh was also utilised in a study of the gaseous pollutant within the internal compartment of two different fuel classification vehicles while in operation.

3.5 Results

3.5.1 AQMesh Calibration / comparison of air pollution measurements with that of regulatory air monitoring stations

The AQMesh monitor was calibrated as per manufacturer recommendations at two sites, Gordon St., Paisley and High St., Irvine. This was to increase the reliability of the measurements obtained from the AQMesh pod but also to provide a comparison of measurements obtained from both the pod and the regulatory sites.

3.5.2 AQMesh calibration against Gordon St., Paisley air quality reference monitor

Figure 3.6 – Voltage measurement trace recorded from AQMesh during Paisley calibration period. Data obtained over 7 day period, 23 – 29 December 2019.

Figure 3.7 – Environmental parameter two-step calibration linear regression performed at Paisley site. A) air pressure and B) temperature from measurements recorded from AQMesh over 7 day period, 23-29th December 2019. Raw values from the Paisley Gordon St. monitoring station and AQMesh shown on the left and corrected vs. raw values shown on the right. The calculations used to calibrate AQMesh pod measurements are highlighted by a black box. REF, Reference station; Paisley site code, 687100.

Figure 3.8 –NO_x two-step calibration linear regression performed at Paisley site. Recorded from AQMesh over 7 day period from 23-29th December 2019. A) Raw values from the Paisley Gordon St. monitoring station and AQMesh shown on the left and corrected vs. raw values shown on the right. B) Trace (15 min averages) of values obtained from AQMesh (red) and Paisley monitoring site (black). The calculations used to calibrate AQMesh pod measurements are highlighted by a black box. REF, Reference station; Paisley site code, 687100.

Figure 3.9 – PM₁₀ two-step calibration linear regression performed at Paisley site. Recorded from AQMesh over 7 day period from 23-29th December 2019. A) Raw values from the Paisley Gordon St. monitoring station and AQMesh shown on the left and corrected vs. raw values shown on the right. B) Trace (15 min averages) of values obtained from AQMesh (red) and Paisley monitoring site (black). The calculations used to calibrate AQMesh pod measurements are surrounded by a black box. REF, Reference station; Paisley site code, 687100.

Figure 3.10- Trace of Humidity values from AQMesh obtained during Paisley calibration period. Data obtained during the Paisley reference site calibration period (23rd – 29th December 2019) (15 min averages).

Calibrations were performed as described in Section 2.1.2. The measurements used to perform the calibration at the Paisley site (REF 687100) were obtained from the period spanning 23rd to 29th December 2019. All air pollution data was analysed from 15 minute averages unless otherwise stated. The voltage of the AQMesh monitor can affect the quality and frequency of PM measurements; the voltage during this time was deemed acceptable as this did not fall below 3.4 V over the duration of the calibration period (Figure 3.6).

Pre-calibration measurements from the AQMesh correlated well with that of air pressure and temperature values recorded from the monitoring site as shown in Figure 3.7 ($R^2=0.9986$ and 0.9856 , respectively). As too did the NO and NO₂ values obtained from both monitors ($R^2=0.938$ and 0.9051 , respectively), which is illustrated by not only the correlation between the synchronised NO_x measurements (Figure 3.8 A) but also that of the time resolved traces from both instruments (Figure 3.8 B).

Calibration was also performed for the PM₁₀ measurements of the AQMesh during the same time period at the Paisley site. The resulting linear correlation was far poorer than that of the gaseous and environmental linear regression calculations. Not only was the coefficient of determination poor ($R^2=0.0009505$) but the trace values demonstrated far increased measurements obtained from the AQMesh in comparison to the reference site on days 1/2 and 5/6 ($> 50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) (Figure 3.9). Calibration for other PM fractions (4, 2.5 & 1) could not be performed as the Paisley monitoring site did not record these measurements. One possible source of interference of PM measurements that must be considered is the environmental temperature and humidity. Temperature during this time fell within the permitted -20 to +50 °C range (Figure 3.7), however, humidity often exceeded the manufacturer stated maximum guidelines of 85 % for optimal performance. (Figure 3.10).

3.5.3 AQMesh calibration against High St., Irvine Site air quality reference monitor

Figure 3.11 – Trace of voltage values from AQMesh obtained during Irvine calibration period. Data obtained during the Irvine reference site calibration period (13th – 19th November 2020) (15 min averages).

Figure 3.12 – Environmental parameter two-step calibration linear regression performed at Irvine site. A) air pressure, B) temperature and C) humidity from measurements recorded from AQMesh over 7 day period from 13-19th November 2020. Raw values from the Irvine High St. monitoring station and AQMesh shown on the left and corrected vs. raw values shown on the right. The calculations used to calibrate AQMesh pod measurements are surrounded by a black box. REF, Reference station; Irvine site code; 609100.

Figure 3.13 – Two-step Nox calibration linear regression performed at Irvine site. Recorded from AQMesh over 7 day period from 13-19th November 2020. A) Raw values from the Irvine High St. monitoring station and AQMesh shown on the left and corrected vs. raw values shown on the right. B) Trace (15 min averages) of values obtained from AQMesh (red) and Irvine monitoring site (black). The calculations used to calibrate AQMesh pod measurements are surrounded by a black box. REF, Reference station; Irvine site code, 609100.

Figure 3.14 – Two-step PM calibration linear regression performed at Irvine site. Recorded from AQMesh over 7 day period from 13-19th November 2020, A) PM₁₀, B) PM_{2.5} C) PM₁. Raw values from the Irvine High St. monitoring station and AQMesh shown (left) and corrected vs. raw values (centre). Trace (15 min averages) of values obtained from AQMesh (red) and Irvine monitoring site (black) shown on the right. The calculations used to calibrate AQMesh pod measurements are surrounded by a black box. REF, Reference station; Irvine site code, 609100.

Calibration during the AQMesh co-location with the Irvine reference monitoring site (REF 609100) was performed from the period 13th to 19th November 2020. The voltage during this period remained stable at 3.6 V (Figure 3.11), and therefore should not have affected the measurements obtained during this period.

Environmental parameter linear regressions for air pressure ($R^2 = 0.9991$), temperature ($R^2=0.9885$) and humidity ($R^2=0.9362$) showed little variation in correlation between AQMesh pod and reference monitor time resolved measurements (Figure 3.12).

Similar to observations from the Paisley monitoring site calibration, the Nox values from the AQMesh correlated well with that of the Irvine High Street reference monitoring site, this can be seen in both linear correlation and the measurement trace trends (Figure 3.13).

As the Irvine monitoring site was actively measuring not only PM₁₀ but also PM_{2.5} and PM₁, these particulate fractions could be calibrated against the monitor. Unlike the linear regression of PM₁₀ measurements performed at the Paisley site, the coefficient of determination of the monitoring methods showed far less variability ($R^2 = 0.4892$) (Figure 3.14A). The PM_{2.5} values also showed a high correlation ($R^2=0.5336$) (Figure 3.14B), whereas, that of the PM₁ was more comparable to the 10 μ m fraction calibration observed from the Paisley site linear regression ($R^2=0.08417$) (Figure 3.14C). Nevertheless, all trace trends appeared to demonstrate similar trends and unlike at the Paisley site, the AQMesh measurements underestimated the PM concentrations when compared with the Irvine reference station monitoring system.

Overall, the measurements observed between the AQMesh monitor and the reference sites showed high correlations for environmental parameter measurements (air pressure, temperature and humidity) and gaseous pollutants at both the Paisley and Irvine monitoring sites. Additionally, there was reasonable correlation between PM fractions 10 and 2.5 μ m fraction measurements but not of 1 μ m at the Irvine site, however, this high correlation for PM₁₀ was not observed upon comparison of the AQMesh with the Paisley site monitor. Ozone was not measured at either of the reference monitoring sites and therefore monitor calibration for this pollutant could not be performed.

3.5.4 Air pollution profile of Gordon Street, Paisley

3.5.4.1 Gaseous pollutant profile of Gordon Street, Paisley

Figure 3.15 – Voltage, temperature and humidity value traces from AQMesh at Paisley site. Data (15 min averages) obtained over the period from 11th October 2019 to 13th January 2020.

Figure 3.16 – *NO* concentration measurements obtained from Paisley site. (A) monthly averages from AQMesh and Paisley reference site. (B) monthly averages from AQMesh alone. Monthly average data displayed as Mean ± SEM. (C) Trace (15 min averages) from AQMesh. Data obtained over the period from 11th October 2019 to 13th January 2020. (A) monthly average comparison between AQMesh and Paisley monitoring site.

Figure 3.17 – *NO₂* concentration measurements obtained from Paisley site. (A) monthly average comparison between AQMesh and Paisley monitoring site. (B) monthly averages from AQMesh alone. Monthly average data displayed as Mean ± SEM. (C) Trace (1 hr averages) from AQMesh. Data obtained over the period from 11th October 2019 to 13th January 2020. (D) Collated *NO₂* average from AQMesh over entire sampling period from 11th October 2019 to 13th January 2020, given as a representative indicator of annual values.

Figure 3.18 – O₃ concentration measurements obtained from AQMesh at Paisley site. (Left) monthly averages. Monthly average data displayed as Mean ± SEM. (Right) Trace (8 hr averages). Data obtained over the period from 11th October 2019 to 13th January 2020.

The AQMesh was located within the cage of the Paisley monitoring site as previously described in section 2.1.3.1 (Calibration sites: Gordon Street, Paisley, Renfrewshire). The monitor was located at this site from 7th October 2019 to 28th January 2020. As the monitor was installed with new sensors and battery and had to adjust to the new environment prior to monitoring, data obtained from the Paisley site used in this analysis was obtained from 11th October 2019 to 13th January 2020. Voltage remained stable, not falling below 3.3 V at any stage during the analysis period. Temperature also fell within the allowed limitations for optimal AQMesh measurement acquisition although, as with the example period, the humidity was frequently above the 85 % recommended maximum limit, Figure 3.15.

The NO and NO₂ data collected during the sampling period are highlighted in Figure 3.16 and Figure 3.17, respectively.

NO values measured from this site regularly exceed the common annual NO_x limit of 30 µg/m³ shared between the EU directive and national air quality (NAQ) regulations (for all current air quality limitation guidelines / regulations see

Table 1.1, correct as of March 2023). Although there is no stated limit of NO, a limitation breach here is still indicated as NO_x values calculated as the sum of NO & NO₂ (Mazzeo, Venegas and Choren, 2005). If this analysis had been performed for the year, the NO annual average could likely be higher than limitation values as NO, as a precursor for NO₂, is typically elevated in more temperate seasons and conditions (Platikanov *et al.*, 2022).

Conversely, this period might be considered as the optimal time to analyse NO₂ as this should have an inverse environmental relationship. During this time NO₂ values did not exceed the 200 µg/m³ 1 hr mean or the 40 µg/m³ annual mean, remaining below all guidelines / regulations barring the current WHO limitations of 10 µg/m³. Over the entirety of the year the concentrations for this pollutant could potentially be lower than those observed during this period and the 40 µg/m³ limit would be unlikely to

be breached. It is improbable that the values would have fallen below $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ assuming similar travel trends for all seasons, however, this cannot be fully concluded without the remaining annual data.

Since O_3 is not measured at the Paisley or Irvine sites, the data, unlike that of the NO_x values, could not be corrected and so is used in raw form in all analysis henceforth. Although, the gas sensors used within the AQMesh pod are calibrated during manufacture and are reported to be accurate to ± 10 ppb ($\sim 20 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) according to the manufacturer standard operating procedure.

From the data obtained from the urban Paisley site it is evident that the level of O_3 pollution surpasses the $100 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ WHO (2005, 2021) and NAQ regulation limits & the $120 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ EU regulation limits based on an 8 hr mean. From the measurements obtained between 11th October 2019 and 13th January 2020 the $100 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ limit was exceeded a total of 92 times and the $120 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ limit 43 times as evidenced by the trace trend of O_3 (Figure 3.18). This far surpasses the maximum allowed exceedances of 3 days per year (99th percentile) and 10 days per year for WHO & NAQ limits respectively. Furthermore, this strongly suggests that the 25-day (3-year mean) EU limit would also be surpassed based on the information obtained over the 3-month period. As with the NO concentrations, O_3 could also reach elevated levels within the summer period (DEFRA, 2021).

3.5.4.2 Particulate pollutant profile of Gordon Street., Paisley

Figure 3.19 – Particulate matter concentration measurements obtained from AQMesh at Paisley site. (Left) monthly averages. Monthly average data displayed as Mean ± SEM. (Right) Trace (15 min averages). Data obtained over the period from 11th October 2019 to 13th January 2020.

Figure 3.20 – $PM_{2.5}$ concentration trace (24 hr averages) and annual mean obtained at Paisley site. Data obtained over the period from 11th October 2019 to 13th January 2020. Collated average from AQMesh over entire sampling period.

Figure 3.21 – PM₁₀ concentration measurements obtained from AQMesh at Paisley site. A) Monthly average values (uncorrected). B) Trace (24 hr averages, uncorrected data). C) Corrected monthly average data from AQMesh and Paisley reference monitoring data. D) Uncorrected monthly average data from AQMesh and Paisley reference monitoring data. Data obtained over the period from 11th October 2019 to 13th January 2020. Monthly average data displayed as Mean ± SEM. E) Uncorrected annual average based data obtained from AQMesh site obtained over the period from 11th October 2019 to 13th January.

Particulate matter measurements obtained during the Paisley site sampling period are illustrated in Figure 3.19, Figure 3.20 and Figure 3.21. There are no regulatory limits or guidelines implemented into air pollution control strategies for PM₁ and PM₄, although including these values allows the identification of common trends between the particulate measures obtained. No correction factor was applied to particulate data described except PM₁₀, where stated, as other fraction levels were not recorded by the Paisley reference monitor. PM₁₀ uncorrected data was compared with guidelines and limitations due to the erratic nature of the data post-correction (large negative values).

During the period of deployment, the levels of PM_{2.5} regularly surpassed all of the 24 hr and annual mean limitations (highest limit 25 µg/m³) (Figure 3.20). The collated monthly average values (max approx. 35 µg/m³ in Dec.) met or surpassed the annual mean Scottish Air Quality objective (10 µg/m³) on every month studied (Figure 3.19). A similar trend is observed when referring to the PM₁₀ (uncorrected) data as the highest implemented limit (50 µg/m³, 24 hr mean) is often exceeded, this alongside the 45 µg/m³ limit were exceeded on 31 occasions (Figure 3.21). This constitutes a breach of all guideline limits, including allowed exceedances, barring the EU limitation which allows 35 per annum, although a breach is therefore strongly suggested due to the proximity to limitation allowances considering the short time-frame. Additionally, in months December and January, average values were higher than the max 40 µg/m³ annual mean limit (EU regulation) and consequently far above the annual mean limit of 18 µg/m³ limit stated in the Scottish national air quality objectives. This is reflected in the annual data for this period (Figure 3.21 E).

Studies suggest that PM measurements can be elevated during the winter period as boundary layer inversions form (attributed to low ground temperatures), trapping this pollution locally. Although, spring is another period when PM concentrations can be elevated when compared to the rest of the year (Macintyre *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, when studying the monthly average values here, the measurements cannot be used as an absolute proxy to inform the annual mean values for these pollutants as the sampling period is only a partial period across 4 months. When comparing the reliability of measurements obtained from both reference monitor and AQMesh, there appears to be some disparity between both corrected and uncorrected measurements and the monitoring station (Figure 3.21 C& D). Therefore, reliability of measurements obtained during this period are questionable. Certainly, the corrected AQMesh values reach impossibly large negative values, however, the uncorrected values, if taken to be correct, suggest massively underreported concentrations from the Paisley reference monitor.

3.5.5 Air pollution profile of Sun Street, Stranraer

3.5.5.1 Gaseous pollutant profile of Sun Street, Stranraer

Figure 3.22 – Voltage, temperature and humidity value traces from AQMesh at Stranraer site. Data (15 min averages) obtained over the period from February 17th 2020 to 7th November 2020.

Figure 3.23 – NO concentration measurements obtained from Stranraer site. (left) Monthly average and (right) Trace (15 min averages) from AQMesh over the period from February 17th 2020 to 7th November 2020. Monthly average data displayed as Mean ± SEM.

Figure 3.24 – *NO₂ concentration measurements obtained from Stranraer site. (A) Monthly averages (uncorrected) (B) Trace (1 hr averages, uncorrected data) (C) Collated NO₂ average from AQMesh over entire sampling period (uncorrected) (D) Monthly averages (corrected) (E) Trace (1 hr averages, corrected data) (F) Collated NO₂ average from AQMesh over entire sampling period (corrected). Data is obtained from AQMesh over the period from February 17th 2020 to 7th November 2020. Monthly average data displayed as Mean ± SEM.*

Figure 3.25 – O₃ concentration measurements obtained from Stranraer site. (left) Monthly averages and (right) Trace (8 hr averages) from AQMesh over the period from February 17th 2020 to 7th November 2020. Monthly average data displayed as Mean ± SEM.

The AQMesh monitor was placed on a lighting column on Sun Street, Stranraer as previously described (section 2.1.4.1). The monitor was located at this site from February 17th 2020 to 7th November 2020. Prior to movement of the monitor, it was removed from the Paisley site and relocated to a courtyard within the grounds of the Paisley campus of the University of the West of Scotland. This was performed to ease the adjustment to new environmental conditions in Stranraer. Voltage of the AQMesh pod remained relatively stable during the months of February to April and June to November, however, voltage readings obtained during April to June indicated instability and therefore power loss.

On March 11th 2020 a global viral pandemic was announced by the World Health Organisation due to the widespread transmission of the SARS-CoV-2 virus. All data hereafter must be considered with a caveat that air pollution trends may have been influenced by unprecedented, drastically altered anthropogenic activities.

Due to the subsequent implementation of social distancing rules and travel restrictions the power loss issues could not be corrected until an authorised team from ACOEM replaced the battery. Consequently, PM measurements from this period halted from 13th April 2020 until battery replacement on May 26th 2020 (Figure 3.22). However, gaseous pollution sampling continued throughout. Temperature during this time remained within ideal limits while humidity regularly breached the 85 % recommended upper limit (Figure 3.22), as previously considered this may be a factor of PM measurement interference.

NO measurements obtained from the Stranraer site are illustrated in Figure 3.23. Although average monthly values approached the 30 µg/m³ annual limit, this was not met. Due to the apparent trend of elevated levels in February, October and November (when compared with other months) this might indicate that highest values may have been observed in December and January. Alongside the concentration values from NO₂ monitoring it appears that there may have been a breach in NO_x limitations as the NO₂ annual value alone reaches ~30 µg/m³.

NO₂ average monthly values were not close to the annual mean 40 µg/m³ limit determined by WHO (2005), EU or the NAQ objectives (Figure 3.24). The highest observed prescaled value was < 10 µg/m³ NO₂ in November however once the correction was applied the highest observed value was 39 µg/m³.

As an upwards trajectory is observed from July onwards the highest mean values could be observed in December or January. Nevertheless, this would be unlikely to skew the average above the 40 µg/m³ 2005 WHO, EU & NAQ NO₂ limit. Furthermore, the 200 µg/m³ 1 hr limit was not surpassed; from the time resolved average values measurements were not recorded at values above 100 µg/m³. Conversely, corrected values did show an annual exceedance above the new 2021 WHO guideline on 10 µg/m³, with reference to monthly average values it appears that this may indicate a breach for the remaining portion of the year as these averages do not fall below 20 µg/m³ on any single monitored month.

Analysis of O₃ measurements (Figure 3.25) demonstrated that levels were regularly elevated above the 8 hr WHO & NAQ limitation of 100 µg/m³ and EU limitation of 120 µg/m³; this is particularly evident in February and April where the monthly average exceeds the 100 µg/m³ figure. The maximum allowed exceedances of these values are 3 days per year (99th percentile), 25 days (averaged over 3 years) and 10 days per year for WHO, EU & NAQ limits, respectively. From the data obtained we can see that the 100 µg/m³ limit was surpassed on 214 occasions and the 120 µg/m³ limit was surpassed on 58 occasions. This constitutes exceedances of 100 days and 41 days, respectively indicating a breach.

3.5.5.2 Particulate pollutant profile of Sun Street, Stranraer

Figure 3.26 – Particulate matter concentration measurements obtained from AQMesh at Stranraer site. (Left) monthly averages. (Right) Trace (15 min averages). Data obtained over the period from February 17th 2020 to 7th November 2020. Monthly average data displayed as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 3.27 – $PM_{2.5}$ concentration measurements obtained from AQMesh at Stranraer site. Uncorrected data. Left) Trace of AQMesh data (24 hr averages). Right) Annual data collated. Data obtained over the period from February 17th 2020 to 7th November 2020. Mean annual data displayed as Mean \pm SEM.

Figure 3.28 – PM_{10} concentration measurements obtained from AQMesh at Stranraer site. A) Uncorrected data. B) Corrected data. Left) Monthly average values . Middle) Trace (24 hr averages) of corrected AQMesh data. Right) Annual data collated. Data obtained over the period from February 17th 2020 to 7th November 2020. Mean monthly and annual data displayed as Mean \pm SEM.

As previously discussed, PM measurements were not obtained over a partial period from April to May due to power depletion and energy saving mechanisms. Therefore, for these months the remaining data has been used to obtain a representative monthly average.

PM_{2.5} values demonstrate that although the continuous measurements exceed objective values, reference to monthly averages shows that values were typically lower than that of the lowest reference guideline (WHO 2021: 5 µg/m³) (Figure 3.26). This is reflected in the annual data, 24 hr analysis of concentrations shows that the new WHO 2021 guidelines were exceeded on two separate occasions, without the remaining annual data it would not be possible to determine if this guideline was breached on the year studied (Figure 3.27).

Comparatively, PM₁₀ (uncorrected) levels were higher with reference to the WHO 2021 guideline annual mean value of 15 µg/m³ on March, however, this does not constitute a breach for the representative annual period (Figure 3.26 & Figure 3.28).

Data are displayed in both uncorrected form and corrected (factor obtained from calibration with the Paisley monitor applied). As can be observed, the corrected values are far higher than the uncorrected values, with annual values ~10 x higher in the former when compared with the latter. This data is unlikely to be reliable as the calibration of this pollutant against the Paisley reference station showed little correlation. All other PM data is shown as uncorrected only due to lack of monitoring at the Paisley site for comparison.

3.5.6 Air pollution profile of High Street, Irvine

3.5.6.1 Gaseous pollutant profile of High Street, Irvine

Figure 3.29 –Voltage, temperature and humidity value traces from AQMesh at Irvine site. Data (15 min averages) obtained over the period from November 11th 2020 to July 20th 2021.

Figure 3.30 – NO concentration measurements obtained from Irvine site. (Top) Monthly averages from AQMesh (corrected) and Irvine reference monitoring station. Mean monthly average displayed as Mean ± SEM. (Bottom) Trace (15 min averages until March 8th then values are 1 hr averages) from AQMesh over the period from November 11th 2020 to July 20th 2021.

Figure 3.31 – NO₂ concentration measurements obtained from Irvine site. (A) Monthly averages from AQMesh (corrected) and Irvine reference monitoring station. Mean monthly average displayed as Mean ± SEM. (B) Trace (1 hr averages). (C) Collated NO₂ average from AQMesh over entire sampling period. Red line indicates WHO guideline (2021) limit of 10 µg/m³ annual average. Data obtained over the period from November 11th 2020 to July 20th 2021.

Figure 3.32 – O₃ concentration measurements obtained from Irvine site. (Left) Monthly averages from AQMesh (uncorrected). Mean monthly average displayed as Mean \pm SEM. (B) Trace (8 hr averages). Data obtained over the period from November 11th 2020 to July 20th 2021.

Following AQMesh placement in Stranraer the monitor was relocated to Irvine High Street on November 11th 2020 where monitoring continued until July 20th 2021. As with the Stranraer location, PM monitoring during this time halted due to depletion of power, as indicated by voltage (Figure 3.29). Temperature remained within allowed limits but humidity surpassed the 85% guidance limit, and therefore could be a source of PM interference (Figure 3.29). Gaseous measurements did not halt and were obtained during the entirety of the period and data were used in the analysis shown here. During the sampling period data was removed from the airmonitors.net website and was only accessible via: https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/data/data_selector_service. Therefore, all data used in the Irvine reference data and 15 min raw data trace are obtained from the period spanning March 8th until July 20th 2021 and are illustrated as hourly average values (Figure 3.30 & Figure 3.31).

NO concentrations regularly increased to over 100 µg/m³, however, the regulatory value limit for NO_x is an annual mean of 30 µg/m³ indicating a pollutant concentration breach, although average values were typically less than or equal to 10 µg/m³ (Figure 3.30). A discrepancy of approximately 5 µg/m³ was observed between corrected AQMesh values and those obtained from the Irvine reference monitor.

Concentrations of NO₂ all fell under the 40 µg/m³ limits set by the EU, the NAQ objectives and the 2005 WHO guidelines. Some months were above the 2021 WHO guideline limit of 10 µg/m³, and subsequently the observed representative annual average also breached this limit (Figure 3.31). Concentrations did not exceed the 200 µg/m³ 1 hr WHO, EU, NAQ limit. Analysis of O₃ values (Figure 3.32) showed that readings often surpassed the 100 µg/m³ (8 hr) limit, monthly values were commonly observed at 60 – 80 µg/m³. Although the 120 µg/m³ limit was not broken on any of the days analysed, the 100 µg/m³ limit was exceeded on 37 separate days.

3.5.6.2 *Particulate pollutant profile of High Street, Irvine*

Figure 3.33 – PM_{10} concentration measurements obtained from Irvine site. (Top) Monthly averages from AQMesh (corrected) and Irvine reference site. Mean monthly average displayed as Mean \pm SEM. (Bottom) Trace (15 min averages). Data obtained over the period from November 11th 2020 to July 20th 2021.

Figure 3.34 – $PM_{2.5}$ concentration measurements obtained from Irvine site. (A) Monthly averages from AQMesh (corrected) and Irvine reference site. Mean monthly average displayed as Mean \pm SEM. (B) Trace (24 hr averages). Data obtained over the period from November 11th 2020 to July 20th 2021. Data from period 28th January 2020 to period 12th February 2020 in trace replaced with representative Irvine monitoring data. (C) Collated $PM_{2.5}$ average from AQMesh over entire sampling period.

Figure 3.35 – PM₁₀ concentration measurements obtained from Irvine site. (A) Monthly averages from AQMesh (corrected) and Irvine reference site. Mean monthly average displayed as Mean ± SEM. (B) Trace (24 hr averages). Data obtained over the period from November 11th 2020 to July 20th 2021. (C) Collated PM₁₀ average from AQMesh over entire sampling period.

As previously discussed, PM measurements were not recorded from 29th November 2021 to February 2022 as a result of battery depletion. A partial average is provided here as a representative of complete monthly average data. Observations from PM₁, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀ (Figure 3.33, Figure 3.34, and Figure 3.35 respectively) data show a discrepancy between corrected AQMesh data and data from the Irvine reference monitor. Interestingly AQMesh PM₁ values were higher than Irvine monitoring values, whereas a discrepancy on this scale was not seen in PM_{2.5} or PM₁₀ analysis.

PM_{2.5} corrected values were lower than all limitations according to monthly values except from the 5 µg/m³ annual WHO 2021 guideline. Furthermore, 24 hr values exceeded the 2005 and 2021 limitations; however, a breach was found for the lower guideline as this was surpassed more than 3 times.

When investigating PM₁₀ concentrations most monthly average values and the annual mean are far from the lowest regulation annual mean concentration of 15 µg/m³ (WHO 2021) (from both AQMesh corrected and Irvine monitor). The 15 µg/m³ 2021 WHO guideline and 18 µg/m³ NAQ objective (annual mean) were not met. The time resolved trace shows that concentrations surpassed the WHO 2005 50 µg/m³ 24 hr mean limitation on one occasion, however, as there are 3 exceedances permitted per annum, this does not constitute a breach.

3.5.7 Air pollution profile of Glencairn Street, Stevenston

3.5.7.1 Gaseous pollutant profile of Glencairn Street, Stevenston

Figure 3.36 – Voltage, temperature and humidity value traces from AQMesh at Stevenston site. Data (15 min averages) obtained over the period from July 20th 2021 to January 10th 2022.

Figure 3.37 – NO concentration measurements obtained from Stevenston site. (Left) Monthly averages from AQMesh (corrected). Mean monthly average displayed as Mean ± SEM. (Right) Trace (15 min averages) from AQMesh over the period from July 20th 2021 to January 10th 2022.

Figure 3.38 – NO₂ concentration measurements obtained from Stevenston site. (A) Trace (1 hr averages) from AQMesh over the period from July 20th 2021 to January 10th 2022. (B) Monthly averages from AQMesh (corrected). Mean monthly average displayed as Mean ± SEM. (C) Collated NO₂ average from AQMesh over entire sampling period. Red line indicates WHO guideline (2021) limit of 10µg/m³ annual average.

Figure 3.39 – O₃ concentration measurements obtained from Stevenston site. (Left) Monthly averages from AQMesh (corrected). Mean monthly average displayed as Mean ± SEM. (Right) Trace (8 hr averages) from AQMesh over the period from July 20th 2021 to January 10th 2022.

Throughout the majority of the sampling period from July 20th 2021 to January 10th 2022, voltage remained stable, only beginning to drop on December 30th 2021 (henceforth PM sampling ceased). Temperature remained within ideal limitations. However, as with all other sampling periods, humidity exceeded the 85 % recommended surrounding environmental humidity and therefore could be a source of interference in monitoring during this time (Figure 3.36).

Analysis of NO and NO₂ levels (Figure 3.37 and Figure 3.38 respectively) showed that concentrations did not exceed the annual (with reference to monthly averages) or hourly EU and NAQ objectives. The NO₂ total average value did surpass 10 µg/m³, the annual mean specified by 2021 WHO guidelines. Elevated concentrations appeared to be present in months September to December, if concentrations remained low from January to July the average annual value may have been lower than the guideline limit.

Although monthly measurements suggest the mean values of ozone were typically <80 µg/m³ (Figure 3.39), O₃ values surpassed the 120 µg/m³ 8 hr limitation although this does not constitute a breach as the limitation set by the EU allows 25 occasions for breach and this limit was only met twice. However, the 100 µg/m³ 8 hr limit was regularly exceeded (16 occasions). This would mean a breach of the 2005 and 2021 WHO limitations (0 and 3 exceedance allowances per annum) and the NAQ limitation (10 exceedance allowance per annum).

3.5.7.2 *Particulate pollutant profile of Glencairn Street, Stevenston*

Figure 3.40 – Particulate matter concentration measurements obtained from AQMesh at Stevenston site. (Left) monthly averages. (Right) Trace (15 min averages). Data obtained over the period from July 20th 2021 to December 30th 2021. Monthly average data displayed as Mean ± SEM.

Figure 3.41 – PM_{2.5} & PM₁₀ concentration measurements obtained from Stevenston site. All values here are corrected. A) PM_{2.5} collated values. B) PM₁₀ collated values. (Left) Monthly averages from AQMesh during sampling period. (Middle) Trace (24 hr averages). (Right) Collated PM₁₀ average from AQMesh over entire sampling period. Mean monthly average displayed as Mean ± SEM. Data obtained over the period from July 20th 2021 to December 30th 2021.

As a result of power loss, PM measurements were not recorded from December 30th 2021 onwards and therefore all January measurements of this pollutant were not included in analysis. From the data observed in Figure 3.40 and Figure 3.41 it is evident that PM_{2.5} values are elevated above the WHO 2021 annual guideline of 5 µg/m³, although as this is a representative annual mean the limit may not have been surpassed in reference to the complete annual period. It can also be seen that the WHO 2005 and 2005 & 2021 24 hr limits were breached as trace values show levels regularly exceeded 25 µg/m³ (>3 days) (Figure 3.41).

PM₁₀ did not surpass the annual mean regulatory limit of any guidelines / regulations (Figure 3.41). Conversely, with reference to the 24 hr limits exceedances were seen these events were also spread across more than 3 separate days, as is evident by the trace values. The 50 and 45 µg/m³ limits/guidelines were surpassed on 5 and 6 days, respectively. This constitutes a breach of both WHO limitations as 3 days per annum are permitted to reach these elevated levels before surpassing the guidelines.

3.5.8 Internal Combustion Engine and Electronic Vehicle Internal Ambient Pollution

Figure 3.42 – Electronic Vehicle (EV) and Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) Vehicle Air Pollution Profile. Pollutant concentrations recorded by AQMesh monitor from rear storage compartment. Measurements obtained from ICE on 7th November 2021 and EV on 10th January 2022, over 1 hr period. Collated measurements shown with centrelines representing medians, upper quartile above and lower quartile below, whiskers represent max and min values. Unpaired t-test * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ ($n = 4$).

The AQMesh monitor was loaded into the storage compartment of an Internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicle and on a separate occasion an electric vehicle (EV) to measure the internal pollution environment. NO_x and O₃ measurements were obtained whilst the vehicles were in operation, the ICE measurements were obtained on November 7th 2022 at 10 am and the EV measurements were obtained on 10th January 2022 at 3:30 pm. Measurements from a 1 hr period were then collated (15 min frequency) and compared. PM concentrations were not compared as this parameter was not recorded by the AQMesh in January 2022.

Measurements of NO and NO₂ were collated and compared, findings showed that the electric vehicle had significantly lower levels of both NO and NO₂ when compared with that of the ICE vehicle. Measurable concentrations were seen of O₃ in the EV, however, these were substantially low, this alongside the presence of negative ozone values triggered an error in the AQMesh. This indicated that there had been a depletion event in the measurements but was likely the case of the air pollution

collection within a closed space. This further indicates that the air pollution measured from within the storage area originated from external exhaust within the respective vehicles. Additionally, on no other occasion were such low concentrations of O₃ observed when measuring ambient concentrations. Results here suggest that there are higher levels of NO_x within the ICE when compared with the EV, this may be related to availability of the gaseous pollutants to travel into the storage cabin from outside or the proximity of the exhaust to the internal space. Values of NO₂ recorded from the ICE were above the annual WHO guidelines of 40 µg/m³ and consequently 10 µg/m³ whereas the measurements from the EV were above the 10 µg/m³ limit only.

3.6 Discussion

3.6.1 Air pollution calibration

Air pollution monitoring was performed at four locations, two of which were reference stations at which the AQMesh monitor was stationed to calibrate obtained measurements. The two other locations were identified areas within the lesser monitored COPD hotspot focus locations of Dumfries and Galloway & Ayrshire and Arran. Following analysis of calibration data at both sites, environmental parameters of air pressure, temperature and humidity were obtained, all with R^2 values of correlations between AQMesh and reference monitor of > 0.9 . Additionally, NO and NO₂ concentrations from the AQMesh and reference showed general agreement at both sites, with all R^2 determination coefficients showing little variation (lowest $R^2=0.8486$). Furthermore, a comparison of time resolved datasets demonstrated a strong trend correlation. The trend observations, however, were lower and correlation variation was higher, from observations of PM concentration determination compared to gaseous pollution at both calibration sites. Other studies have shown a similar correlation for PM₁₀ ($R^2 = 0.12 - 0.34$) (Wahlborg, Björling and Mattsson, 2021) as was observed from the Irvine calibration ($R^2=0.4892$) and PM_{2.5} values had slightly higher R^2 at 0.5366. Conversely, PM₁ R^2 values from the Irvine site and PM₁₀ from the Paisley site were very low (0.08417 and 0.0009505, respectively). PM₁ measurements may always show this inconsistency, but PM₁₀ correlation varies drastically between the two locations. The reason for this discrepancy is unclear, humidity may have been an interfering factor in this analysis, as this can lead to condensation which can affect the optical particle counter *via* deliquescence of particulates. Although all sites including the Irvine calibration site also had similar humidity levels, this can be further complicated if local PM properties promote deliquescence and therefore potential for hygroscopic growth (D'Angelo *et al.*, 2016). The AQMesh has a flagging system following determination of this interference, although data included here was presented with no such warning. The system can be included with an optional heating element to prevent this interference; however, this was not a feature of the unit discussed here.

Another potential factor which must be considered is the PM determination method utilised at each of the calibration sites. The Paisley reference monitor uses the TEOM / FDMS gravimetric detection method whereas the Irvine site uses a FIDAS 200 fine dust optical analyser system, which is more similar to the optical sensor system utilised by the AQMesh. The most likely scenario observed here may be that a meteorological event such as mist has caused interference of the particulate monitoring capabilities of the AQMesh at the Paisley site. From data obtained from the open access Met Office Data Access System (MIDAS) recorded in nearby town Bishopton (Renfrewshire, 55.907, -4.533), there were a number of occasions on 23rd, 27th & 28th of December (during the calibration period) where visibility was “poor” and humidity levels were often above 90 % relative humidity (Met Office, 2022). This indicates that a weather event such as mist is likely to have occurred (Met Office, 2023). If another

event such as this did not occur at the Irvine site, then less of a discrepancy between sampling outcomes would be observed during calibration.

Interference such as this is less likely to impact the sampling observed from TEOM-FDMS sampling, although it has been well documented that this system is limited by inability to accurately measure semi-volatile compounds (Green, Fuller and Baker, 2009). For this reason the FDMS system was developed to determine volatile components of ambient samples and provide a correction of the TEOM sample and increase accuracy. As both the TEOM-FDMS and FIDAS 200 systems have sample drying processes (Palas GmbH, 2022; Green, Fuller and Baker, 2009) but this is absent in the AQMesh system this may explain the discrepancies observed during PM calibration. Further studies would preferably include more than one AQMesh pod to determine inter-pod variability, and increase reliability of typical operation of the monitor. Furthermore, it would be useful to observe the function of the AQMesh when supplemented with the heated element feature to determine if resulting measurements would allow better correlation with the TEOM FDMS under subpar environmental conditions.

Humidity interference is a particularly important interference factor in countries such as Scotland, where levels are regularly higher than those within ideal limitations, as was observed in every site observed within this study. Following this observation it should be noted that when performing monitor calibration, resulting correlation and trace comparison should be checked during the period. If measurements do not correlate well this can lead to large deviations from typical measurements and resulting unnaturally high or negative values as observed in the “corrected” data trace illustrated in Figure 3.28. This could also lead to altered values, leading to the misclassification of the local pollution profile in line with AQMA guidelines.

Another drawback of the AQMesh system is the requirement for calibration for improved monitoring accuracy. In this study it was possible to calibrate the unit against reference measurements of NO_x and PM_{10} . However, monitoring was not available at both sites for all other measurements, and O_3 calibration could not be performed at either site. As reference monitors are sparse within our two focus regions, it could be difficult to consistently calibrate the air pods regularly as they would have to be relocated. To counter this, ACOEM suggests having one reference monitor calibrated pod to correct all AQMesh pods in an area via co-location. This becomes complicated when all focus pollutants are not measured at one location, and the AQMesh has to be relocated before obtaining a full pollution calibration which can lead to the introduction of error.

The aforementioned sources of error could lead to over or under-estimation of local pollution and reduce data quality, and are a major factor to consider when utilising the resulting data in studies. For instance, real trends in exposure – outcome studies (e.g. air pollution exposure vs. COPD exacerbation) could be lost due to inaccurate results, affecting reliability of conclusions. Although, gaseous pollutant

concentrations showed very good correlation even before calibration, and PM concentration correlation was fair when observed between the Irvine reference monitor and AQMesh.

Additionally, an added benefit of using the AQMesh monitor is the ability to access real-time data remotely which would allow faster identification of air pollution episodes with high resolution. This data could be made publicly available for vulnerable persons to manage personal exposure. Furthermore, the monitor is relatively low-cost, operation procedures were simple and arguably far less labour intensive and more informative than other widely used solutions such as passive diffusion tubes. Under ideal conditions (or with use of additional heated inlet) the AQMesh could provide a consistently precise and accurate method of air pollution concentration determination and hotspot identification, and could be used to better inform remediation strategies.

3.6.2 Air pollution profiles of focus regions

Air pollution monitoring was a vital aspect of this study to begin to assess if the concentrations of pollution, when compared with EU & NAQ objectives and WHO guidelines, could be a potential factor leading to increased rate of COPD exacerbations or even prevalence in the local community. Throughout the duration of the study a number of guideline and regulation air pollution limitations were breached or likely breached (although further information would be required to make a fully informed conclusion). The AQMesh was initially stationed at the Paisley site across 4 months; during this time likely breaches were observed for all regulated pollutants studied. It was observed that pollutants were recorded above annual guidelines and 24 hr limitations (Table 3.1). Only Paisley and Stranraer showed a potential breach of EU directive limitations for (NO, PM_{2.5} annual mean O₃ 8 hr mean) although Paisley (for all pollutants except NO₂), Stranraer (NO annual and O₃ 8 hr mean) Irvine (O₃ 8 hr mean) and Stevenston (PM_{2.5} annual) all breached NAQ or Scottish air quality objective limitations. Therefore, assuming these data were verified and extended by further investigation, potentially mean these limitations warrant further investigation as limitation breaches may be prevalent in all areas including Dumfries & Galloway and Ayrshire & Arran sites, and may require remediation. The AQMesh therefore would be useful in this investigation considering benefits and drawbacks alongside careful data validation as previously discussed.

Site Specific Air Pollution EU, WHO & NAQ Breaches

Table 3.1 – Outline of site air pollution breaches and specified breaches. Conclusions formed with caveat that data is indicative, but may not be representative of annual data; actual observations may vary over an annual period. NO is compared with the NO_x limitation as an indicator of a breach. EU – European Union, NAQ – National Air Quality & WHO – World Health Organisation.

Area	Pollutant	Breach (informed potential)			
		WHO 2005	WHO 2021	EU regulation	NAQ objective
Paisley	NO _x	n/a	n/a	Yes (30 µg/m ³ annual)	Yes (30 µg/m ³ annual)
	NO ₂	No	Yes (10 µg/m ³ annual)	No	No
	O ₃	Yes (100 µg/m ³ 8 hr mean)	Yes (100 µg/m ³ 8 hr mean)	Yes (120 µg/m ³ 8 hr mean)	Yes (100 µg/m ³ 8 hr mean)
	PM _{2.5}	Yes (10 µg/m ³ annual, 25 µg/m ³ 24 hr mean)	Yes (5 µg/m ³ annual, 15 µg/m ³ 24 hr mean)	Yes (25 µg/m ³ annual)	Yes (10 µg/m ³ annual)
	PM ₁₀	Yes (20 µg/m ³ annual, 50 µg/m ³ 24 hr mean)	Yes (15 µg/m ³ annual, 45 µg/m ³ 24 hr mean)	Yes (40 µg/m ³ annual)	Yes (18 µg/m ³ annual, 50 µg/m ³ 24 hr mean)
	Stranraer	NO _x	n/a	n/a	Yes (30 µg/m ³ annual)
Stranraer	NO ₂	No	Yes (10 µg/m ³ annual)	No	No
	O ₃	Yes (100 µg/m ³ 8 hr)	Yes (100 µg/m ³ 8 hr)	Yes (120 µg/m ³ 24 hr mean (assuming 3-year av.))	Yes 100 µg/m ³ 8 hr)
	PM _{2.5}	No	No	No	No
	PM ₁₀	No	No	No	No
	Irvine	NO _x	n/a	n/a	No
Irvine	NO ₂	No	Yes (10 µg/m ³ annual)	No	No
	O ₃	Yes (100 µg/m ³ 8 hr mean)	Yes (100 µg/m ³ 8 hr mean)	No	Yes (100 µg/m ³ 8 hr mean)
	PM _{2.5}	No	Yes (5 µg/m ³ annual, 15 µg/m ³ 24 hr mean)	No	No
	PM ₁₀	No	No	No	No
	Stevenston	NO _x	n/a	n/a	No
Stevenston	NO ₂	No	Yes 10 µg/m ³ annual)	No	No
	O ₃	Yes (100 µg/m ³ annual)	Yes (100 µg/m ³ annual)	No	Yes (100 µg/m ³ annual)
	PM _{2.5}	Yes (25 µg/m ³ 24 hr)	Yes (5 µg/m ³ annual, 15 µg/m ³ 24 hr)	No	Yes (10 µg/m ³ annual)
	PM ₁₀	Yes (50 µg/m ³ 24 hr)	Yes (45 µg/m ³ 24 hr)	No	No

When studying the Paisley site it is not surprising that PM₁₀ limitations have been met and surpassed as Paisley has a declared AQMA for this pollutant. However, an AQMA has not been declared for NO, O₃ or PM_{2.5} for this area (latter two pollutants not measured by the local reference station). The data are particularly interesting when studying areas such as Stranraer and Stevenston, as these locations are within COPD hotspot regions but have a lack of local monitoring. Additionally, in Irvine, where local monitoring is present within an area of high footfall, a limitation breach in O₃ was predicted from the available data. All regions showed exceedances for at least one pollutant when compared with WHO 2021 guideline limits. This is an interesting aspect to the results, as WHO guidelines are based upon predicted health outcomes following exposure (WHO, 2021). These exposure estimates are based on a number of studies including one by Lim *et al* (2019) that demonstrated hazard ratios of 1.04 for respiratory disease and 1.06 for COPD associated mortality per ~20 µg/m³ increase in O₃. Furthermore, this association becomes 1.1 for respiratory associated mortality at ~ 100 µg/m³ (Lim *et al.*, 2019). However, the effects observed with air pollution exposure have been reported at lower concentrations than those stated by WHO. For instance, a study conducted by Xu *et al* (2024) determined the effects of ozone during months with lower average temperature and therefore low ozone concentrations with an average concentration finding of 16.6 µg/m³. An increase of 10 µg/m³ resulted in an increase in biomarkers of lung injury (surfactant protein & hepatocyte growth factor) and inflammation (including IL-1β and RANTES) (Xu *et al.*, 2024). Additionally, it observed in another study that an increase of 5.7 µg/m³ PM₁₀ from 0.3 µg/m³ resulted in an increased association with fatal myocardial infarction (Rosenlund *et al.*, 2009). This reinforces the idea reported by some sources that there is no safe level of air pollution (Marks, 2022; Chandia-Poblete *et al.*, 2022). Although this is acknowledged within the WHO guidelines, the aim of these guideline limits is to identify the lowest level of exposure which the guidance development group has associated adverse health effects with moderate certainty (WHO, 2021). Therefore, in areas such as Stranraer where there are exceedances of O₃ limits, this is particularly relevant, as these levels may be higher than those which can induce inflammation, reduction in lung function and potentially exacerbation in COPD patients. This is especially important as elevated levels of air pollution would potentially not be identified in these areas due to the lack of local monitoring.

It must be noted that all air pollution studied after the initial lockdown period was initiated on March 23rd 2020 would not necessarily be representative of the typical air pollution profiles identified within the studied areas. This has given a unique insight into the pollution profile of Stranraer, as a brief profile of the area was obtained before and after lockdown. Contrary to what might be expected from this data, particulate matter during this time increased in concentration in March and April compared with the other analysed months including February (Figure 3.26 & Figure 3.28). This is unexpected, as anthropogenic emissions such as the combustion of fossil fuels attributes to a large proportion of PM emissions (Lelieveld *et al.*, 2019). This increase has been reported in other studies of air pollution during the initial lockdown period performed across all four sovereign states within the United Kingdom

indicating this increase is not related to changes in regional emissions (Acosta-Ramírez and Higham, 2022). However, NO₂ were reported to reduce during the lockdown period, and low values were observed from February to June followed by a gradual increase from mid-July onwards, also as similarly reported in another study (Acosta-Ramírez and Higham, 2022). This, along with global reports of reduced human-mobility (Nouvellet *et al.*, 2021), indicates that this increase is not due to an increase in anthropogenic activity such as vehicle emissions. Rather, studies have reported a difference in meteorological conditions when comparing February 2020 with the 6-week period following the date of the UK lockdown initiation. For instance, the period before the lockdown had higher wind speeds when compared with historic average baseline values, and high rainfall levels. Conversely, the period following the beginning of the lockdown period saw low rainfall and increased proportion of easterly direction winds due to anticyclonic weather patterns, bringing PM from mainland Europe (a trend historically typical of this annual period) (Air Quality Expert Group, 2020; Acosta-Ramírez and Higham, 2022). This further reinforces a statement on air pollution control measures broached within a number of research works, not only are local remediation strategies pivotal to local reduction but also those on a wider, global scale (Amann *et al.*, 2020; Reis, Drouet and Tavoni, 2022; Sokhi *et al.*, 2021). For this reason, guidelines such as those introduced by WHO are important; when discussing air pollution remediation and policy introduction the aim is to reduce air pollution levels as far as is possible. Informed guidelines such as this one are particularly relevant as predictions suggest that the 2005 WHO guidelines would prevent an estimated 57,975 deaths attributed to PM_{2.5} and 56,130 to NO₂ compared with 109,188 and 57,030, respectively if WHO 2021 guidelines were reached (Khomenko *et al.*, 2021).

As with the results obtained from Stranraer, another area where there was elevated levels of pollution above regulatory guidelines but minimal monitoring was Stevenston, where PM_{2.5} levels exceeded both WHO (2005 & 2021) and NAQ limitations. PM is one of the wider studied pollutants, with largely varied outcomes following exposure (WHO, 2021). However, PM exposure outcomes for COPD patients often vary from no effect on spirometry results (Jansen Karen *et al.*, 2005) to FEV₁ decrements (Trenka *et al.*, 2006), increased risk of morbidity (Zhang *et al.*, 2016) and mortality (Li *et al.*, 2016). PM alone is a more complicated pollutant to consider than gaseous pollutants because it also can lead to a combined effect during exposure of multiple pollutants, but also can itself vary in composition. This may be a factor in the differences observed upon pollutant exposure, and would could have relevance in areas such as Stranraer, where PM concentrations are within guideline and objective stated acceptable levels but may still have adverse health effects. Alongside the recommendations made here for a detailed level pollutant concentration overview, analysing the composition of particulates and investigating the axis between particulate composition and exposure-linked health prognosis (particularly in relation to those with respiratory disorders e.g. COPD) would better inform and potentially increase efficiency of remediation strategies.

This study has identified the AQMesh low-cost monitoring system as a reliable and (potentially, given implementation of interference reducing measures) realistic system which could be used to create a network of airborne pollutant monitoring systems utilised to inform remediation strategies. Also, this study has been the first to identify pollution levels within two COPD focus regions and subsequent potential breaches of air quality guidelines and objectives, with the added aspect of observing the pollution change in these areas during a global pandemic. This study suggests that air pollution within lesser-monitored COPD hotspots could potentially be a source of COPD pathogenesis and exacerbation left otherwise undetected by current monitoring strategies. Implementation of an AQMesh network could be a viable system to improve and update current monitoring systems and potentially reduce the prevalence and exacerbation rates of COPD populations in hotspot areas.

4 Chapter 4 – Effects of diesel engine particulates and PAR2 activation in an immortalised lung epithelial monolayer model

4.1 Pathobiological Investigation of Air Pollution in COPD Models

COPD development is often synonymous with tobacco smoke exposure but estimations suggest one-third of sufferers have no history of smoking (Salvi and Barnes, 2009). Therefore, recent studies have placed an emphasis on elucidating the effects of other potential causative factors such as airborne toxicants and their influence on disease pathology (Li *et al.*, 2011). However, understanding of the physiological effects of air pollution exposure on COPD is frequently complicated by the heterogeneous nature of the former and latter.

Epidemiological studies are utilised to identify the correlation which stands between exposure – effect observations but these are often influenced by confounding factors such as dependability of air monitoring solutions (as discussed in chapter 3), multiple pollutant synergism and population characteristics (Fann *et al.*, 2011). The data derived from such observations is invaluable as this serves to identify adverse effects on a large scale, however, finer subtleties such as singular pollutant action or composition is often indecipherable. Pathobiological studies may facilitate the clarification of such details.

Currently, there are no fully validated *in vivo* models for the study of COPD but there have been a number of advancements in *in vitro* techniques which also align with the three Rs principles (BéruBé *et al.*, 2010). These principles (Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement) are concerned with the reduction of animal use and distress in research (Hubrecht and Carter, 2019). In recent years this has been a growing area of interest in all areas including pulmonary research where a number of other models have been developed which act as a replacement for animal models. More advanced examples include microfluidic chips (lung on a chip) and 3D organoid cultures such as bronchospheres & air liquid interface cultures (Joo, Min and Cho, 2024). More simplistic models also exist, namely immortalised and adenocarcinomic (BEAS-2B, A549 etc.) cell monolayers which have long been utilised as representative models of bronchial and alveolar lung epithelia in characterisation and toxicological studies (Han *et al.*, 2020; Garcia-Canton *et al.*, 2013). Examples of these models are outlined in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 – Examples of *in vitro* cell line models used in the study of pulmonary epithelium.

Cell type	Source	Description	Reference
BEAS-2B	Bronchial epithelial cells (autopsy)	Epithelia derived from non-cancerous individual. Immortalised with adenovirus 12-SV40 virus hybrid.	(Reddel <i>et al.</i> , 1988b)
A549	Epithelial Lung adenocarcinoma	Immortalised, tumorigenic	(Giard <i>et al.</i> , 1973)
Calu-3	Epithelial Lung adenocarcinoma	Immortalised, tumorigenic	(Fogh, Fogh and Orfeo, 1977)
16HBE14o-	Bronchial epithelial cells (brushings)	Epithelia derived from non-cancerous individual. Immortalised via transfection with adenovirus SV40 (ori- plasmid). expresses high levels of cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (CFTR)	(Cozens <i>et al.</i> , 1994)

The BEAS-2B cell line used in this study offers several advantages over other models. Notably, its immortalised nature allows for extended experimentation and simpler culture maintenance compared with primary cell counterparts, which have finite lifespan (Stewart *et al.*, 2012). Crucially, BEAS-2B originates from normal human bronchial epithelium (Reddel *et al.*, 1988a). This distinction is significant because commonly used alternatives, such as A549 and Calu-3 are derived from cancerous tissue (Giard *et al.*, 1973; Fogh, Fogh and Orfeo, 1977). The healthy origin of BEAS-2B may make this cell line more suitable for use in investigations into the mechanisms of non-diseased lung epithelia, cancer development and pathogenesis of non-malignant lung diseases such as asthma or COPD (Reddel *et al.*, 1988a; Park *et al.*, 2015; Kim *et al.*, 2023; Kono *et al.*, 2021; Jairaman *et al.*, 2016). A difference in the inflammatory response between BEAS-2B and cancer cell line (A549) in response to air pollution has previously been confirmed as PM_{2.5} (sampled from Nanjing) was able to induce IL-6 and IL-8 release from BEAS-2B but only IL-8 release from A549. In the same study, PM_{2.5} sampled from Shanghai also induced IL-6 and IL-8 inflammation from BEAS-2B but neither was released from A549 (Huang *et al.*, 2017).

There are other comparative cell lines which are not cancerous and have been immortalised via transfection with adenovirus such as 16HBE14o- (Cozens *et al.*, 1994). Importantly, this cell has been shown to contain subpopulations which have differing expression of cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (CFTR) (Kerschner, Paranjapye and Harris, 2023). This channel has been shown to be impaired in patients with COPD (Marcus *et al.*, 2023).

Therefore, in the investigation of COPD development mechanisms, responses of 16HBE14o- potentially could be unrepresentative of those seen in normal epithelia. This heterogeneity in relation to CFTR expression has not been reported in BEAS-2B.

While the BEAS-2B cell line is frequently used in toxicological assays, including the assessment of pollutant effects (e.g. PM), there are several known limitations in the use of this cell line (Huang *et al.*, 2017; Han *et al.*, 2020; Garcia-Canton *et al.*, 2013). For instance, BEAS-2B have altered metabolism when compared with healthy primary cells, this can prevent the bioactivation of toxins into more harmful components and reduce negative effect observations (Garcia-Canton *et al.*, 2013). Moreover, this model has been shown to express properties and cell surface markers typical of mesenchymal stems cells. Research suggests that this could be attributable to misclassifications during initial characterisation of this cell line (Han *et al.*, 2020).

Nevertheless, BEAS-2B are a commonly used model due to their aforementioned capacity for indefinite culture maintenance and relative homogeneity (Garcia-Canton *et al.*, 2013). Investigations using models such as these can lead to a better understanding of the mechanisms by which air pollutants modify cellular homeostasis. Findings, alongside air pollution monitoring, could aid in the identification of particularly harmful air pollution components/combinations with relevance to conditions such as COPD and direct remediation strategies accordingly (Garcia-Canton *et al.*, 2013).

4.2 PAR2 Agonism and Antagonism

PAR2 has been implicated in the processes of many inflammatory diseases. For instance, Ferrell *et al* studied an adjuvant-induced chronic inflammation monoarthritis model in PAR2-deficient and wild-type (WT) mice⁹. Joint swelling observed in WT mice was largely inhibited in the PAR2-deficient model (Ferrell *et al.*, 2003). PAR2 has also been implicated in the formation of lesions in atopic dermatitis (Barr *et al.*, 2019).

⁹ Wild-type (WT) describes model organisms which are considered typical for the species used as a comparative control to investigate variation between model organisms e.g. PAR2 deficiency (Holmes *et al.*, 2017).

With relevance to respiratory disease, upregulation of PAR2 has been observed in patients with asthma and COPD (Knight *et al.*, 2001). Furthermore, known serine protease activators of PAR2 have been detected at elevated levels in the bronchial alveolar lavage fluid of patients with pulmonary inflammation (Heuberger and Schuepbach, 2019; Shavit-Stein *et al.*, 2017; Mihara *et al.*, 2016). To delineate the physiological action of PAR2 and downstream signalling effects, potent peptidomimetic agonists have been developed. These include C391, SLIGKVN₂, GB88 (biased signal activator of cAMP, RhoA and ERK1/2), and 2-Furoyl-LIGRLO-NH₂ (FLIGRLO). Additionally, a number of antagonists for PAR2 have been developed, including antibodies (B5, SAM11, MAB3949, MEDI0618), peptidomimetic drugs (K-14585, K-12940, C391), peptides (FSLLRY-NH₂, SLIGRL-NH₂), and novel small molecules (AZ3451 & AZ8838) (McIntosh *et al.*, 2020; Boitano *et al.*, 2015; Kennedy *et al.*, 2020; Kanke *et al.*, 2009; Cheng *et al.*, 2017). This study utilises FLIGRLO and AZ8838 in the study of lung epithelia action and characterisation. FLIGRLO was first described in a study by McGuire *et al.* in 2004 whereby the previously investigated PAR2 agonist SLIGRL-NH₂ was modified by the addition of an ornithine group on the c-terminal end, the resulting peptide showed greatly enhanced potency (McGuire *et al.*, 2004). Conversely, AZ8838 is a significantly more novel compound with the antagonist having been first detailed in 2017 by Cheng *et al.* High-throughput screening identified an imidazole series and AZ8838 was developed following further optimisation (Cheng *et al.*, 2017). Having initially been thought to bind in the allosteric site of an occluded pocket within PAR2, further studies discovered AZ8838 binds within both allosteric and orthosteric sites thereby functioning as a competitive antagonist (Cheng *et al.*, 2017; Kennedy *et al.*, 2018; McIntosh *et al.*, 2020). Further studies have unveiled the role of AZ8838 in an *in vivo* system; Kennedy *et al.* found that the antagonist considerably inhibited FLIGRLO induced inflammation in rat paw through the suppression of tissue mast cell and neutrophil activation (Kennedy *et al.*, 2020). These findings serve to provide the framework for the design and development of future PAR2 targeted therapeutics. In the meantime, synthetic receptor agonists and antagonists act as tools with which novel PAR2 activating compounds can be identified.

4.3 PAR2 in External Exposure Induced Lung Inflammation

Lung epithelia constitutes a physical barrier as part of the pulmonary first line of defence and as such is particularly susceptible to airborne microbes and pollutants. Consistent assaults may lead to sustained inflammation and damage accumulation resulting in the development of disorders such as COPD over time (LeMessurier *et al.*, 2020). PAR2 is an ideal candidate for

the study of external factor induced inflammation as it has been shown to have roles in both xenobiotic-induced exposure pathways and COPD pathophysiology. For example, PAR2 has been observed at elevated levels within lung homogenates and epithelial cells of both smokers and COPD patients (Lee *et al.*, 2018). Following further investigation in BEAS-2B cells cigarette smoke extract (CSE) was found to upregulate PAR2 mRNA and protein expression after 24 hr *via* p38 MAPK activation (Lee *et al.*, 2018). Further, emphysema in transgenic PAR2 overexpressing murine models following CSE exposure was greatly enhanced when compared with WT (De Cunto *et al.*, 2011). Another relevant exposure to consider are the airborne particulates that comprise air pollution, which can often share a composition commonality with cigarette smoke (Invernizzi *et al.*, 2004). As has been observed in CSE exposure, recent studies have implicated PAR2 in the inflammatory cascade triggered by diesel engine particulate exposure, however, further study is required to understand this process (Brinchmann *et al.*, 2018b; Li *et al.*, 2011).

4.4 Hypothesis and aims

The central hypothesis of this chapter is that diesel engine particulates have an action on lung epithelial cell behaviour, which may be mediated via PAR2.

The aim of this chapter was to study a common ubiquitous pollutant (DEP) in the context of an inflammatory modulator (PAR2), known to be implicated in the pathogenesis of respiratory conditions including COPD, within a relevant model of lung epithelia.

The main research areas addressed within this chapter are as follows:

- Does BEAS-2B monolayer present a viable model to study biological effects of PM exposure?
- Does PAR2 activation in BEAS-2B induce (pro-inflammatory) cellular processes?
- Do DEP induce inflammation in lung epithelia?
- Could PAR2 play a role in DEP induced pro-inflammatory cytokine release?

4.5 Methodology

The full methodology utilised here is illustrated in Section 2.2. All studies in this chapter use BEAS-2B immortalised bronchial epithelial cell line. Expression of the PAR2 receptor was investigated by immunofluorescence of the receptor. Cytotoxic effects were determined using the metabolism assay MTT as a proxy for cell viability analysis following 24 hr FLIGRLO & DEP exposure. The activation of PAR2 by FLIGRLO and DEP was investigated using immunofluorescence to identify PAR2 re-distribution after 4 hr stimulation. Separately, Fluo-

4 calcium assay alone and in the presence of PAR2 antagonist was utilised in the determination of PAR2 mediated Ca^{2+} mobilisation. This assay was also used to investigate the potential of DEP aqueous and organic extract to increase intracellular calcium. This was again performed alone and in the presence of AZ8838 to elucidate the role of PAR2 in this mechanism. Capacity for aqueous DEP to induce reactive oxygen species release was identified in ROS and lipid peroxidation assays. Finally, ELISA was performed to quantify levels of relevant pro-inflammatory cytokines following stimulant exposure alone and following 30 min AZ8838 pre-incubation.

4.6 Results

4.6.1 BEAS-2B characterisation: PAR2 expression and distribution

Figure 4.1 – Morphology of BEAS-2B immortalised human lung epithelial cell line. BEAS-2B cells were seeded and grown to approx. 80 % confluence, in a 96-well clear bottom cell culture plate. Subsequently, representative images of a single cell passage were captured using an EVOS XL core bright field microscope. Cells illustrated at A) 10 x magnification, scale bar: 25 μm & B) 20 x magnification, scale bar: 50 μm .

Figure 4.2 – Identification of PAR2 in BEAS-2B cell line (immunofluorescence staining). Cells were seeded on to sterile coverslips and allowed to adhere for 24 hr then washed with PBS, fixed, permeabilised and incubated with PAR2 primary antibody (Alomone) and AlexaFluor 488 conjugated secondary rabbit antibody (green). Nuclei were stained with Hoechst stain (blue). Images were obtained with an Olympus LX71 microscope and Image J used to merge channels. Appropriate antibody was used as an isotype control (bottom row). Images representative of $n=3$, scale bar = 50 μM (20 x magnification).

Figure 4.3 – Cell viability following 24 hr exposure of BEAS-2B to DEP, FLIGRLO & AZ8838. Cell viability was determined using MTT assay. Cells were seeded 24 hr prior to stimulation with experimental reagents, following stimulation spent medium was aspirated and MTT reagent solution was added to wells. Following 4 hr incubation reagent was aspirated and formed formazan crystals were dissolved in DMSO before quantification via absorbance readings obtained with Biotek, ELX 800 microplate reader (570 nm) and GEN5 1.08 software. Viability was calculated as a percentage of the experimental control. Results displayed as mean \pm SEM (Paired t -test, $n=3$, measured in triplicate).

Figure 4.4 – Redistribution of PAR2 following 4 hr exposure with FLIGRLO and DEP. PAR2 immunofluorescence of FLIGRLO and DEP treated BEAS-2B. Cells were seeded on to sterile coverslips and allowed to adhere for 24 hr before incubation medium with PBS (CTRL), DEP or FLIGRLO for 4 hr. Cells were then washed with PBS, fixed, permeabilised and incubated with PAR2 primary antibody (Alomone) and AlexaFluor 488 conjugated secondary rabbit antibody (green). Nuclei were stained with Hoechst stain (blue). Images were obtained with an Olympus IX71 microscope and Image J used to merge channels. Appropriate antibody was used as an isotype control (bottom row). Images representative of $n=3$, scale bar = 10 μM (100 x magnification).

Before investigating the effects of DEP exposure and any involvement of PAR2 in DEP effects, BEAS-2B monolayer cell cultures were characterised in terms of reagent tolerance, as well as PAR2 expression and subcellular distribution under basal and stimulated conditions.

Initially, BEAS-2B utilised within this chapter were examined for suitability as a model within this investigation. The BEAS-2B cell line was first established in 1988 when normal human bronchial epithelial cells derived from primary tissues from a non-cancerous patient were transfected with an adenovirus 12-SV40 hybrid virus (Reddel *et al.*, 1988a). Since development, BEAS-2B have been used widely in lieu of primary cell lung epithelia in studies with a focus of viral infection (Thuy, Bao and Moon, 2022), bacterial infection (Ishibashi and Nishikawa, 2003) and toxicological mechanistic response to cigarette smoke (Xu *et al.*, 2019), e-cigarette vapour (Dusautoir *et al.*, 2021), and biogenic (Lin *et al.*, 2016) & anthropogenic (Dergham *et al.*, 2015) ambient compounds / particulates. However, the reliability of these results has been called into question due to variations observed between these transfected cells and their primary counterparts both in phenotype and stimuli response (Han *et al.*, 2020; Ekstrand-Hammarström *et al.*, 2012). Initially morphology was assessed using phase contrast microscopy (Figure 4.1). As was demonstrated within another study, BEAS-2B showed an elongated morphology similar to that observed of mesenchymal cells rather than the rounded structure of HBEC (Han *et al.*, 2020). Nevertheless, BEAS-2B are a typical model used to derive initial findings within studies of lung epithelia.

As PAR2 is investigated here in the axis of DEP induced pro-inflammatory effects, the presence of the receptor was confirmed via immunofluorescence. Localisation of the receptor appeared in a diffuse pattern with concentrated punctate areas (Figure 4.2) with perinuclear localisation evident at higher magnification (CTRL, Figure 4.3). The isotype control showed no evidence of non-specific secondary antibody binding.

As an early indicator of whether PAR2 activation might be induced by DEP, localisation of the receptor was assessed following exposure (4 hr) to 6.25 µg/ml and 12.5 µg/ml whole DEP equivalent concentrations, as well as the PAR2 specific agonist 2-furoyl-LIGRLO-N2 (FLIGRLO) (10 µM) (n=3) (Figure 4.4).

Assessment of cytotoxic effects of any of the reagents used within these experiments was performed by MTT assay (Figure 4.3). MTT is a colorimetric assay which directly acts to measure cellular metabolic activity and is commonly utilised in many published studies as a conduit for cytotoxicity assessment and proliferation (Yoshida *et al.*, 2019; Zerboni *et al.*,

2022). Results here indicated no significant metabolic, proliferative or cytotoxic effect of any of the compounds used following an acute stimulation after 24 hr period.

Exposure to the lower DEP concentration appeared to have little effect on redistribution observations when compared with the unstimulated control. However, exposure to the higher concentration was more comparable to the FLIGRLO stimulated cells with less evidence of ubiquitous diffuse staining and stronger staining observed within select punctate areas (Figure 4.4). The appropriate isotype control was void of all observable fluorophore signal.

4.6.2 Calcium influx in BEAS-2B following stimulation with FLIGRLO in the presence and absence of AZ8838

Figure 4.5 – Calcium mobilisation in BEAS-2B following exposure with FLIGRLO and Trypsin. Cells were incubated in black plates and allowed to adhere for 24 hr prior to analysis. Medium was aspirated and cells incubated with FLUO-4 NW dye (30 min) before stimulation with trypsin and varying concentrations of FLIGRLO. Fluorescence (excitation/ emission, 490/ 520 nm) was measured with a Varioskan LUX multimode microplate reader (and SkanIT 6.0 software) every 1 s. B) Traces are representative of 1 s resolved real-time measurements. Values in panels A&C obtained from maximum fluorescence values (after reagent addition) minus average of baseline values (initial readings to 9 s – prior stimulation). Results displayed as mean \pm SEM One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparison's test. ($n=4$ measured in triplicate; * $p<0.05$; ** $p<0.01$; *** $p<0.001$).

Figure 4.6 – Calcium mobilisation in BEAS-2B following exposure with FLIGRLO in the presence and absence of AZ8838. Cells were incubated in black plates and allowed to adhere for 24 hr prior to analysis. Medium was aspirated and cells incubated with FLUO-4 NW dye (30 min) before addition of PAR2 agonist (FLIGRLO) concentration range. Fluorescence (excitation/ emission, 490/ 520 nm) was measured with a Varioskan LUX multimode microplate reader (and SkanIT 6.0 software) every 1 s. Results of FLIGRLO induced Ca^{2+} mobilisation and inhibition with AZ8838 (pre-incubation, 30 min) at A&B) higher and C&D) lower antagonist concentrations. B&D) Representative raw data trace of each agonist / antagonist combination, traces are representative of 1 s resolved real-time measurements. Results displayed as mean \pm SEM maximum Fluo-4 (fluorescence dye) RFU (post-stimulation) normalised against baseline RFU (pre-stimulation). ($n=3$ measured in triplicate; one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test. *cf. vehicle CTRL; #cf. FLIGRLO. # $p<0.05$; ## $p<0.01$; ###/*** $p<0.001$).

Figure 4.7 – Calcium mobilisation in BEAS-2B following acute exposure with AZ8838. Cells were incubated in black plates and allowed to adhere for 24 hr prior to analysis. Medium was aspirated and cells incubated with FLUO-4 NW dye (30 min) before stimulation with FLIGRLO and varying concentrations of AZ8838. Fluorescence (excitation/ emission, 490/ 520 nm) was measured with a Varioskan LUX multimode microplate reader (and SkanIT 6.0 software) every 1 s. Values obtained from maximum fluorescence values (after reagent addition) minus average of baseline values (initial readings to 9 s – prior stimulation). Results displayed as mean \pm SEM maximum Fluo-4 (fluorescence dye) RFU (post-stimulation) normalised against baseline RFU (pre-stimulation). ($n=3$; one-way ANOVA with Dunnett’s multiple comparisons test. *** $p<0.001$ cf. CTRL).

A common method used to assess activation of PAR2 in epithelial cells is to assess downstream indicators such as cytoplasmic calcium mobilisation. Here BEAS-2B were exposed with increasing concentrations of FLIGRLO (1 – 100 μ M) and calcium influx was assessed via fluorescence based assay as described in Chapter 2 (Figure 4.5). Trypsin, the non-specific physiologic activator of PAR2, was used as a positive control.

Stimulus response traces show a rapid increase of Ca^{2+} , reaching a peak ~ 40 s followed by a gradual decrease throughout the remaining sampling period (Figure 4.5A). A concentration-response effect was observed following treatment and significance was observed with 10 & 100 μ M concentrations of the agonist, as well as with Trypsin (Figure 4.5B).

The efficiency of a novel PAR2 antagonist, AZ8838, to inhibit this calcium signal was then tested in BEAS-2B with the most effective FLIGRLO concentration. Cells were pre-incubated with the antagonist prior to stimulation with 100 μ M FLIGRLO initially at concentrations of 3 nM to 30 μ M, which completely eradicated any Ca^{2+} mobilisation signal (Figure 4.6). As no concentration-response relationship was observed from this data this experimental format was repeated with a lower concentration range (3 pM – 3 nM). At the lower range a concentration dependent negative relationship was observed between increasing AZ8838 concentrations and

FLIGRLO induced calcium mobilisation, with significant effect observed at even the lowest concentration studied ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 4.6C).

As AZ8838 concentration pre-incubation indicated calcium levels below that of the vehicle treated control, a control experiment was performed to assess any initial agonistic effect that AZ8838 may have on the lung epithelial cells prior to stimulation. For this the same procedure was performed again but with the AZ8838 investigated as the stimulant, FLIGRLO was used as a positive control. Although a slight increase was observed from the baseline following DMSO (AZ8838 vehicle) and concentrations 3 – 300 nM AZ8838, no significant change in Ca^{2+} flux was observed following acute treatment with the antagonist.

These data provided validation of this fluorescence-based method to determine PAR2 activation and inhibition in BEAS-2B cells. (Figure 4.7)

4.6.3 Effect of aqueous and organic extract of DEP on calcium mobilisation in BEAS-2B

Figure 4.8 – Calcium mobilisation following exposure of BEAS-2B with aqueous and organic (hexane) extract of DEPs (12.5 μg/ml equivalent) alone and following pre-incubation (30 min) with AZ8838. Cells were incubated in black plates and allowed to adhere for 24 hr prior to analysis. Medium was aspirated and cells incubated with FLUO-4 NW dye (15 min) before addition of antagonist and DMSO CTRL pre-incubation. Fluorescence (excitation/ emission, 490/ 520 nm) was measured with a Varioskan LUX multimode microplate reader (and SkanIT 6.0 software) every 1 s. Results of DEP induced Ca²⁺ mobilisation and inhibition with AZ8838 (pre-incubation, 30 min). C) Representative raw data trace of each DEP / antagonist combination shown in B, traces are representative of 1 s resolved real-time measurements. Results displayed as mean ± SEM maximum Flou-4 (fluorescence dye) RFU (post-stimulation) normalised against baseline RFU (pre-stimulation). A) n=5; B) n=3 (one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test). C) Representative trace of organic DEP extract exposure in the presence and absence of AZ8838. *p<0.05 cf. CTRL; #cf. DEP (organic). #p<0.05; ##p<0.01; ###p<0.001).

Figure 4.9 – Aqueous DEP extract stimulation (24 hr) of ROS in BEAS-2B. Cells were seeded and allowed to adhere for 24 hr then exposed before spent supernatant was removed and cells incubated with CM-H2DCFDA dye. Results displayed as mean \pm SEM RFU. Data shown in A) presence and B) absence of Tert (tert-butyl hydroperoxide) (200 μ M; 2 hr) stimulation positive control ($n=3$). Statistics performed on both datasets separately using paired t -test (A) and One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparison's test (B). (* $cf.$ CTRL. * $p<0.05$; ** $p<0.01$).

Figure 4.10 – Lipid peroxidation in BEAS-2B following treatment with aqueous DEP extract. Cells were seeded and allowed to adhere for 24 hr then exposed before spent supernatant was removed and cells incubated with BODIPY 581/591 C11 dye. As the lipophilic dye is oxidised fluorescence of the dye shifts from red (581/610 nm) to green (484/510 nm), the green : red ratio calculated then correlated with the lipid peroxidation levels observed following treatment with DEP (24 hr) (right) or H₂O₂ (1 hr) (left). Results displayed as mean \pm SEM. ($n=3$, results performed in duplicate. One-way ANOVA with Bonferroni's correction * $p<0.05$).

Calcium mobilisation is a downstream indicator of PAR2 activation and an upstream mechanism of pro-inflammatory cytokine production, therefore, the role of DEP in the induction of calcium mobilisation was assessed.

To identify the active component of DEP in cytoplasmic calcium influx induction, aqueous (PBS) and organic (hexane) extracts of DEP were assessed; extraction process of both components obtained as described in chapter 2. This method also permitted the investigation of DEP action whilst negating interference produced by whole DEP in the (no wash) Fluo-4 fluorescence assay. Organic DEP induced a significant increase in influx when compared with the hexane equivalent control (1.5 fold increase)(Figure 4.8B); no such change was observed following aqueous DEP treatment. To assess a potential role for PAR2 in this process stimulations were performed in the presence and absence of AZ8838 (pre-incubation 30 min) (3 nM - 30 μ M). Antagonist pre-treatment abolished organic DEP induced calcium influx signal to baseline levels even at concentrations as low as 3 nM ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 4.8B).

Although aqueous DEP did not play a role in the early signalling event and pro-inflammatory indicator of calcium mobilisation assessed here, this does not necessarily mean this DEP component has no effect on the lung epithelial cells. Rather, previous research suggests a role for aqueous DEP in cellular ROS mechanisms (Verma *et al.*, 2014). Therefore, the potential for ROS induction by aqueous DEP was assessed in the BEAS-2B monolayer model using a fluorescence-based ROS quantification assay as previously described in chapter 2. Tert-butyl hydroperoxide (200 μ M; 2 hr) was used as a positive control ($p < 0.001$) Figure 4.9A. A slight but significant concentration-dependent increase in ROS was observed following 24 hr treatment with 6.25 and 12.5 μ g/ml equivalent concentrations of aqueous DEP (Figure 4.9B). Results are displayed alone and in the presence of the positive control, as significance in aqueous DEP generated ROS increase was lost when the positive control was included in post-hoc pairwise comparison statistical analysis. To further investigate potential effects cells with aqueous DEP extract lipid peroxidation was measured following 24 hr exposure as an indicator of intracellular ROS (Figure 4.10). A significant increase from the unstimulated control in both the positive control (H_2O_2) and 12.5 μ g/ml DEP extract concentration stimulation.

4.6.4 Pro-inflammatory cytokine release from BEAS-2B following stimulation by DEP: effect of PAR2 antagonism

Figure 4.11 – Pro-inflammatory cytokine release in BEAS-2B following stimulation with DEP and FLIGRLO. Cells were seeded and allowed to adhere for 24 hr before supernatant was replaced. Following a subsequent 24 hr incubation, spent medium was aspirated and stored until analysis by ELISA for IL-6 & IL-8 concentration. ELISA colorimetric assay was quantified via absorbance readings obtained with Biotek, ELX 800 microplate reader (450 nm) and GEN5 1.08 software. A) IL-6 & IL-8 release following 24 hr incubation with FLIGRLO (10 & 100 μM). Cytokine levels were quantified from supernatant following exposure via ELISA. B) IL-6 & IL-8 release following 24 hr incubation with DEP (6.25 & 12.5 μg/ml). Results displayed as mean ± SEM. (n=3; One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test *cf. CTRL. *p<0.05).

Figure 4.12 – AZ8838 inhibition of DEP induced pro-inflammatory cytokine production in BEAS-2B. Cells were seeded and allowed to adhere for 24 hr before supernatant was replaced. Following a subsequent 24 hr incubation, spent medium was aspirated and stored until analysis by ELISA for IL-6 & IL-8 concentration. ELISA colorimetric assay was quantified via absorbance readings obtained with Biotek, ELX 800 microplate reader (450 nm) and GEN5 1.08 software. MTT reagent solution was added to wells. Release of A) IL-6 and B) IL-8 was assessed following 24 hr incubation with DEP (12.5 µg/ml) in the presence and absence of AZ8838 (30 min pre-incubation). Effect of DMSO vehicle (0.003 %) on C) IL-6 and D) IL-8 was assessed from following 24 hr incubation. Results displayed as mean \pm SEM. (IL-6 data $n=6$) (IL-8 data $n=3$; One way ANOVA with Bonferroni's multiple comparison's test C & D) Paired t -test. *cf. CTRL * $p<0.05$; #cf. 12.5 µg/ml ## $p<0.01$).

Pro-inflammatory cytokine release is a central hallmark of PAR2 activation and the method by which it has been observed to drive pathogenesis in many conditions (McCulloch *et al.*, 2018; Schmidlin *et al.*, 2002). To assess the potential for FLIGRLO and DEP to induce a pro-inflammatory response, BEAS-2B were incubated with the respective agonists (FLIGRLO 10 & 100 µM; DEP 6.25 and 12.5 µg/ml) before supernatant media was collected and assessed via ELISA for IL-6 and IL-8 release. No effect on cytokine release was observed following FLIGRLO exposure, although a concentration-dependent non-significant trend toward increase in IL-8 release might be inferred ($p = 0.1$) (Figure 4.11). Conversely, DEP induced concentration-dependent release of IL-8 but this was only significant for 12.5 µg/ml treatment (21.27 ± 4.108) (Figure 4.11).

To determine involvement of PAR2 in any DEP induced pro-inflammatory cascade, IL-6 and IL-8 release was quantified via ELISA following 24 hr DEP stimulation (12.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) in the presence or absence of varying concentrations of AZ8838 (30 min pre-incubation; 0.3 – 30 μM). Reduction of both IL-6 and IL-8 release was seen in the presence of 30 μM AZ8838, although this was only significant for IL-8 and this was arguably not to baseline levels (Figure 4.12 A,B). Any effect owed to the DMSO vehicle was assessed with an exposure control, 24 hr vehicle stimulation showing no significant increase in either IL-6 or IL-8 (Figure 4.12 C,D).

4.7 Discussion

Herein this chapter addressed the potential axis between diesel engine particulate exposure and pro-inflammatory effects on immortalised lung epithelia, specifically investigating a potential role for PAR2. This has previously been investigated in few studies and further investigation is required to understand the action of pollutants such as DEP on lung epithelia (Li *et al.*, 2011; Bach *et al.*, 2015).

This research was initially addressed in a BEAS-2B model following initial characterisation by assessing morphology of the cell line. Compared with the rounded shape of HBEC, BEAS-2B displayed an elongated, fibroblastic morphology. This has previously been demonstrated in another study by Han *et al.* alongside other non-epithelial indicating factors including gene expression profile and characteristics shared with human umbilical cord-derived mesenchymal stem cells (fibroblast-like cells) (Han *et al.*, 2020). The same study also observed differences in protein expression and potential to stimulate monocytes toward M2 macrophage polarisation, although this was thought to be attributed to SV-40 interference (Han *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, any measured cell response could deviate from that observed in primary epithelia and physiologically relevant lung models and should be considered as such. Nevertheless, BEAS-2B is one of the most-accessible and studied models in pulmonary research, and studies have confirmed many commonalities between primary and cell line responses (Le Vée *et al.*, 2019; Leclercq *et al.*, 2018).

Before assessing functional capacity of the receptor, PAR2 presence was confirmed in BEAS-2B with IF. The presence of PAR2 on BEAS-2B has also previously been reported via immunohistochemistry and real-time PCR (Asokanathan *et al.*, 2002). The diffuse and punctate patterns observed from the IF are consistent with the process of PAR2 internalisation and trafficking (Adams *et al.*, 2011). This was further reinforced by evidence of this post-PAR2 activation process, seen herein in FLIGRLO and DEP treated cells via IF. This result is corroborated by previous findings in a study by Déry *et al.* whereby Kirsten murine sarcoma virus-transformed rat kidney epithelial cells were stimulated with trypsin. IF findings from this prior study showed internalisation of PAR2 and trafficking of the receptor at 4 hr (same time point investigated here) following enzyme activation (Déry *et al.*, 1999). As resting unstimulated cells appeared to show some level of the PAR2 activation process this may be attributable to many factors including epifluorescent method of image capture (thereby limiting location visualisation) which only allows a planar view of the cellular layout. Higher resolution and clearer determination of localisation could be obtained with image capture from confocal

microscopy (Thorn, 2016). A further consideration is that PAR2 could have undergone activation prior to fixation and IF processing, perhaps by proteases which are present in the foetal bovine serum utilised in the supplementation of growth medium (10 % v/v), as batch variation is common and reagent composition is not fully clarified (Subbiahanadar Chelladurai *et al.*, 2021). In further studies this hypothesis could be investigated by first implementing cell starvation (serum-free medium growth period) prior to IF processing.

To further investigate the suitability of BEAS-2B in the study of PAR2 and inflammatory mechanisms, functional status of the receptor was assessed via calcium assay. Calcium mobilisation is a signature of canonical PAR2 signalling, and has been used in various studies as a downstream indicator of activation (Sevigny *et al.*, 2011; Kennedy *et al.*, 2020; Liu *et al.*, 2013). Here, the PAR2 specific activator FLIGRLO was used alongside trypsin, a physiological PAR activator, to stimulate BEAS-2B before calcium release was assessed (McGuire *et al.*, 2004; Adams *et al.*, 2011). Significance was observed following treatments with trypsin, and FLIGRLO, and the latter demonstrated a concentration – dependent calcium increase. With reference to the trace values, at the highest concentrations an initial increase was followed by a slow gradual decline towards the end of the sampling period. A longer measurement period could have demonstrated calcium measurements returning to baseline levels as has been demonstrated previously in human umbilical vein endothelial cells stimulated with trypsin (Selmi *et al.*, 2012). This would have allowed for the identification of response duration and any change between the metrics of DEP mediated activation compared with that of FLIGRLO. For instance, from the traces provided here, the organic extract of DEP stimulated response resulted in a smaller maximum response, however, the signal was sustained at the same level until the end of the sampling period. A previous study by Brinchmann *et al* showed that the calcium response triggered by the hexane extract of diesel engine particulates demonstrated a biphasic pattern of initial increase followed by a second sharper increase sustained at an upward trajectory for a considerable period of ~20 min (Brinchmann *et al.*, 2018a). This second increase was seen to be caused by intracellular influx suggesting that the DEP extract was triggering the store operated calcium entry mechanism. This process maintains cellular homeostasis by replacing depleted calcium stores by triggering intracellular Ca^{2+} influx (Hogan and Rao, 2015). This increase is unlikely to be seen in this study due to the short time frame of the analysis period.

Calcium mobilisation was confirmed here and linked with the reagents of interest, however, Ca^{2+} signalling is a pivotal process involved in other signalling events such as PLC enzyme

activation from a number of other receptors including a range of GPCRs (Bill and Vines, 2020). To ensure that the calcium signalling witnessed here is via the PAR2 receptor, the specific antagonist AZ8838 was utilised to confirm FLIGRLO and DEP agonism.

As the antagonist appeared to reduce the calcium levels to below that observed from the control an assessment on the potential for AZ8838 agonistic effects was investigated. If the antagonist had shown any potential to activate PAR2 this may have caused internalisation of the receptor shortly before stimulation. The subsequent reduction of the membrane available concentration of the receptor could then have been reduced inadvertently, indicating antagonism of PAR2. This inability to induce PAR2 stimulation following an initial activation has been demonstrated previously in human nasal ALI culture (Carey *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, as the calcium signal has been shown to be delayed following PAR2 activation, depending on the agonist in question, any activation potential of AZ8838 could alter the starting baseline of these experiments. Ideally this experiment would be repeated to determine any effects in calcium mobilisation effect over the pre-incubation and stimulation period (~32 min). This would mitigate any interference from delayed AZ8838 activation potential. However, as the AZ8838 effectively inhibited any signal and no significant increase from the baseline levels of calcium was seen in AZ8838 stimulated cells this is likely to be negated. Further, lack of AZ8838 PAR2 agonistic potential indicated by calcium signalling has previously been reported in PAR2 transfected Chinese hamster ovary cells (CHO) (Kennedy *et al.*, 2020).

As the diesel engine particulates utilised here are comprised of solid particulates suspended in vehicle, they characteristically blocked fluorescence signal when direct well measurements were obtained following addition in initial experiments (data not shown). Therefore, DEP extracts were instead assessed for calcium mobilisation potential. This also allowed for the identification of the PAR2 activating component of DEP (polar – aqueous or non-polar – organic / hexane).

Aqueous extract appeared to have no effect on calcium mobilisation, however, a significant effect was observed when BEAS-2B were treated with the organic extract when compared with the vehicle control. Further, cell pre-treatment with AZ8838 also significantly inhibited the organic DEP mediated calcium influx to levels comparable to baseline measurements. These results are corroborated by previous findings reported by Li *et al* whereby organic extract of DEP (obtained directly from diesel engine) stimulated calcium increase in BEAS-2B. This

increase was attenuated by PAR2 siRNA and inhibitors of downstream PAR2 signalling molecules (PLC & PI3-K) (Li *et al.*, 2011).

Although aqueous DEP extract did not exhibit any effect in the Ca^{2+} assay, this component was further assessed for other parameters of cellular response, particularly associated with stress and toxicity. As aqueous extracts of DEP have shown potential to play a role in ROS formation thereby activating another pathway, inducing pro-inflammatory cytokine release (Ball *et al.*, 2000; Bach *et al.*, 2015) (potentially through dissolved transition metals), ability of aqueous DEP extract was assessed for ROS-inducing effects in BEAS-2B (Figure 4.9). Slight but significant concentration-dependent increases in ROS were found following DEP aqueous extract stimulation.

DEP aqueous content of soluble transition metals have been one of the components driving ROS inducing properties, as metal components can contribute to Fenton reactions within the cell (Valko, Morris and Cronin, 2005). For this reason lipid peroxidation has previously been used as an assessment for metal exposure ROS outcome in cells treated with cigarette smoke (Yoshida *et al.*, 2019); therefore this parameter was investigated here. Significant increase was seen in both ROS and lipid peroxidation following stimulation with the highest equivalent concentration of aqueous DEP extract.

In line with this another study has previously demonstrated that both organic and aqueous extracts, and concomitant ROS release and PAR2 activation, are important in the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines in BEAS-2B (Bach *et al.*, 2015). However, this aforementioned study showed that the organic component is the main contributor of ROS; a suggestion for further study would be to investigate the effect of the hexane component on this parameter.

To determine downstream effects of FLIGRLO and DEP in BEAS-2B, cytokine release was measured from conditioned supernatant media. No effect of FLIGRLO on the release was observed barring a trend in IL-8 release following exposure to the highest concentration utilised here. This is surprising as a previous study has shown that the PAR2 activating peptide SLIGKV can induce a significant increase in the release of both IL-6 and IL-8 following 24 hr stimulation (Asokanathan *et al.*, 2002). TNF α release was also assessed from these cells but no production of the cytokine was observed (data not shown). To further investigate the induction of cytokines in BEAS-2B a positive control such as lipopolysaccharide (similar to PAR2 activates MAPK/NF κ B pathways) or a more physiologically relevant PAR activator

such as matriptase or trypsin could have been used as a positive control (Nakayama *et al.*, 2013). Conversely, DEP stimulation showed a significant concentration-dependent response in production of IL-8. Increases in cytokines were slight in both cytokine sets (IL-6 & IL8; ~2-fold and 5-fold increase respectively), however, pre-treatment with AZ8838 reduced the production of pro-inflammatory cytokine – although arguably not down to basal levels. This was only significant in IL-8 levels. The difference seen here in the inflammation inducing potential between DEP and FLIGRLO could be attributed to particulates working via more than one mechanism such as aforementioned ROS induction prior to cytokine release. DEP induction of IL-6 and IL-8 has been previously confirmed in BEAS-2B, however, PAR2 inhibition was seen to reduce only IL-6 but not IL-8 (Bach *et al.*, 2015). Interestingly, this study also showed that both cytokines were induced by the non-polar extract of DEP whereas IL-6, which was also stimulated by the polar extract of DEP, was the only cytokine to be reduced following PAR2 silencing. This pro-inflammatory action was unaltered following aryl hydrocarbon silencing or antagonism (Bach *et al.*, 2015). Another study by the same group found that the hexane extract of sampled DEP induced a significant increase in IL-8 in human microvascular endothelial cells (Brinchmann *et al.*, 2018b). This study also showed that inhibition of PAR2 and AhR, separately, significantly decreased IL-8 expression when compared with cells stimulated with different organic fractions of DEP (Brinchmann *et al.*, 2018b). Furthermore, studies have shown that the differing compositions of particulates can have altered effects on the release of pro-inflammatory mediators depending on source (Zerboni *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, the composition of DEP and similarly the cell type can change the effects observed. These variables change the outcomes of findings so the identification of individual pollutant component action on physiologically relevant experimental layouts would better inform the expected outcomes from real-world mimicked exposures. Including the additional facet of disease-appropriate models would also allow for the understanding of pollutant action on vulnerable groups.

4.8 Conclusion

Overall, results herein indicate that BEAS-2B are a suitable model to study pro-inflammatory biological effects of the putative DEP and PAR2 axis, although results should be considered with the caveat that there may be differences between observations in this model and primary cells. Therefore, it was decided that findings should be further validated in primary epithelia (Chapter 5). BEAS-2B expressed PAR2 and the receptor appeared functional in this cell line, as indicated by IF and calcium influx response following PAR2 specific agonist treatment.

Finally, DEP appeared to show PAR2 activation capabilities, as indicated by stimulation induced receptor trafficking (IF), downstream Ca^{2+} mobilisation and pro-inflammatory cytokine release (ELISA). PAR2-dependence of these effects was shown in some experiments by inhibition of the receptor a novel antagonist (AZ8838), which ameliorated these effects.

5 Chapter 5 – Diesel engine particulate effects in primary Human Bronchial Epithelial Cells (normal and COPD) at monolayer and Air-Liquid Interface

5.1 Introduction

5.1.1 Primary cell models in toxicological research

As previously described, there are a number of benefits which accompany the utilisation of immortalised or transformed cell lines in the study of biological processes and as such they can make an excellent basis for screening processes. However, these are not always ideal candidates for characterisation and mechanism focussed studies for a multitude of reasons. For instance, Garcia-Canton *et al* found that BEAS-2B and A549 displayed limited cytochrome P450 (CYP) activity when compared with previous published results obtained from HBEC studies. This was demonstrated through restricted gene expression of CYP enzymes and reduced ability to metabolise CYP substrates when compared with previously validated hepatic control cell lines (Garcia-Canton *et al.*, 2013). This is particularly relevant in toxicology studies, as CYP capabilities dictate the bioactivation of compounds e.g. B[a]P which typically would be transformed into a diol-epoxide carcinogenic compound when metabolised (Nebert *et al.*, 2013). Furthermore, cigarette smoke contains a number of known AhR receptor agonists which can induce the activation of CYPs and therefore, is likely to display toxicologically relevant action via this mechanism. Another consideration of model use is that there have been many identified dissimilarities in phenotype, receptor expression, and stimuli response of immortalised and transformed cell lines when compared with counterpart primary cells (Han *et al.*, 2020; Asokanathan *et al.*, 2002). Comparatively, primary cells (cells isolated directly from human tissue) can be considerably more challenging to maintain, more expensive to maintain, show greater variability, and their use is limited by passaging restrictions due to limited proliferative capacity and phenotypic drift.

Primary cells are, however, a vital tool in the research of pathological processes relevant to disease pathogenesis. Where healthy and disease classification cells have been compared, findings have shown COPD human bronchial epithelial cells to suppress superoxide dismutase-1 (SOD-1) activity in response to diesel emission exposure; the opposite was observed in non-COPD cells (Vaughan *et al.*, 2019b). Cells from COPD patients were also shown to have increased expression of major histocompatibility complex class II (MHC II) and demonstrated greater metabolic response (CYP1A1 mRNA increase) in response to the insult (Vaughan *et al.*, 2019b). Differences such as these cannot be fully modelled in immortalised cells due to the lack of multifactorial environmental variation prior to culture. Disparity between primary cells can be seen as a factor which can confound findings, however, it is also an advantage over cell lines as findings may be more informative. COPD and ‘healthy’ non-disease donor cell

response to stimuli and therapy can be discerned, whilst results may be more representative of general population groups (Mori *et al.*, 2022; Mertens *et al.*, 2017; Krimmer and Oliver, 2011).

5.1.2 Air-liquid Interface Culture

Cells differentiated at the air-liquid interface (ALI) form a model which has been considered as the gold standard in the study of *in vitro* airway biological studies (Saint-Criq *et al.*, 2020). ALI cultures are formed in a process by which cells are seeded into transmembrane inserts and grown to confluence before the apical surface medium is removed and growth medium supplemented with compounds such as hydrocortisone and retinoic acid, which act to drive differentiation (Bluhmki *et al.*, 2020) (also see Chapter 2). Following a 4-week period, the culture monolayer develops into a fully differentiated pseudostratified epithelial layer more representative of the airway *in vivo*, with goblet cells, tight junctions and ciliated cells. In studies of the effects of toxicants and their action within these models, insults can be applied through more realistic methods than in submerged cultures, for example, via dose-controlled nebulisation application systems which more accurately mimic the *in vivo* exposure process (Aufderheide and Mohr, 2000). This model has been utilised in a number of research works due to the correlation between ALI exposure outcomes and those from *in vivo* analyses. For instance, one study by Smyth *et al* demonstrated reduced epithelial barrier integrity following exposure with SRM 2975 diesel particulate matter in parallel ALI and *in vivo* murine models. *In vitro*, this was demonstrated by decreased TEER measurements and increased FITC-Dextran permeability, whilst in neonatal BALB/c mice, reduced Tricellulin (tight junction protein) mRNA and protein was observed (Smyth *et al.*, 2020). On the other hand, inconsistencies in *in vitro* observations between immortalised cell line and ALI culture have been found following insult exposure (Rossner *et al.*, 2021). The use of differentiated models also allows for the analysis of changes in features which are not present in monolayer, such as mucus secretion and cilia-beat frequency (Kanai *et al.*, 2015; Tratnjek *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, as research develops, organoid models such as the one discussed here are being utilised more frequently as they present a more reliable system to represent the outcomes expected within human tissue (Kim, Koo and Knoblich, 2020).

5.2 Hypothesis and aims

The central hypothesis of this chapter is that diesel engine particulate exposure can induce pro-inflammatory cytokine production in primary epithelia of “normal” and COPD-disease state patients, which may be mediated by PAR2.

The aim of this chapter was to study the effects of DEP on lung epithelia derived from non-COPD donors and COPD patients. This was to be investigated in both monolayer and differentiated culture models.

The main research areas addressed within this chapter are as follows:

- Does DEP show potential to activate PAR2 in primary lung epithelia?
- Does PAR2 activation in HBEC induce (pro-inflammatory) cellular processes?
- Do DEP induce inflammation in lung epithelia?
- Could PAR2 play a role in DEP induced pro-inflammatory cytokine release?

5.3 Methodology

The methods used here are documented in full in Section 2.2. All experiments performed within this chapter utilised normal (HBEC) and COPD patient derived human bronchial epithelial cells (COPD-HBEC). Both HBEC classifications were characterised, the presence of PAR2 expression was identified with immunofluorescence and baseline production of cytokines IL-6 and IL-8 quantified using ELISA. Cytotoxic effects of FLIGRLO and DEP stimulants were assessed with MTT metabolism assay as a proxy for cell viability. The functional capacity of PAR2 in cells was assayed with Fluo-4 NW calcium mobilisation assay in the presence of both stimulants alone and post AZ8838 pre-incubation to confirm a role for PAR2 in observations. Additionally, p38/SAPK and p44/42/ERK pathway activation was assessed following agonist and particulate exposures by determining phosphorylation via western blot (WB) up to a period of 60 min. WB was again used in the assessment of maximal phosphorylation reduction following AZ8838 pre-incubation. Final monoculture experiments were performed with ELISA of spent medium following 24 hr FLIGRLO and DEP exposure. Air-liquid interface (ALI) cultures were developed from HBEC and COPD-HBEC. Cells were seeded on to apical compartments of transwell inserts in 24-well plates and grown to confluence then apical medium was removed, differentiation specific medium added to the basolateral side only and cultures maintained for 21 days. After this time full differentiation of the ALI culture was assessed with immunofluorescence. ELISA was utilised in the study of pro-inflammatory modulating effects of FLIGRLO, DEP and AZ8838 on these 3D pseudostratified epithelial models.

5.4 Results

5.4.1 Assessment of PAR2 in HBEC and COPD-HBEC

Figure 5.1 – Expression of PAR2 in HBEC and COPD-HBEC (immunofluorescence staining). Cells were seeded on to sterile coverslips and allowed to adhere for 24 hr then washed with PBS, fixed, permeabilised and incubated with PAR2 primary antibody (Alomone) and Alexa Fluor 488 conjugated secondary antibody (green). Nuclei were stained with Hoechst stain (blue). Images were obtained with Olympus IX71 microscope and ImageJ used to merge image channels. Appropriate antibody was used as an isotype control on HBEC cells (bottom row). Images representative of n=3, scale bar = 50 μ M (20 x magnification).

Figure 5.2 –Basal IL-6 & IL-8 cytokine secretion levels in HBEC and COPD-HBEC. Cells were seeded and allowed to adhere for 24 hr before supernatant was replaced. Following a subsequent 24 hr incubation, spent medium was aspirated and stored until analysis by ELISA for IL-6 & IL-8 concentration. ELISA colorimetric assay was quantified via absorbance readings obtained with Biotek, ELX 800 microplate reader (450 nm) and GEN5 1.08 software. Results displayed as mean \pm SEM. ($n=3$ measured in triplicate; unpaired t-test $*p<0.01$ cf. HBEC).

Figure 5.3 - Cell viability following 24 hr exposure of HBEC and COPD-HBEC to DEP, FLIGRLO & AZ8838. Cells were seeded 24 hr prior to stimulation with experimental reagents, following stimulation spent medium was aspirated and MTT reagent solution was added to wells. Following 4 hr incubation reagent was aspirated and formed formazan crystals were dissolved in DMSO before quantification via absorbance readings obtained with Biotek, ELX 800 microplate reader (570 nm) and GEN5 1.08 software. Viability was calculated as a percentage of the experimental control. Results displayed as mean \pm SEM One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparison's test ($n=4$ measured in duplicate).

Figure 5.4 - Calcium mobilisation in HBEC and COPD-HBEC following exposure with FLIGRLO and Trypsin. Cells were incubated in black plates and allowed to adhere for 24 hr prior to analysis. Medium was aspirated and cells incubated with FLUO-4 NW dye (30 min) before stimulation with trypsin and varying concentrations of FLIGRLO. Fluorescence (excitation/ emission, 490/520 nm) was measured with a Varioskan LUX multimode microplate reader (and SkanIT 6.0 software) every 1 s. B) Traces are representative of 1 s resolved real-time measurements. Values in panels A&C obtained from maximum fluorescence values (after reagent addition) minus average of baseline values (initial readings to 9 s). Results displayed as mean \pm SEM One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparison's test. (p value & *cf. vehicle CTRL; n=4 measured in triplicate; * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$).

Figure 5.5 – Calcium mobilisation in HBEC and COPD-HBEC following exposure with FLIGRLO in the presence and absence of AZ8838. Cells were incubated in black plates and allowed to adhere for 24 hr prior to analysis. Medium was aspirated and cells incubated with FLUO-4 NW dye (15 min) before addition of either DMSO (CTRL) or AZ8838 at varying concentrations and incubated for a further 30 min. All cells barring the control (HBSS) were stimulated with FLIGRLO. Fluorescence (excitation/ emission, 490/ 520 nm) was measured with a Varioskan LUX multimode microplate reader (and SkanIT 6.0 software) every 1 s. B) Traces are representative of 1 s resolved real-time measurements. Values obtained from maximum fluorescence values (after reagent addition) minus average of baseline values (initial readings to 9 s). (n=3 measured in triplicate; One way ANOVA with Bonferroni's multiple comparison's test. * $p < 0.05$ cf. CTRL; # $p < 0.05$ cf. FLIGRLO 100 μ M).

Primary normal (HBEC) and COPD diseased (COPD-HBEC) human bronchial epithelial cells were initially characterised prior to determining effects of DEPs on lung epithelia and assessing PAR2 involvement. Firstly, morphology was observed to be more rounded and less elongated when compared with the BEAS-2B, indicating the correct epithelial morphological structure and absence of stress (Appendix I, Figure 0.1). Next the presence of PAR2 and distribution was confirmed with IF. PAR2 distribution was observed to be diffuse throughout, with punctate

patterns of localisation (Figure 5.1). The appropriate isotype control indicated no presence of secondary antibody binding.

As COPD is characteristically a condition defined by chronic inflammatory processes, basal levels of IL-6 and IL-8 secretion were assessed in HBEC and COPD-HBEC incubated 24 hr conditioned growth medium and quantified via ELISA (Figure 5.2). No significant difference was observed in levels of IL-6; however, IL-8 was significantly increased in COPD cells when compared with “healthy” comparator cells.

MTT analysis of HBEC and COPD-HBEC following exposure (24 hr) to highest concentrations of experimental treatments (FLIGRLO, AZ8838 and DEP) indicated no effect on cell viability (Figure 5.3). To determine the functional status of PAR2 within HBEC, Ca^{2+} mobilisation was assessed following stimulation with FLIGRLO (1 – 100 μ M). Trypsin was used as a positive control ($p < 0.01$, Figure 5.4 A). Results displayed no change from the unstimulated control, however, a trend was observed following stimulation with the highest concentration of FLIGRLO (Figure 5.4 C).

To further inform these findings and determine the capability of AZ8838 to inhibit PAR2 activation induced Ca^{2+} mobilisation, cells were stimulated with FLIGRLO (100 μ M) alone and following 30 min pre-incubation of the antagonist. From the results of this experiment, it can be seen that FLIGRLO treatment of HBEC initiated a trend toward increase ($p = 0.0648$) which was significantly ameliorated in the presence of AZ8838 (3 μ M) (Figure 5.5). A similar pattern was observed in COPD-HBEC, although variations from the control were not statistically significant.

5.4.2 FLIGRLO regulation of MAPK (p38/SAPK and p44/42/ERK) in human bronchial epithelial cells

Figure 5.6 – MAPK phosphorylation in HBEC following FLIGRLO stimulation. Cells were stimulated with FLIGRLO (100 μ M) then collected following stimulation over a series of time points and protein (cell homogenates) transferred to nylon membrane via western blot protocol. Membranes were probed with phosphorylated and total protein (p44/42 & p38) targeted antibody then HRP-bound secondary antibody. Following appropriate wash steps membranes were incubated with ECL substrate and chemiluminescence signal was imaged with G:BOX Chemi XX6 gel documentation system (Syngene) and GeneSys automatic control software. Quantification was performed on obtained images with ImageJ and phosphorylation values normalised against total protein values of the same well. (Images and quantification representative of $n=2$).

Figure 5.7 – MAPK phosphorylation in HBEC following FLIGRLO stimulation alone and in the presence of AZ8838. Cells were stimulated with FLIGRLO (20 min; 100 μ M) alone, AZ8838 alone (30 min; 300 nM) and FLIGRLO + AZ8838 (agonist added following antagonist pre-incubation, total incubation time 50 min). Protein (cell homogenate) was collected following stimulation before being transferred to nylon membrane via western blot protocol. Membranes were probed with phosphorylated and total protein (p44/42 & p38) then HRP-bound secondary antibody. Following appropriate wash steps membranes were incubated with ECL substrate and chemiluminescence signal was imaged with G:BOX Chemi XX6 gel documentation system (Syngene) and GeneSys automatic control software. Quantification was performed on obtained images with ImageJ and phosphorylation values normalised against total protein values of the same well. (Images and quantification representative of n=2).

Figure 5.8 –IL-6 & IL-8 release from HBEC and COPD-HBEC following stimulation with FLIGRLO. Cells were seeded and allowed to adhere for 24 hr before supernatant was replaced. Following a subsequent 24 hr incubation the agonist was added for a 24 hr exposure period, conditioned medium was aspirated and stored until analysis by ELISA for IL-6 & IL-8 concentration. ELISA colorimetric assay was quantified via absorbance readings obtained with Biotek, ELX 800 microplate reader (450 nm) and GEN5 1.08 software. Results displayed as mean \pm SEM. One way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test ($n=3$; measured in triplicate).

To further elucidate the sequelae of PAR2 activation and gain a better understanding of the downstream cascade following FLIGRLO stimulation in HBEC and COPD-HBEC, MAPK pathway activation was determined. This was performed by assessing p44/42 (ERK) and p38 (SAPK) phosphorylation via western blot (WB) analysis (Figure 5.6).

For this HBEC were stimulated with 100 μ M FLIGRLO (100 μ M) over a time-course spanning 5 - 60 min. At each time point following exposure, cell homogenates were collected in line with the western blot protocol (Chapter 2). Observed phosphorylation was normalised against

the total kinase protein. Both p38 and p44 phosphorylation appeared to increase with levels reaching a maximal point at 20 – 30 min after addition of the agonist. Significance testing could not be performed on WB quantification data due to the low sample number assessed.

Following this, efficiency of AZ8838 in blocking MAPK pathway activation was assessed again via WB. As optimal phosphorylation was observed at the 20 minute time point following FLIGRLO stimulation, HBEC were again stimulated for this period in the absence and presence of the antagonist (pre-incubation: 300 nM, 30 min). An apparent reduction in agonist-induced phosphorylation both p38 and p44/42 was observed in the antagonist pre-treated cells (Figure 5.7). Significance testing could not be performed on WB quantification data due to the low sample number assessed. AZ8838 alone was also assessed for agonistic activity following the 30 min pre-incubation period, and no apparent effect on phosphorylation was observed.

As MAPK signal transduction regulates expression and production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, downstream cytokine response was assessed following FLIGRLO stimulation (24 hr). IL-6 and IL-8 release was determined via ELISA from conditioned medium. However, no significant deviation from the control was observed (Figure 5.8).

5.4.3 DEP mediated activation of PAR2

To investigate the potential of DEP to activate PAR2 downstream signalling the organic (hexane) extract equivalent of 12.5 µg/ml of whole DEP was used to treat HBEC and COPD-HBEC, before Ca²⁺ mobilisation was assessed (Figure 5.9). This was performed alone and in the presence of AZ8838 at varying concentrations (3 nM – 30 µM). A similar trend in HBEC and COPD-HBEC was observed when compared with the same experiment performed in BEAS-2B. An apparent increase in intracellular Ca²⁺ following the addition of organic DEP was inhibited in AZ8838 pre-treated cells. However, no statistically significant difference was observed in any of the conditions analysed.

As downstream calcium signalling was not statistically established, and for further comparison with the PAR2 activating peptide, the effects of whole DEP were determined in HBEC via WB. As DEP does not act the same way as many other stimulants due to the nature of the compound matrix (physical particulates suspended in PBS and diluted in appropriate cell medium), many studies quantify exposure based on particle deposition (e.g. µg/cm²). Therefore, the concentration used here was equivalent to 12.5 µg/ml whole particulates (as used in a 96-well plate) in a 6-well plate format (7.8 µg/cm²). HBEC were treated with whole DEP over a time range from 10 – 60 min, the resulting phosphorylation is illustrated in Figure 5.10. A shorter time-frame was utilised in the p44 analysis when compared with that of p38 due to limited cell availability. A gradual increase was seen in p-p42/44, however, the phosphorylation of p38 showed a sharp increase at the last time point analysed. Both protein groups were maximally phosphorylated (from this data set) at 60 min (Figure 5.10). This observation was used to inform investigation into the role of PAR2 in this activation process. Cells were treated with whole DEP alone for 60 min and following pre-incubation with AZ8838 (300 nM) for 30 min, before phosphorylation was assessed and normalised to total protein levels (Figure 5.11). The concentration of AZ8838 used here was based upon the observations of Ca²⁺ mobilisation reduction in organic DEP treated primary cells, although not significant. A reduction was observed in both p44 and p38 in the agonist pre-treated cells when compared with DEP stimulation alone. AZ8838 appeared to show slight agonistic activity following p38 phosphorylation when compared with the unstimulated control in p38 blots but this was not observed in p44 analysis. Statistical analysis on this data was not performed due to the low number of sample replicates assessed.

To assess downstream effects of DEP mediated MAPK signalling the production of cytokines was assessed from HBEC and COPD-HBEC exposed to 6.25 and 12.5 µg/ml DEP (Figure

5.12). However, as with FLIGRLO in these cells, cytokine levels did not significantly deviate from the unstimulated control.

Figure 5.9 – Calcium mobilisation in HBEC and COPD-HBEC following exposure with hexane extract of DEP in the presence and absence of AZ8838. Cells were incubated in black plates and allowed to adhere for 24 hr prior to analysis. Medium was aspirated and cells incubated with FLUO-4 NW dye (15 min) before addition of either DMSO (CTRL) or AZ8838 at varying concentrations and incubated for a further 30 min. All cells barring the control (HBSS) were then stimulated with hexane extract of DEP (12.5 μg/ml equivalent). Fluorescence (excitation/ emission, 490/ 520 nm) was measured with a Varioskan LUX multimode microplate reader (and SkanIT 6.0 software) every 1 s. B) Traces are representative of 1 s resolved real-time measurements. Values obtained from maximum fluorescence values (after reagent addition) minus average of baseline values (initial readings to 9 s). One-way ANOVW with Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test ($n=3$ measured in triplicate).

DEP 12.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

Figure 5.10 – MAPK phosphorylation in HBEC following DEP stimulation. Cells were seeded and allowed to adhere for 24 hr prior to exposure. Cells stimulated with DEP ($7.8 \mu\text{g/cm}^2$; $12.5 \mu\text{g/ml}$ equivalent adapted for 6 well plate format) were homogenised and collected following stimulation over a series of time points before protein was transferred to nylon membrane via western blot protocol. Membranes were probed with phosphorylated and total protein (p44/42 & p38) targeted antibody then HRP-bound secondary antibody. Following appropriate wash steps membranes were incubated with ECL substrate and chemiluminescence signal was visualised with G:BOX Chemi XX6 gel documentation system (Syngene) and GeneSys automatic control software. Quantification was performed on obtained images with ImageJ and phosphorylation values normalised against total protein values of the same well. (Images and quantification representative of $n=2$).

DEP 12.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ + AZ8838 300 nM

Figure 5.11 – MAPK phosphorylation in HBEC following DEP stimulation alone and in the presence of AZ8838. Cells were stimulated with DEP (60 min; 7.8 $\mu\text{g/cm}^2$; 12.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ equivalent adapted for 6 well plate format) alone, AZ8838 alone (30 min; 300 nM) and FLIGRLO + AZ8838 (agonist added following antagonist pre-incubation, total incubation time 90 min). Protein (cell homogenate) was collected following stimulation over a series of time points before being transferred to nylon membrane via western blot protocol. Membranes were probed with phosphorylated and total protein (p44/42 & p38) then HRP-bound secondary antibody. Following appropriate wash steps membranes were incubated with ECL substrate and chemiluminescence signal was imaged with G:BOX Chemi XX6 gel documentation system (Syngene) and GeneSys automatic control software. Quantification was performed on obtained images with ImageJ and phosphorylation values normalised against total protein values of the same well. (Images and quantification representative of $n=2$).

Figure 5.12 – HBEC and COPD-HBEC IL-6 & IL-8 release following stimulation with DEP. Cells were seeded and allowed to adhere for 24 hr before supernatant was replaced. Following a subsequent 24 hr incubation the DEP was added for a 24 hr exposure period, conditioned medium was aspirated and stored until analysis by ELISA for IL-6 & IL-8 concentration. ELISA colorimetric assay was quantified via absorbance readings obtained with Biotek, ELX 800 microplate reader (450 nm) and GEN5 1.08 software. Results displayed as mean \pm SEM. One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparison's test. ($n=3$; measured in triplicate).

5.4.4 Characterisation of Air Liquid Interface Culture

Figure 5.13 – Air liquid interface culture development. HBEC were grown until confluence on transwell inserts then medium was removed from the apical surface of the cells whilst the basal medium was replaced with differentiation medium. Phase contrast images of the ALI process on day 1 (seeding) (A) at airlift (B), and 1 week post-airlift (C) were captured with an EVOS XL core bright field microscope (Scale: 50 μ M, 20 x magnification).

Figure 5.14 – Markers of differentiation in HBEC differentiated at the air-liquid interface. HBEC cells were seeded onto transwell inserts and grown to confluence before the apical layer was aspirated and the basal layer medium was changed from expansion to differentiation medium and cultures were maintained for 21 days. Following this both apical and basal compartments were incubated with target protein primary antibody and appropriate secondary antibody bound with Alexa Fluor 488 (yellow) or Alexa Fluor 647 (magenta). Nuclei were stained with Hoechst (blue). Images of fixed air liquid interface culture samples were captured with a Zeiss LSM 880 upright microscope Zeiss Zen blue analysis software. Appropriate antibody control for murine and rabbit isotype shown in appendix I, Figure 0.2 & Figure 0.3.

Figure 5.15 – PAR2 expression in HBEC differentiated at the air-liquid interface. HBEC cells were seeded onto transwell inserts and grown to confluence before the apical layer was aspirated and the basal layer medium was changed from expansion to differentiation medium and cultures were maintained for 21 days. Following this both apical and basal compartments were incubated with PAR2 primary antibody and appropriate secondary antibody bound with Alexa Fluor 488 (yellow). Images of fixed air liquid interface culture samples were captured with a Zeiss LSM 880 upright microscope Zeiss Zen blue analysis software. Appropriate antibody control for rabbit isotype shown in appendix I Figure 0.3.

To further investigate the effects of inflammation in a more physiologically relevant model of lung epithelia, HBEC and COPD-HBEC were differentiated at the air-liquid interface (ALI)¹⁰. This process results in a fully pseudostratified epithelial layer more representative of that observed within the airway and is considered the gold standard model in the study of *in vitro* airway biology studies (Saint-Criq *et al.*, 2020). Cells were seeded and grown until the cobblestone morphology of confluent HBEC was observed, before the medium was aspirated from both apical and basal compartments and replaced with differentiation medium on the basal side, after which the cells began to differentiate. Apical mucus was observable 1 week post-airlift (Figure 5.13).

To characterise the ALI culture, immunofluorescence and confocal microscopy¹¹ was performed on cells following full air liquid interface differentiation process (Figure 5.14) for the identification of differentiation markers: MUC5AC (mucins), β -tubulin (cilia), forkhead box J (FOXJ, cilia), zonula occludens (ZO-1, tight junctions). Nuclei were stained blue with Hoechst stain while the green and red staining represent the secondary antibody bound to the antibody of interest. Appropriate isotype antibody controls showed no evidence of secondary antibody non-specific binding. Findings here suggest the process of ALI differentiation of primary HBEC was successful.

The presence and localisation of PAR2 in the differentiated cultures was also identified (Figure 5.15) Furthermore, localisation may differ between these cultures as the PAR2 visualised within the submerged counterpart appears diffuse throughout the cytoplasm whereas, in the ALI differentiated

¹⁰ Air –liquid interface culture experiments performed in conjunction with colleagues Mariarca Bailo and Kirsty McCallum.

¹¹ Confocal microscopy performed on air-liquid interface cultures performed in conjunction with Mariarca Bailo and Kirsty McCallum. Performed at the Glasgow Imaging Facility at the University of Glasgow with help from Mrs Susan Baillie and Dr Leandro Lemgruber Soares.

epithelia, PAR2 appeared to have areas of more and less evident PAR2 concentration throughout the epithelial layer.

5.4.5 Inflammatory Response in Air-Liquid Interface Culture

Figure 5.16 – Baseline IL-8 release from HBEC and COPD-HBEC differentiated at ALI. Cells were seeded onto transwell inserts and grown to confluence before the apical layer was aspirated and the basal layer medium was changed from expansion to differentiation medium and cultures were maintained for 21 days. Spent medium was replaced with fresh medium and cells were incubated for 4, 24 and 48 hr before apical and basal medium was collected and IL-6 & IL-8 levels were determined via ELISA. Error bars are \pm SEM, individual points are the results from each patient subset (HBEC n=5; COPD-HBEC n=4). Unpaired t-test.

Figure 5.17 - No significant change observed in IL-6 & IL-8 cytokine production in HBEC ALI cultures treated with apical (Ap) and basal (Bas) FLIGRLO 10 μ M. Cells were seeded onto transwell inserts and grown to confluence before the apical layer was aspirated and the basal layer medium was changed from expansion to differentiation medium and cultures were maintained for 21 days. Spent medium was replaced with fresh medium and cells were incubated for 4 and 24 hr with apical or basal FLIGRLO before apical and basal medium was collected and IL-6 & IL-8 levels were determined via ELISA. Error bars are \pm SEM, individual points are the results from each patient subset (n=5). One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's correction.

Figure 5.18 – No significant change observed in IL-8 cytokine production in COPD - HBEC ALI cultures treated with apical (Ap) and basal (Bas) FLIGRLO 10 μ M. Cells were seeded onto transwell inserts and grown to confluence before the apical layer was aspirated and the basal layer medium was changed from expansion to differentiation medium and cultures were maintained for 21 days. Spent medium was replaced with fresh medium and cells were incubated for 4 and 24 hr apical or basal FLIGRLO before apical and basal medium was collected and IL-6 & IL-8 levels were determined via ELISA. Error bars are \pm SEM, individual points are the results from each patient subset (n=4). One way ANOVA with Dunnett's correction.

Figure 5.19 – No significant change observed in IL-6 cytokine production in HBEC ALI cultures treated with apical and basal AZ8838 30 μM. Cells were seeded onto transwell inserts and grown to confluence before the apical layer was aspirated and the basal layer medium was changed from expansion to differentiation medium and cultures were maintained for 21 days. Spent medium was replaced with fresh medium and cells were incubated for 4 and 24 hr with AZ8838 before apical and basal medium was collected and IL-6 levels were determined via ELISA. Error bars are ± SEM, individual points are the results from each patient subset (n=5). Paired t-test.

Figure 5.20 – No significant change observed in IL-8 cytokine production in HBEC ALI cultures treated with apical and basal AZ8838 30 μM. Cells were seeded onto transwell inserts and grown to confluence before the apical layer was aspirated and the basal layer medium was changed from expansion to differentiation medium and cultures were maintained for 21 days. Spent medium was replaced with fresh medium and cells were incubated for 4 and 24 hr with AZ8838 before apical and basal medium was collected and IL-8 levels were determined via ELISA. Error bars are \pm SEM, individual points are the results from each patient subset ($n=5$). Paired t-test.

Figure 5.21 – No significant change observed in IL-6 cytokine production in COPD - HBEC ALI cultures treated with apical and basal AZ8838 30 μ M. Cells were seeded onto transwell inserts and grown to confluence before the apical layer was aspirated and the basal layer medium was changed from expansion to differentiation medium and cultures were maintained for 21 days. Spent medium was replaced with fresh medium and cells were incubated for 4 and 24 hr with AZ8838 before apical and basal medium was collected and IL-6 levels were determined via ELISA. Error bars are \pm SEM, individual points are the results from each patient subset (n=4). Paired t-test.

Figure 5.22 – Significant change observed in IL-8 cytokine production in COPD - HBEC ALI cultures treated with apical and basal AZ8838 30 μM. Cells were seeded onto transwell inserts and grown to confluence before the apical layer was aspirated and the basal layer medium was changed from expansion to differentiation medium and cultures were maintained for 21 days. Spent medium was replaced with fresh medium and cells were incubated for 4 and 24 hr with AZ8838 before apical and basal medium was collected and IL-8 levels were determined via ELISA. Error bars are ± SEM, individual points are the results from each patient subset (n=4). Paired t-test *cf. CTRL, *p<0.05.

The basal levels of pro-inflammatory cytokine release were assessed from apical and basal medium incubated with air-liquid interface differentiated HBEC and COPD-HBEC. Both IL-6 and IL-8 (Figure 5.16) were measured via ELISA. No significant change from the baseline concentrations can be found in any of the datasets. It is possible that a trend may emerge within this data with a higher quantity of samples in the dataset, however, that cannot be concluded here. What can be said is that patient sample results show large disparity even between basal cytokine release concentrations.

For ALI stimulations reagents of interest were applied to both apical and basal compartments unless otherwise stated. Additionally, DMSO was added to all stimulations at the same concentration as that of the control.

To investigate the potential to induce inflammation (specifically via PAR2) in this culture the apical and basal surfaces of the ALI culture were stimulated with 10 μ M FLIGRLO for 4 and 24 hr separately. Following this levels of IL-6 and IL-8 were assessed by ELISA (HBEC: Figure 5.17; COPD- HBEC: Figure 5.18). Neither stimulation of the apical or basal (alone) stimulations increased the influx of pro-inflammatory cytokine release at 10 μ M FLIGRLO concentration. Another stimulation was performed with treatments of FLIGRLO (10 μ M) on both the apical and basolateral sides of the ALI simultaneously, and again no response was seen in release of IL-8 or IL-6 (data not shown).

As it was not possible to discern increased pro-inflammatory cytokine release, cells were incubated alone and in the presence of the AZ8838 antagonist to investigate the potential for PAR2 mediated constitutive pro-inflammatory cytokine release. Contrary to the hypothesis that AZ8838 might reduce the baseline cytokine expression in COPD- and /or normal HBEC, data here suggests either effect on IL-6 release (Figure 5.19 & Figure 5.21) or COPD-HBEC IL-8 release. However, an unexpected significant increase was seen following AZ8838 24 hr stimulation in apical IL-8 release from HBEC indicating a partial agonistic effect (Figure 5.22). Analysis of the effect of the DMSO vehicle at the same concentration as used in the AZ8838 incubations showed no effect on cytokine secretion (data not shown).

5.4.6 DEP Stimulation on pro-inflammatory cytokine release and PAR2 activation

Figure 5.23 – No significant change observed in IL-6 cytokine production in HBEC ALI cultures treated with apical DEP. Cells were seeded onto transwell inserts and grown to confluence before the apical layer was aspirated and the basal layer medium was changed from expansion to differentiation medium and cultures were maintained for 21 days. Spent medium was replaced with fresh medium and cells were incubated for 4 and 24 hr With apical DEP before apical and basal medium was collected and IL-6 levels were determined via ELISA. Error bars are \pm SEM, individual points are the results from each patient subset (n=5). One-way ANOVA with Dunnett’s correction.

Figure 5.24 – No significant change observed in IL-8 cytokine production in HBEC ALI cultures treated with apical DEP. Cells were seeded onto transwell inserts and grown to confluence before the apical layer was aspirated and the basal layer medium was changed from expansion to differentiation medium and cultures were maintained for 21 days. Spent medium was replaced with fresh medium and cells were incubated for 4 and 24 hr With apical DEP before apical and basal medium was collected and IL-8 levels were determined via ELISA. Error bars are \pm SEM, individual points are the results from each patient subset (n=5). One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's correction.

Figure 5.25 - No significant change observed in IL-6 cytokine production in COPD - HBEC ALI cultures treated with apical DEP. Cells were seeded onto transwell inserts and grown to confluence before the apical layer was aspirated and the basal layer medium was changed from expansion to differentiation medium and cultures were maintained for 21 days. Spent medium was replaced with fresh medium and cells were incubated for 4 and 24 hr With apical DEP before apical and basal medium was collected and IL-6 levels were determined via ELISA. Error bars are \pm SEM, individual points are the results from each patient subset (n=4). One way ANOVA with Dunnett's correction.

Figure 5.26 –Significant change observed in IL-8 cytokine production in COPD - HBEC ALI cultures treated with apical DEP. Cells were seeded onto transwell inserts and grown to confluence before the apical layer was aspirated and the basal layer medium was changed from expansion to differentiation medium and cultures were maintained for 21 days. Spent medium was replaced with fresh medium and cells were incubated for 4 and 24 hr With apical DEP before apical and basal medium was collected and IL-8 levels were determined via ELISA. Error bars are \pm SEM, individual points are the results from each patient subset (n=4). One-way ANOVA with Dunnett's correction, *cf. CTRL, * $p < 0.05$.

Figure 5.27 – Significant increase in IL-8 production from COPD – HBEC treated with DEP ameliorated in following pre-incubation with AZ8838. Cells were seeded onto transwell inserts and grown to confluence before the apical layer was aspirated and the basal layer medium was changed from expansion to differentiation medium and cultures were maintained for 21 days. Spent medium was replaced with fresh medium and cells were incubated for 4 and 24 hr with apical DEP in presence or absence of AZ8838 before apical and basal medium was collected and IL-8 levels were determined via ELISA. Error bars are \pm SEM, individual points are the results from each patient subset ($n=4$). One way ANOVA with Bonferroni's correction, * $p < 0.05$ cf. CTRL; # $p < 0.05$ cf. 12.5 µg/ml DEP

Much of the previous data herein has illustrated the potential for DEP to activate PAR2, although pro-inflammatory cytokine release was only observed in a DEP treated cell line within this study. However, as the monolayer does not provide an accurate representation of the airways the potential action of DEP is investigated here in the more physiologically relevant ALI model.

DEP suspensions were applied to the apical surface of the air-liquid interface culture of HBEC and COPD-HBEC for a period of 4 or 24 hr. After the incubation period spent medium was aspirated and stored before ELISA analysis for IL-6 and IL-8 quantification. From this analysis there appeared to be no pro-inflammatory effect of DEP on the release of the cytokines of interest in HBEC at either time point (Figure 5.23 & Figure 5.24).

Next, the action of apical DEP stimulation on COPD-HBEC was investigated via the same experimental setup. As was observed in HBEC, IL-6 release was not affected by incubation with the particulates (Figure 5.25). Interestingly, a concentration-dependent increase was seen in IL-8 concentrations from basal side medium in COPD-HBEC (Figure 5.26), perhaps indicating a disease feature imparting pre-disposition to DEP exposure sensitivity.

To determine if this pro-inflammatory effect involved PAR2 as was seen in BEAS-2B cells, ALI cultures were stimulated with DEP alone and in the presence of AZ8838. All exposure assessments showed a general pattern of increase with DEP and decrease with AZ8838, however, this was only significant in basal side IL-8 levels, indicating that DEP induced pro-inflammatory cytokine production acts at least in part via PAR2 (Figure 5.27).

5.5 Discussion

This chapter addresses the effects of DEP on primary lung epithelia, cultured both at monolayer and differentiated at the air-liquid interface with particular focus on the role of PAR2.

Initially, the presence of PAR2 on the cell surface was confirmed by IF on normal and COPD patient human bronchial epithelial cells. Patterns of distribution showed diffuse distribution throughout the cell although exact location cannot not be determined without the use of more informative techniques such as confocal microscopy.

As COPD is a condition characterised by chronic inflammation, basal levels of IL-6 and IL-8 were assessed. No significant difference was observed between IL-6 levels between the cell groups; however, IL-8 concentrations were significantly elevated in COPD-HBEC media. Previous studies have shown that IL-6 and IL-8 responses have both been significantly elevated in serum levels of COPD patients when compared with healthy controls (de Moraes *et al.*, 2014). Further, IL-8 has been observed at higher levels in COPD sputum when compared with non-smoking control patients, and IL-6 sputum levels of COPD patients have been seen at significantly higher concentrations than those from comparator asthma patients (Keatings *et al.*, 1996; Grubek-Jaworska *et al.*, 2012). Conversely, another study has shown IL-8 production to be elevated in COPD-HBEC but the opposite result was seen in IL-6 HBEC (Leclercq *et al.*, 2016). However, levels of these cytokines have been shown to fluctuate in response to modulatory factors such as COPD severity and patient exacerbation status (Donaldson *et al.*, 2005; Singh *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, more evident trends may have been established here had patients been classified into groupings and patient sample numbers increased, these factors are a limitation of this study.

Prior to cell stimulation experiments MTT was used to demonstrate that reagents used in all experiments showed no effect on cellular proliferation, metabolism or cytotoxicity on epithelia. Calcium influx was utilised to gain a measure of PAR2 activation capacity in HBEC as was performed in BEAS-2B. The calcium signal was not significantly increased from the control, however, a trend was observed in COPD-HBEC with the highest concentration of FLIGRLO ($p=0.0919$). Further, calcium mobilisation following FLIGRLO stimulation was significantly ameliorated post incubation with AZ8838 (3 μM) thereby indicating successful PAR2 antagonism in the HBEC monolayer model. This may indicate that a lack of significant change seen here is attributable to low patient sample numbers and increasing this could potentially decrease standard error and provide more reliable findings. Additionally, a longer time frame could be assessed to determine a delayed effect on Ca^{2+} mobilisation.

To further characterise PAR2-dependent signalling, phosphorylation of MAPK pathway components p 42/44 and p38 was seen in both target protein sets towards 20-30 min, this phosphorylation rapidly decreased in p 42/44 but remained sustained to the 60 min time point in p 38. Studies have previously shown that MAPK activation can be seen following FLIGRLO stimulation after 5 min in 16HBE14o- cells, an immortalised human bronchial epithelial cell line (Flynn *et al.*, 2011). Antagonism with AZ8838 pre-incubation (300 nM; 30 min) also ameliorated this signal as was seen in the calcium response.

Finally, the pro-inflammatory cytokine release following FLIGRLO stimulation in primary cells was assessed via ELISA, a typically expected outcome commonly observed following ERK and SAPK pathway activation (Chow *et al.*, 2010; Pan *et al.*, 2008). Although there was a slight increase in IL-8 in HBEC, none of the treatments in either cell type resulted in significant inflammatory response. This could again be due to a number of factors including low sample number and patient heterogeneity. Further, the differences observed between primary cells and previous findings in BEAS-2B could also be attributed to PAR2 expression levels or accessibility of the receptor on the cell surface. Another reason for the lack of response here and low response seen in the immortalised cell line could be due to interferences in the typical cytokine secretion induction process. For instance, the experimental set up here may be limiting store-operated calcium entry (SOCE) via Ca^{2+} release-activated Ca^{2+} (CRAC) channels. This is a process previously observed to be involved in PAR2 mediated cytokine release in a previous study by Jairaman *et al* whereby production of IL-6 and IL-8 was ameliorated following CRAC inhibition in airway epithelial cells. This was determined from cells cultured in medium supplemented with calcium. Further, calcium-free media was seen to reduce the pro-inflammatory response (Jairaman *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, calcium supplementation could be a strategy utilised in future experiments built on research investigated herein to elucidate any modulating effect this may play in pro-inflammatory cytokine secretion.

The next stage of this research focussed on the potential of DEP to activate PAR2 signalling cascade in primary monolayer. Calcium mobilisation following HBEC treatment with hexane extract of DEP did appear to increase the level of Ca^{2+} in both cell types (Figure 5.9). However, the increase following stimulation was smaller than that induced by FLIGRLO (~0.5 – 1.5 RFU (max-min)) and not significantly different from the control. The increase observed was again fully inhibited in the presence of AZ8838. Although the results were not significant here the trends of stimuli / antagonist treatment are similar to that observed from

FLIGRLO treated primary cells and FLIGRLO & DEP treated BEAS-2B, indicating that an increase in experimental samples may show a more demonstrable effect.

Phosphorylation of p38 & p42/44 also indicated that DEP can lead to the activation of PAR2 downstream cascade components. The phosphorylation seen is far slower than that induced by FLIGRLO, reaching a maximal point at approximately 1 hr, indicating that there may be a different, perhaps indirect, activation mechanism taking place explaining the PAR2 activation kinetics. Conversely, the Ca^{2+} mobilisation trend was only slightly slower in DEP organic extract-treated cells than that in FLIGRLO stimulated HBEC. A previous study by Li *et al* showed that DEP could mediate calcium mobilisation in ALI-differentiated HBEC producing a biphasic response largely inhibited by TRPV4 antagonism (Li *et al.*, 2011). Comparatively, the work presented here potentially cannot demonstrate this biphasic response due to short analysis time frame. However, the work by Li and colleagues did highlight a differential response of organic DEP extract and DEP bound particulates, with the former triggering an earlier signal. Thereafter it was hypothesised that the DEP carbonaceous core could act as a slow-release delivery system for surface-bound organic components (Li *et al.*, 2011). This may provide an explanation to the differences in time-response seen in the Ca^{2+} mobilisation and WB results, as the former assay was performed with the organic extract and the latter the whole suspended DEP. Again, the cytokine response following confirmation of DEP induced PAR2 activation was examined by quantifying IL-6 and IL-8 levels after 24 hr stimulation (Figure 5.12). Although an increase was seen in both cytokine levels in BEAS-2B, the stimulations in HBEC again (as with FLIGRLO) did not show a significant increase from baseline levels. This may again be due the previously discussed influence of patient variability, low sample number and potentially impaired calcium influx. Alternatively, the time point here could be too short to account for a change in transcription, translation and protein production required to show a change in secretion rate. The time-frame analysed here may only have allowed for the release of previously packaged cytokines from intracellular vesicles.

The final model of study, and most physiologically relevant, is the air liquid interface culture. ALI culture in this study developed in only primary human bronchial epithelia as literature from cell line studies suggest drawbacks such as inability to maintain a monolayer structure or form suitable tight junctions (He *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, this allowed the determination of difference between responses from normal donor cells and those of COPD patients.

Primary monolayers were expanded and differentiated at the air-liquid interface for a total period of 21-28 days and analysed for differentiation markers. Presence of mucus was observed from airlifted cells as well as typical morphology expected during differentiation phases, including the cobblestone pattern expected of confluent HBEC (at airlift). A similar pattern was observed in previous studies (Yao *et al.*, 1996; Bluhmki *et al.*, 2020). Further, the profile of the air-liquid interface culture was analysed by IF of epithelial differentiation markers. Cells showed presence of mucin (MUC5AC), cilia (β -tubulin & FOXJ) and tight junctions (ZO-1) after the 28-day period indicating a successful ALI protocol and full differentiation of the HBEC used. This confirms that the process of differentiation used herein was successful in producing differentiated cellular models distinctive of physiological airway structure. These markers have previously been used in a number of previous studies to confirm differentiation of the ALI culture in human bronchial cells (Ishikawa and Ito, 2017; Sotty *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, PAR2 receptor within the ALI culture was examined and presence was established, PAR2 presence on human bronchial epithelia has been previously confirmed by immunoblotting and immunohistochemistry (Lin *et al.*, 2008). Although there was a pattern of higher IL-6 values in HBEC and higher IL-8 values in COPD-HBEC there were no significant differences in cytokine expression between healthy and COPD patient cells, in contrast to the results seen in submerged cells. This lack of significant difference in cytokine secretion between HBEC and COPD-HBEC ALI cultures including IL-6 and IL-8 is reinforced by previous observations (Sotty *et al.*, 2019). IL-8 levels were also seen at higher levels than that of IL-6 as seen here in ALI and submerged cells indicating a similar cytokine profile as those investigated here.

As there was no difference observed between the two cytokine secretion rates in the cells the potential for PAR2 mediated inflammatory induction was observed between the two ALI models. A previous study by Carey *et al* demonstrated differential pro-inflammatory cytokine induction following apical and basal (separate) FLIGRLO stimulation of human nasal epithelial cells differentiated at ALI, suggesting PAR2 polarisation (Carey *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, to determine any effects of spatially separated PAR2 pools on inflammatory effects, FLIGRLO was used to stimulate the apical and basal chambers and cytokine concentrations were measured from compartments separately. No effect was observed following stimulation at 4 or 24 hr, this may be in part due to the low concentration of FLIGRLO used here (10 μ M). Based upon previously discussed calcium measurements, a concentration of 100 μ M could have provided a greater response. Inability to induce IL-8 and TNF α production has previously

been demonstrated in 16HBE14o- ALI cultures stimulated with LPS, potentially due to initially high basal cytokine expression (Bisig *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, the potential to reduce any constitutive inflammatory state of the ALI and determine any mechanisms of PAR2 perpetuation in this inflammation were investigated. Previously, studies have demonstrated AZ8838 as an effective inhibitor of PAR2 induced inflammation (Kennedy *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, cells were pre-incubated with AZ8838 to determine any such process, however, contrary to expectation the antagonist displayed agonistic effects at the 24 hr period. This may be due to (in part) an agonistic effect of the compound on the ALI culture at the high concentrations used. This may not have been observable in the other assays due to the long incubation time of 24 hr vs. those observed in western blot (1 hr) and calcium assay (2 min). Agonistic effect of a PAR2 antagonist has been observed before in another small molecule antagonist, GB88 (Hollenberg *et al.*, 2014). This antagonist was one of the first antagonists found to inhibit activation of PAR2 at low micromolar concentrations (as with AZ8838), which has been observed to act as a competitive inhibitor of FLIGRLO and GB110, and non-competitive inhibitor of trypsin (Suen *et al.*, 2012). Also, as with AZ8838, GB88 was seen to reduce PAR2 agonist-induced rat paw oedema (Suen *et al.*, 2012; Kennedy *et al.*, 2020). This action is mediated via biased blockade of the $G\alpha_{q/11}$ pathway, however, this compound also displays dual action and serves as a partial agonist, activating $G_{i/o}$ and increasing ERK1/2 phosphorylation (in CHO cells transfected with PAR2) (Suen *et al.*, 2012). Further experiments could be focussed on investigating the action of a lower concentration of AZ8838 on HBEC ALI pro-inflammatory cytokine release to counteract any partial agonistic effect observed. This was not performed here due to time limitations and limited availability of primary cells.

To determine any effect of DEP exposure on the air-liquid interface model, both differentiated HBEC and COPD-HBEC were stimulated on the apical surface for periods of 4 and 24 hr before cytokine secretion was measured from conditioned medium. As with the results in submerged cells, no change was observed in the cytokine expression was seen in HBEC stimulated with DEP, neither was any change seen in the IL-6 production in COPD-HBEC. Lack of effect of DEP stimulation on IL6 and IL-8 cytokine production at a shorter time-point in primary HBEC differentiated at ALI has previously been shown, with IL-8 increase only seen with increasing biodiesel fraction (Vaughan *et al.*, 2019a). Contrary to results from HBEC, a significant increase in IL-8 production was seen from exposed COPD-HBEC, perhaps indicating that features of disease pathology may result in heightened

sensitivity of lung epithelia in COPD patients to acute DEP exposure. Similar results were shown in a study by Leclercq *et al.*, whereby COPD-HBEC exhibited a significantly higher IL-8 response (alongside TNF α and IL-1 β) than HBEC following exposure with fine ambient air pollution particulates over 24 hr (Leclercq *et al.*, 2016). Comparatively, the same study illustrated that IL-6 production was not increased in COPD-HBEC following either acute or repeated exposures of PM, whereas the opposite was observed in cells from non-diseased patients. Further investigations building upon this research should focus on elucidating the effect of repeated dose exposures on inflammatory outcomes. However, as the toxicant delivery method herein relies on apical membrane submersion this would likely have to be modified in a repeated dose experiment. This is because submersion been seen to result in de-differentiation of ALI cultures following a 2-day period while TEER measurements were maintained, illustrated in a study of ALI human nasal epithelial cultures (Carey *et al.*, 2020). The results shown here disagree with the previous findings shown herein in submerged cells, with the more physiologically relevant model showing increased susceptibility to DEP than the non-differentiated counterpart. This may be in part due to the higher sample number used in the ALI culture experiments (n=5 vs. n=3), but studies have shown a discrepancy between differentiated and non-differentiated cells previously. For example, primary human bronchial epithelial cells have been shown to display increased levels of IL-8 and markers of oxidative stress in response to aldehydes found within cigarette smoke and e-cigarette vapours, a result not seen when experiments were reconstructed in submerged cells (Dwivedi *et al.*, 2018). Importantly, the findings from the study mentioned in ALI culture model more closely mimicked the observations from *in vivo* studies (Dwivedi *et al.*, 2018; Pezzulo *et al.*, 2010).

Many exposures are known to increase inflammation in lung epithelia via a myriad of receptor interactions and intracellular communication pathways. To confirm that the inflammatory profile observed here implicated PAR2 involvement, exposures were performed alone and in the presence (pre-incubation) of AZ8838. As hypothesised, the inflammatory response observed was significantly reduced in antagonist pre-incubated cells; IL-8 levels were reduced down to baseline values. Interestingly, these observations were seen in only basal cytokine secretion with the higher DEP concentration assessed. Further investigation with a higher concentration of FLIGRLO may be required to understand the dynamics of PAR2 signalling in ALI differentiated COPD-HBEC and HBEC.

There are a number of important considerations which must be taken into account when discussing PAR2 stimulation in ALI culture, especially as the results seen here differ from the

monolayer culture findings. PAR2 localisation is altered in the ALI culture, as a recent finding by Li *et al* shows, the receptor was found to localise to the cilia within HBEC differentiated at the air liquid interface (Li *et al.*, 2011). Therefore, DEP which come into contact with these projecting surfaces which create a large surface area could facilitate the slow-release bound components directly to the receptor. (Li *et al.*, 2011). Other studies have shown that basal, not apical PAR2 stimulation resulted in an increase in calcium mobilisation in well differentiated (nasal ALI) cultures (Carey *et al.*, 2020). Conversely, when cultures were pre-treated with disease-linked modifiers such as cigarette smoke condensate (CSC) during the differentiation stage, calcium mobilisation and cytokine increase (TGF β ₂ & GM-CSF) were seen following both exposures (Carey *et al.*, 2020). As this change was seen despite a lack of change in TEER measurements, and separate experiments indicated separate PAR2 apical and basal “pools”, it was thought that CSC could alter the polarisation of PAR2 in the ALI culture (Carey *et al.*, 2020). This may also explain the fact that a response was seen in the COPD-HBEC and not the HBEC. As it is not clear if any of the patients seen here have a previous history of smoking, the predisposition to this based on previous exposure to xenobiotics cannot be determined. However, it appears that these findings from COPD patient cells indicate disease pathogenesis mechanisms which have resulted in DEP exposure sensitivity in patients with the condition over unaffected individuals via a process involving the PAR2 receptor. One study approached this by demonstrating that DEP mediated PAR2 activation resulted in a greater calcium response and elevated MMP1 production in cells with TRPV4_{19S}, a COPD-predisposing variant, when compared with wild-type (Li *et al.*, 2011).

Previous studies have hypothesised that the PAR2 activation mechanism following DEP stimulation involves the prior activation of AhR. This is because it has previously been seen that DEP extract induced calcium mobilisation was attenuated following AhR receptor siRNA knockdown and antagonism (Brinchmann *et al.*, 2018a). Further, investigation into this process showed that PAR2 signalling was involved as antagonism of either receptor separately inhibited expression of oxidative and pro-inflammatory markers (Brinchmann *et al.*, 2018b). As PAR2 has known roles in sensory signalling such including the detection of proteases such as chitinase, it is hypothesised that the DEP / PAR2 signalling may have developed from man-made pollutant hijacking this evolutionary sensing mechanism (Li *et al.*, 2011). The exact mechanism by which this occurs, if the activation is direct or indirect and any involvement in disease-linked PAR2 polarisation is unclear and further investigation would be required to unveil these findings.

5.6 Conclusion

Overall, results herein indicate that there are differences between the observations of PAR2 activation in submerged monoculture and 3D differentiated HBEC. Additionally, findings in equivalent model of primary epithelia differed from that of BEAS-2B cell line (Chapter 4). Although low sample numbers may introduce error and loss of significance due to patient variability. Experiments with FLIGRLO and DEP exposure in monoculture did not see an increase in Ca^{2+} mobilisation but did show a gradual increasing trend and increase in p42/44 & p38 phosphorylation, although, no cytokine increase was seen following either treatment. This was however seen in ALI culture post 24 hr DEP exposure from the basal side of COPD-HBEC only. This effect was ameliorated with pre-incubation of AZ8838 indicating a role for PAR2 in the process of DEP mediated pro-inflammatory cytokine release from differentiated COPD-HBEC. Further, that COPD pathogenesis increases susceptibility of HBEC to DEP mediated inflammatory effects. The role of PAR2 mediated pro-inflammatory response to DEP is incompletely understood.

6 Chapter 6 – Discussion

6.1 Aims and Rationale

The central aims of this study were two-fold: firstly, to investigate the potential of air pollution within urban and remote focus regions to play a contributory role in COPD pathogenesis. Secondly, to investigate the axis between a common ubiquitous pollutant (DEP), inflammatory modulator (PAR2) and a hallmark of COPD (inflammation).

COPD is often associated with a history of smoking; however, an estimated one-third of cases are non-smoking related (GOLD, 2022; Salvi and Barnes, 2009). Therefore, other causative factors of pathogenesis and exacerbation such as air pollution have been a growing focus of investigation. Currently, air remediation strategies rely on data acquisition from mainly urban sites while reports suggest that airborne pollutants within other regional profiles can contribute to disease pathology (Eduard, Pearce and Douwes, 2009; van Kersen *et al.*, 2020; Post *et al.*, 2021). Although much of the prior knowledge on the impact of air pollution on health originates from epidemiological and panel-based studies, current evidence reports that *in vitro* assessment of toxicity can provide more detailed information of component action. Notably, this study has shown that air pollution levels, with reference to guideline and regulation limits could promote COPD pathogenesis. Further, that DEP can initiate a PAR2 dependant cascade resulting in pro-inflammatory cytokine release within a physiologically relevant model of lung epithelia. The work herein suggests that low-cost monitoring solutions and better understanding of component and mechanistic action of pollutants can better inform remediation strategies to improve population health and protect vulnerable COPD populations.

6.2 Evaluating performance of AQMesh low-cost monitor

Due to limitations of the current air pollutant concentration report system a number of advancements have been made in low-cost monitoring solutions. This study illustrated the potential of one such system, the AQMesh, and highlighted benefits and drawbacks in the use of this instrument for purposes of regular monitoring. Gaseous concentration measurements gathered from two monitoring sites showed that AQMesh data correlated well with that of the stationary monitoring stations and that PM₁₀ values were inaccurate but indicative. R² values were in line with findings from literature, however, Paisley PM₁₀ regression illustrated a lack of correlation, contrasting with these reports (Wahlborg, Björling and Mattsson, 2021). This study suggests that variation between monitoring strategies can lead to inconsistent air monitoring data and under / over reporting of suspended pollutant concentrations. Meteorological factors and site-specific particulate composition were

identified as potential complicating factors in the reliability of the low-cost monitoring data. Therefore, the utilisation of a drying process could be employed in future development of this work to negate interferences of particulate deliquescence.

Assessment of the capabilities and efficiency of the AQMesh have been previously performed and this monitor has been utilised in a prior study to determine the effects of major roadworks on pollution levels (Transport Scotland, 2016). Particulate measurements have shown acceptable levels of correlation in reference to established monitoring sites (Ontario) with indication of a strong seasonal influence (Mohammed *et al.*, 2022). It has been suggested that performance of the AQMesh monitor in-field would show variation under diverse environmental conditions in agreement with the findings of this study (Castell *et al.*, 2017). Nevertheless, this system shows great potential, particularly with regards to gaseous and environmental parameter modelling. Additionally, the use of low-cost monitors such as the one investigated here have physical and monetary benefits in reference to modern systems. These benefits have been formerly displayed through the deployment of multiple monitors to create a high-resolution network. Previous work has shown this as an effective system in the location of previously unidentified pollution hotspots (Munir *et al.*, 2019). This study found that the AQMesh system could pose as a practical and reliable alternative to the current traditional air monitoring techniques / instruments given ideal environmental conditions.

Following calibration of the AQMesh, this system was utilised to gain a representative measure of four regions with different profiles, two urban and two non-urban (remote).

6.3 Air Pollution in COPD Hotspot Regions

From the initial stages of monitoring at the Stranraer location onwards it was important to note that there was an unanticipated modifier in the form of the COVID-19 pandemic. This led to vast changes in air pollution affecting parameters, mainly mobility which had incompletely understood alteration effects on air pollution production onwards from this period. Partial annual data was utilised in this study therefore findings are subject to a caveat of changed observations given complete datasets. However, when compared with regulatory limitations and guidelines, air pollution in Paisley was found to exceed a regulation or guideline limit for every pollutant assessed.

Alongside Paisley, Stranraer was the only location assessed which exceeded regulations set by the EU. Additionally, all sites showed an exceedance of NAQ regulations indicating that further investigation may illuminate a requirement for local remediation. Additionally, all areas showed an exceedance of WHO guideline limits for most pollutants. WHO limitations have been set based upon research-based observations on associated health effects including

COPD associated mortality (Lim *et al.*, 2019). Further, other studies have made observations of negative impact on lung function at concentrations lower than the ones recommended by WHO (Xu *et al.*, 2024; Rosenlund *et al.*, 2009). Therefore, reinforcing the principle that air pollution exposure has no known “safe” exposure limit (Marks, 2022; Chandia-Poblete *et al.*, 2022).

Findings of air pollution change within the SARS-CoV-2 (commonly termed COVID-19) pandemic highlighted a strong influence of transboundary pollution on regional and national air pollution fluctuation (Air Quality Expert Group, 2020; Acosta-Ramírez and Higham, 2022). This was shown via an increase in PM concentrations at the onset of the pandemic in Stranraer, an area where levels remained at relatively low concentrations during other periods. This, alongside published predictions on resultant lower mortality/morbidity rates emphasises the importance of adherence to global air quality restrictions (Khomenko *et al.*, 2021). A limitation of this study was the lack of complete annual datasets, periodic monitor failure and unprecedented change in anthropogenic activity from March 11 2020 onwards; all features which were influenced by the pandemic.

Findings here support the hypothesis that regional air pollution could contribute to the pathogenesis of COPD in urban areas and lesser monitored, remote disease hotspot regions in Scotland. Implementation of the AQMesh instrumentation into a higher-resolution air monitoring strategy could identify breaches of legislative and health-observation enforced regulations and guidelines. Further investigation would be required to elucidate any impact on network reliability introduced by inter-pod inconsistency.

6.4 Personal exposure in internal combustion and electric vehicles

Although external exposure is often utilised as a metric by which personal exposure is measured, this can depend greatly on variables such as indoor pollutant concentrations and travel-linked exposures. For instance, a study by Panchal *et al* showed that concentrations of NO₂ and O₃ were higher in car cabins during a driving commute when compared with surrounding exposures during paired activity commutes (cycling and walking) (Panchal *et al.*, 2022a). Here this was addressed by comparing gaseous pollutant concentrations generated during operation of a internal combustion engine vehicle (ICE) and an electric vehicle (EV). Significantly lower concentrations of NO_x were seen in the EV compared to the ICE. This is in line with findings from a previous study which showed that pollutant concentrations (black carbon and NO₂) were lower in electric hybrid vehicles when compared with that of diesel vehicles (Bos *et al.*, 2021). Variables such as this have an effect on personal exposure levels and are often not considered within epidemiological studies, further investigation may further

emphasise the importance on identifying harmful pollutant components compared with pollutant concentrations alone. This is particularly applicable to PM as the agglomeration of aerogenic particulates is chemically nonspecific and individual analysis of effects have shown differentiation in action. This indicates a role for size, composition, source, concentration and sampling season which all influence measured health impacts upon exposure (Dergham *et al.*, 2015).

6.5 Diesel engine particulates and Protease Activated Receptor 2 in Bronchial Epithelial Cell Line

Concentration – effect studies have been a central hallmark of air pollution impact research but, although highly informative and frequently statistically powerful, cannot alone describe the mechanisms by which pollutants induce such effects. Therefore, the later sections of research placed emphasis on the delineation of the relationship between a common ubiquitous pollutant (DEP) and lung epithelia. Additionally, the potential for inflammation to act via PAR2, an inflammation modulatory receptor, was discussed as this has been previously linked with COPD and strongly associated with inflammation in several conditions including rheumatoid arthritis and allergic asthma (Clark *et al.*, 1995; Ferrell *et al.*, 2003; Knight *et al.*, 2001). Literature has discussed a mechanism involving PAR2 in the DEP mediated inflammation cascade, however, future studies should focus on better understanding this mechanism, particularly with regard to the COPD disease state (Brinchmann *et al.*, 2018b; Li *et al.*, 2011).

This investigation utilised the BEAS-2B cell line, a commonly used representative lung epithelial model due to consistency of results and ease of culture. Models such as this allow for early-stage screening for preliminary results as primary cell use is often restricted due to limitations such as availability, difficulty culturing and time constraints.

Initially the presence of PAR2 in the target model were identified as previously reported with patterns indicating levels of internalisation and trafficking (Asokanathan *et al.*, 2002; Adams *et al.*, 2011). This may be due to the culture method prior to IF processing; serum starvation and confocal image capture (to increase resolution and improve receptor localisation) should be studied further in future examination. This result was enforced with similar but more clearly evident PAR2 internalisation post- FLIGRLO and DEP stimulation.

Functional capacity of the receptor in BEAS-2B was assessed. For this, the downstream activation of PAR2 following FLIGRLO stimulation was confirmed via calcium signalling, a

result ameliorated in the presence of the antagonist AZ8838. Parallel studies of DEP exposure induced effects could not be performed with whole DEP extract due to technical challenges. Notably, organic DEP fractions induced PAR2 activation, whereas the aqueous fraction did not, AZ8838 antagonism again further confirmed the involvement of PAR2 in the resulting Ca^{2+} mobilisation. As the DEP material utilised in this study is a standard reference material, its content has been characterised and the organic fraction has been found to contain PAHs, nitro-PAHs and aliphatic hydrocarbons (NIST, 2021). Further investigation would be required to better understand the component which acts upon PAR2. PAHs including Benzo[a]pyrene, pyrene, and 1-nitropyrene have been shown to increase Ca^{2+} mobilisation within BEAS-2B and MHEC-1 (Mayati *et al.*, 2012; Mayati *et al.*, 2014). However, no information is available on the exact PAR2 activating components within organic extract of DEPs.

The process of DEP mediated calcium flux in BEAS-2B and subsequent attenuation with PAR2 inhibition has been shown previously, although not with the use of the more novel AZ8838 antagonist (Li *et al.*, 2011).

The PAR2 inhibitory potential of AZ8838 has been addressed with regards to calcium mobilisation only once previously, yet not in epithelial cells (Kennedy *et al.*, 2020). Distinct Ca^{2+} signalling patterns of FLIGRLO and DEP were observed in the present study, FLIGRLO triggered a rapid, transient calcium response, while DEP induced a slower, sustained flux, indicating differing receptor activation mechanisms.

This is where the short post-activation analysis period represents a study limitation, as signalling dynamics here are incompletely understood from present data. Calcium signalling observations are not only subject to intracellular mobilisation but also extracellular influx. Further experimentation with an assay capable of measuring this influx alongside longer sampling times would elucidate any involvement of a secondary calcium wave succeeding initial response, as previously described (Brinchmann *et al.*, 2018a). A longer monitoring period would also provide a more robust determination of any agonistic effect of AZ8838; however, the lack of such potential has been reported previously (Kennedy *et al.*, 2020). This is especially pertinent as agonists have been mistaken for antagonists previously due to the irreversible activation and internalisation / degradation of PAR2, as has been seen very recently in the case of the prior misclassified agonist, GB83 (Heo *et al.*, 2022).

Given the lack of effect on intracellular calcium signalling by aqueous DEP compared with the organic extract, the potential for this fraction to induce other effects, namely ROS production, was examined. Results here indicated that the polar soluble component of DEP displayed effects in the induction of ROS and subsequent lipid peroxidation; thereby indicating

involvement of Fenton reactions and metal component action. This hypothesis is backed by a previous investigation by Ball *et al* whereby the production of malondialdehyde from 2-deoxyribose and ascorbic acid in the presence of SRM 2975 aqueous extract was measured, indicative of ROS formation. This production was inhibited in the presence of desferrioxamine (iron chelator) reinforcing an effect induced by transition metals (Ball *et al.*, 2000).

This parameter has been addressed and demonstrated before in another study with BEAS-2B following exposure to another common solid exposure matrix with shared components – cigarette smoke extract (Invernizzi *et al.*, 2004; Yoshida *et al.*, 2019).

Studies have before addressed the segmentation of PM based upon health-based outcomes. For instance, a study by Dergham *et al* found that seasonality alongside origin had a strong influence on the composition and physicochemical properties of sampled PM. This disparity manifested in the form of variation on potential to induce cellular cytotoxicity, oxidative stress and release of inflammatory mediators in BEAS-2B (Dergham *et al.*, 2015). Findings here also suggested varying contributory action of different fractions on negative effects, dependent on parameter observed (inflammation / oxidative stress), reinforcing these conclusions. Additionally, a previous study on the inflammatory effects of DEP on BEAS-2B found that IL-6 and IL-8 induced by PM exposure was linked to a complex combinatorial effect of ROS and receptor signalling (via PAR2, AhR receptors) (Bach *et al.*, 2015).

These factors could also, individually and combined, lead to the downstream, inflammatory cytokine release seen in this study.

The ROS-inducing potential of organic DEP remains unclear, despite suggestions of a higher oxidative potential than polar DEP extract (Bach *et al.*, 2015). Further research should focus on elucidating this potential and identification of the activate components of polar and non-polar fractions.

The tertiary stage of analysis focussed on determining the primary focal outcome of upstream PAR2 signalling, pro-inflammatory cytokine release. Although 24 hr FLIGRLO stimulations did not induce any effect, DEP increased the IL-8 production of BEAS-2B in a significant manner. This lies in contrast with previous findings of IL-6 and IL-8 release following stimulation with another, less potent, PAR2 activating peptide (Asokanathan *et al.*, 2002). Disparities between outcomes following the different stimulations could be because the DEP components acted via more than one pathway alone, as indicated by the production of ROS seen in prior experiments. A limitation of this study is the lack of a positive ELISA-based control e.g. LPS or trypsin to confirm pathway activation and cytokine production capabilities. Additionally, qPCR could be utilised to investigate the potential for influence on

downstream expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines. Conversely, DEP results were in line with previous findings of calcium mobilisation increase and subsequent antagonism with AZ8838, although other reports suggest composition dependent cytokine specificity (Bach *et al.*, 2015; Brinchmann *et al.*, 2018b). As this is a factor influenced by source, further investigations into component contributory action may better reflect in-field observations of lung health effects (Zerboni *et al.*, 2022).

6.6 Diesel engine particulates and Protease Activated Receptor 2 in Human Bronchial Epithelial Cell Monolayer

A potential functional axis between PAR2 and DEP was thus identified in the immortalised cell line BEAS-2B, but reports suggest disparities between these cells and primary counterparts (Han *et al.*, 2020; Asokanathan *et al.*, 2002). Therefore, this parameter was also investigated in cells from both healthy subjects and COPD donor patients.

PAR2 localisation was seen distributed in a diffuse pattern throughout both cell types, however, the inflammatory profile, differed with COPD-HBEC displaying significantly higher basal levels of IL-8 secretion. This finding reinforces previous findings of elevated cytokine expression in COPD patient sputum and serum, although both IL-6 and IL-8 increase was observed in these studies (Keatings *et al.*, 1996; Grubek-Jaworska *et al.*, 2012). A similar *in vitro* study demonstrated more comparable results with higher IL-8 but lower IL-6 in COPD patient cells compared with healthy counterparts (Leclercq *et al.*, 2016). Disparities between these observations could be due to COPD patient history. Classifications on smoking status, age, sex, weight and clinical history could better inform patient variability in all primary cell studies. The lack of this information when using commercially sourced cells remains a limitation of this study.

Calcium mobilisation in primary cells was not significantly increased following cell stimulation with FLIGRLO or DEP organic extract. However, a trend was seen following exposure to the highest concentration of FLIGRLO, followed by a significant reduction post AZ8838 incubation and a similar trend in DEP organic extract-treated cells. Future studies could elaborate on findings shown here by again investigating influence of patient variability, or through implementation of a longer observation time course, lest signalling kinetics differ from that of immortalised cells.

Alongside Ca²⁺ signalling, the PAR2 activation cascade is comprised of multiple divergent components including MAPK pathway activation. The observed phosphorylation of SAPK and ERK in response to DEP and FLIGRLO stimulation as shown here supports the hypothesis

of PAR2 activation, particularly as this was reduced with receptor antagonism. The slower rate of onset following DEP stimulation indicated a modified action when compared with the activity of the agonist. Further study would be required to investigate if this was mediated by transactivation mechanisms (e.g. via AhR receptor) or slow-release mechanisms related to physical characteristics of the stimulant matrix as indicated in previous findings (Li *et al.*, 2011; Brinchmann *et al.*, 2018b). Conversely, other factors such as potency of the active component(s) within DEP organic extract when compared with FLIGRLO could be implicated in the findings here. Characterisation of this process could be identified in future studies via the application of organic extract as a comparator to whole DEP exposure and AhR silencing / antagonism.

As pro-inflammatory cytokine release is a downstream outcome of MAPK pathway activation this parameter was assessed. However, no significant change was seen in response to either FLIGRLO agonism or whole DEP exposure. Implementation of a longer time-frame would further elucidate any change in transcriptional and translational activity. In the case that calcium influx is a pivotal factor of IL-6 and IL-8 release here, as is suggested in the literature, this could be further investigated in extensions of this study through assay modification increasing internal Ca²⁺ movement (Jairaman *et al.*, 2015).

A pro-inflammatory cytokine response was not seen here, although DEP exposure has been reported to increase pro-inflammatory cytokine release in human airways as measured through increasing concentrations of IL-6 and IL-8 in post-exposure bronchial wash (Riedl and Diaz-Sanchez, 2005). It is possible that this was not only due to sub-optimal conditions for cytokine production but potentially also due to the discrepancies between primary epithelial monolayer and the physiological airway.

6.7 Diesel engine particulates and Protease Activated Receptor 2 in Human Bronchial Epithelial Air-liquid Interface Culture Model

Human airway-relevant models display a benefit over other models when investigating the effects of DEP including animal models. For instance, DEP has been shown to induce MMP1 release via a PAR2-dependent mechanism in human bronchial epithelial cells thereby contributing directly to lung remodelling (Li *et al.*, 2011). Whereas the murine model lacks a functional MMP-1-ortholog, therefore this output cannot be quantified and the resulting observed effects of DEP exposure may be lessened (Carver *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, analyses were performed on the pseudostratified structure of the airway, recapitulated in a physiologically more relevant cell model differentiated at the air-liquid interface. Primary cell

pseudostratified epithelia differentiation was confirmed, models displayed morphological similarity with other published reports including the cobblestone appearance of confluent HBEC at airlift (Yao *et al.*, 1996; Bluhmki *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, mucus production was seen alongside positive staining of differentiation markers zona occludens (ZO-1) for tight junctions, β -tubulin and FOXJ for ciliated cells and MUC5AC for mucins – markers utilised previously to confirm successful ALI development (Ishikawa and Ito, 2017; Sotty *et al.*, 2019). The lack of significant difference between healthy and COPD basal cytokine secretion in ALI cultures compared to observations in the monolayer culture may have been attributable to patient variability and low sample numbers.

Inflammatory potential and PAR2 polarisation, reported in previous ALI studies, was investigated via the application of FLIGRLO to apical and basal surfaces of the ALI culture. Neither IL-6 or IL-8 secretion was affected by up to 10 μ M of the agonist; a limitation of this study is the lack of an analysis with a higher concentration of FLIGRLO.

It is possible in this case that any further production of pro-inflammatory cytokine release could have masked an additive effect of the agonist due to prior overactivation of the inflammatory response pathway. This has been demonstrated previously in a study by Bisig *et al* whereby agonism of 16HBE14o- with LPS failed to increase already elevated basal levels of TNF and IL-8 (Bisig *et al.*, 2019). Chronic inflammation is a characteristic of COPD and therefore maintenance of this profile might be expected when cells have been isolated from origin, however, the reason for maximal cytokine production in HBEC at rest is less evident. As a patient profile has not been assessed with regard to these normal HBEC here, this could be due to patient variables such as smoking history or as an outcome of pre-existing, non-COPD disease (e.g. cancer) pathogenesis (O'Callaghan *et al.*, 2010; Jafri, Shi and Mills, 2013; De Cunto *et al.*, 2011).

A potential role for PAR2 in the perpetuation of inflammatory processes was not supported by data showing absence of significant reduction post AZ8838 incubation, a previously observed antagonist of PAR2 mediated inflammation (Kennedy *et al.*, 2020). Contrary to expected findings, AZ8838 displayed agonistic effects, in line with previous observations utilising the potent PAR2 inhibitor, GB88 (Suen *et al.*, 2012; Hollenberg *et al.*, 2014). A study including a wider concentration range of both the antagonist and agonist should be investigated in future development of this work. This omission remains a limitation of this study due to limited primary cell viability and technical difficulties in consistently achieving full differentiation of the ALI culture.

The significant increase of IL-8 in COPD-HBEC with contrasting lack of effect in HBEC seen here has been observed previously although this was in response to atmospheric particulate matter (PM₄) (Leclercq *et al.*, 2016). This finding suggests an inherent difference conveyed by the pathology of COPD conferring increased sensitivity of lung epithelia to acute DEP exposure. Furthermore, current data suggests that this sensitivity is conserved in the ALI model of lung epithelia.

With regard to contrasting results from monolayer and ALI differentiated cells, similar reports of increased sensitivity to xenobiotic exposure of differentiated culture in comparison to the simple culture of epithelia have been described following stimulation with cigarette smoke and e-cigarette vapours (Dwivedi *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, a benefit of the ALI culture over other models is the increased relevance of exposure method i.e. apical application of stimulants/challenges.

Together this report and those from literature suggest increased reliability of ALI culture compared with simple monolayer cultures, and responses which more closely reflect *in vivo* study outcomes (Dwivedi *et al.*, 2018; Pezzulo *et al.*, 2010). Due to the ubiquitous nature of airborne pollutants and persistent/sustained delivery mechanism, an acute exposure does not necessarily replicate a real-world scenario. Chronic exposures would be more representative, however, application delivery system limitations here required culture submersion over the exposure period. Re-application of liquid to the apical layer is documented to induce model de-differentiation over periods longer than those utilised in this study (Carey *et al.*, 2020).

Therefore, further investigation could elucidate chronic treatment outcomes, aided by the implementation of a topical distribution system whilst maintaining optimal growth conditions. This would require the use of a process which would allow the distribution of particulates in a manner that would not submerge the apical layer, many systems of which have been investigated in previous literature (Lenz *et al.*, 2009; Juarez Facio *et al.*, 2022).

The lack of an effect in HBEC but significant response from COPD-HBEC were in line with previous findings following 24 hr exposure with ambient air pollution derived fine particulate matter (PM₄) (Leclercq *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, the exclusivity of basal compartment secretions have been represented through experiments very recently reported in cell line differentiated ALI cultures (Marques dos Santos *et al.*, 2022).

The pivotal finding of the biological component of this work is the abolishment of DEP induced signal in the presence of AZ8838, indicating an important role for PAR2 in the inflammation generated by this common air pollutant. The differing effects observed between submerged cells and the differentiated counterpart may have been attributable to localisation of PAR2 to

ciliary structures – as seen previously (Li *et al.*, 2011). However, this alone may not fully answer the resultant effects as IL-8 increase was solely identified in COPD-HBEC. Therefore, the differential response seen here could be due to inherent differences between ciliary observations in COPD and normal HBEC. For instance, one previous study showed that COPD epithelium have a higher density of cilia than that of non-COPD epithelia, an increase more evident in areas with indication of remodelling (mucus hyperplasia, basal cell hyperplasia etc.) (Perotin *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, impaired mucociliary clearance has been reported as a phenotype characteristic of chronic bronchitis (Bhowmik *et al.*, 2009). One explanation could be that increased surface area and time that particulates remain stationary may interact with a potential slow-release mechanism of organic component delivery to induce inflammation. Conversely, another study demonstrated that 20-day exposure to cigarette smoke condensate resulted in production of TGF- β and GM-CSF following both apical and basal stimulation with FLIGRLO, Der 3p (Dermatophagoides pteronyssinus Mite allergen) and tryptase in a concentration-dependant manner, whereas only basal stimulation response was observed in ALI not exposed with the cigarette condensate (Carey *et al.*, 2020). This was hypothesised to be attributable to altered PAR2 polarity, an effect observed in CSC treated ALI and nasal polyp remodelled tissue (when compared with turbinates) (Carey *et al.*, 2020).

This could have been seen here due to changes in the PAR2 polarisation state of the COPD-HBEC or because of inter-linked prior patient history of smoking; this is not determinable here due to limited patient data. Further investigation could be placed in future studies of PAR2 polarisation with regard to disease state and / or pollutant exposure to elucidate the mechanism behind the differential COPD response.

Another interesting factor which should be further explained here is the precise mechanism by which the PAR2 receptor is activated by the organic extract of DEP which is, as yet, unclear. This mechanism could involve the aryl hydrocarbon receptor as PAHs and dioxins present within organic DEP extract are understood to activate this receptor and previous studies have demonstrated that both receptors have roles in DEP cellular IL-6 and IL-8 release (Andersson *et al.*, 2002; Brinchmann *et al.*, 2018b). Furthermore, previous research has found that non-genomic AhR signalling to be the main mechanism by which organic extract of DEPs triggers Ca^{2+} increase within human microvascular endothelial cell line (Brinchmann *et al.*, 2018a). The possibility of GPCR trans-activation following AhR stimulation with organic components requires further study, however, there has as yet been no interplay identified between signalling of the two receptors. Another theory proposed by Li *et al* suggests a “hijacking” of the innate function of PAR2 as a sensory receptor for microbial proteases. This would be best understood

if the initial process of PAR2 activation, whether direct or indirect, was first elucidated (Li *et al.*, 2011).

Additionally, incomplete understanding of a perceived role of PAR2 in both DEP induced oxidative stress and inflammation has been indicated (Brinchmann *et al.*, 2018a). Elucidating component action on PAR2 may therefore be key in the identification of deleterious component action. The lack of sample specific patient history, low sample numbers and incomplete understanding of PAR2 polarisation state of the ALI culture remain a limitation of this study.

6.8 Recapitulation: Integrating Pollution Measurements and Mechanisms

Determining air pollution concentrations and assessing associated effects within populations is a commonly adopted approach for the comprehension of ambient pollutant exposure outcomes. Considering pollutant concentrations alone, however, may provide an incomplete understanding of effects as particulate matter components can also influence observations. Additionally, population studies cannot decipher mechanism of action or identify exact differences in response between healthy and vulnerable populations e.g. those with COPD.

Therefore, bridging this gap is essential to gain a holistic view of pollutant action. This study was impacted in a myriad of respects by the SARS-COV-2 pandemic. One of these ways was the implementation of travel restrictions imposed by the government to prevent spread of COVID. As it was not possible to travel to locations of interest, site specific pollution samples could not be obtained. Therefore, to investigate the effects of particulates and mechanistic understanding of action a globally ubiquitous pollutant (DEP) was used. This focus extended to the molecule PAR2 due to its tentative links with DEP (Lee *et al.*, 2018; Miotto *et al.*, 2002) and potential relevance to COPD. Given that COPD is characterised by chronic inflammation, and PAR2 is an inflammatory modulator with associations to other inflammatory conditions, exploring the relationship between PAR2 and DEP could provide valuable insights into COPD pathogenesis.

Moreover, by discerning which components of air pollution are detrimental and understanding mechanistic effects, more targeted interventions can be developed. This knowledge could empower policymakers and public health officials to implement more effective control measures that effectively mitigate the adverse effects of specific pollutants.

Given the prior rationale, the central objectives of this study were to identify air pollution concentration information from COPD hotspot regions, identify feasibility of the use of a low-cost monitor and investigate DEP mechanisms of action in epithelial cells.

6.9 Future Developments

Stemming from this work future developments could expand on a number of ideas introduced herein. With regards to the use of low-cost monitoring solutions such as the AQMesh, further investigation could be placed on the intra-pod variability seen under a variety of weather conditions, which could be utilised to further inform reliability of the system. Furthermore, utilisation of a multi-pod system which creates a higher resolution approach to determining air pollution levels would better identify currently unrecognised air pollution exceedances. This could take place in a regional format or down to street level which could both independently give an idea of source apportionment and the fluctuations observed within a short distance-frame. This could better direct findings on COPD population exposure outcomes, identify elevated pollution levels thereby improving current health warning systems and direct local and even international remediation strategies / guidelines.

The current understanding is that pollutants, in particular particulate matter, vary in composition depending on source contributions reinforced by findings that make-up directly influences physicochemical and health associated impacts. Much emphasis has been placed on the determination of highly specific source relevant particulates on inflammatory or ROS measured outcomes. However, a better strategy may be identification of specific components, alone and in combination on cellular response and therefore potential health outcomes. Studies could stratify combinatory effects of not only PM fractions but also of the major gaseous pollutants of focus together and alongside PM. Not least because studies suggest deleterious effects at lower concentration thresholds than those specified within control strategies (Kim *et al.*, 2011). This may be the requirement of finding safe levels of common pollutants such as DEP which are found ubiquitously throughout the atmosphere, actioning their negative impacts often long from their originating source.

These studies could implement physiologically relevant airway models which have been shown here and in previous literature to differ from simple monolayer findings and can unveil disease specific responses. This need not be applicable to COPD only but also to other distinct but closely related conditions such as allergic asthma, or idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, which have also been linked with PAR2 (Lin *et al.*, 2015; Park *et al.*, 2013). Identification of PAR2 specific activating components within pollutants and mechanism of action would show

relevance to a host of conditions such as this and highlight harmful air pollution components. This may also further enforce a drive towards electric vehicle use away from the use of diesel fuels. Additionally, there are shared components between DEPs and cigarette smoke (including dioxins and PAHs) and PAR2 levels showed elevated levels in lung tissue and epithelia of smokers and those with COPD (Lee *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, identified harmful components could be delivered via other processes such as smoking alongside air pollution exposure. Development of this work could not only inform remediation strategies but contribute to future stratification of patient treatments as mechanisms become clear.

6.10 Conclusion

It was originally hypothesised in this study that air pollution could contribute to the disease pathogenesis of COPD in remote COPD hotspot areas and that a common ubiquitous pollutant (DEP) can trigger key processes associated with COPD pathogenesis in human lung epithelia. The data within this thesis supports these hypotheses.

The central findings of this study are highlighted below:

- Low-cost monitoring data correlated well with stationary monitoring stations for ambient gaseous pollutant concentrations but showed inaccuracies for PM as meteorological factors and site-specific particulate composition can complicate the reliability of this data.
- The AQMesh instrumentation can identify breaches of legislative and health-observation enforced regulations and guidelines and shows potential as a practical and reliable alternative to traditional air monitoring techniques.
- Personal exposure to gaseous pollutants can vary between the internal compartment of a vehicle cabin of an ICE versus an EV, highlighting the importance of considering personal exposure variation from an ambient environment.
- An axis was identified between DEP, inflammatory receptor PAR2, and COPD.
- Organic components from DEP can differ in observed effects reinforcing the ideal of compositional attribution to observed effects.
- While primary cell monolayer show indication of PAR2 activation following DEP exposure, these cells may be lacking in potential to translate this to pro-inflammatory cytokine production.

- DEP stimulates pro-inflammatory response from a physiologically relevant model of COPD in a PAR2 dependant manner. This response was not observed in parallel healthy models indicating disease-related predisposition to the negative impact of particulate pollution.

This study highlighted a requirement for deeper understanding of component action on PAR2 as a strategy to identify deleterious component effects. Further development of this work would allow for the future stratification of COPD development processes and potentially patient treatments as response to environmental toxicants become clear. This knowledge alongside implementation of low-cost air monitoring systems could serve to improve current air pollution remediation strategies.

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APPENDIX I – Supplementary Data

Route map out of Lockdown (Scottish COVID-19 Pandemic Regulations/Guidelines)**Table 0.1 – Scottish route map out of lockdown.** Regulations set out by the government to guide Scotland through the COVID-19 pandemic (The Scottish Government, 2020).

	Lockdown	Phase 1	Phase 2	Phase 3	Phase 4
Friends & Family	Contact limited to household only	Outdoor activity permitted while adhering to physical distancing	Can meet larger groups outside with physical distancing	Can meet more than 1 household indoors with physical distancing	Restrictions on gatherings are eased
	Public Gatherings (2 people max)	Can meet another household outdoors with physical distancing	Can meet another household indoors with physical distancing		
	Very high-risk individuals are shielding				
Travel	Essential travel only staying in local area	Outdoor leisure & exercise restrictions eased to within 5 miles of local community	Public Transport increased services but capacity is restricted for physical distancing	Public Transport resumes a full service but capacity is restricted for physical distancing	Public transport resumes a full service
	Outdoor exercise (Walking, cycling etc) restricted to local area	Advised to travel by foot or bike if possible	Can drive locally for leisure and outdoor exercise	Can drive outside of local area for leisure and exercise purposes	
	Limited Public Transport operating with physical distancing measures				
Education	Schools and childcare services are closed	School Staff return to Schools	University Lab research resumes on Campus with physical distancing	All childcare reopens with space prioritised for key workers	College & University campuses reopen
	Universities and Colleges are closed and remote learning is in place	Increase in number of children with access to critical childcare provision		Children return to school part time blended with home teaching	School & Childcare
	Critical Childcare in place for Keyworkers and Vulnerable Children	Child minding and fully Outdoor nurseries reopen		Universities & Colleges return part time blended with remote learning	
Employment	Non-essential workplaces closed	Remote working is recommended if possible	Remote working is recommended if possible	Remote working is recommended if possible	All workplaces open
	Remote working is recommended		Non-essential Indoor non-office-based work resumes	Non-essential Indoor office-based work resumes	Remote working is encouraged
			House market restrictions ease		
Retail & Food Outlets	Non-essential retail and some indoor public spaces closed	Some drive through food outlets reopen	Outdoor Markets reopen	Large retail Units can reopen	All Retail and food outlets reopen
	Food & Drink Businesses closed	Garden centres reopen	Pubs & Restaurants open outdoors	Pubs & Restaurants Open Indoors	
	Outdoor Markets are closed		Small Retail Units can reopen	Personal Retail Services reopen	
Sports & Leisure	Entertainment & Leisure Facilities, Playgrounds & Holiday Accommodation Closed	Non-Contact Outdoor activities in your local area	Playgrounds & Sports Courts Reopen	Some Leisure & Entertainment Facilities Reopen	Further relaxation of live events
				Accommodation restrictions are eased	
				Live events with restricted numbers	
Community / Public services	Limited Courts open	Household Recycling centres reopen			
	All jury business halted	Court & tribunal buildings reopen with limited access			
Social Gatherings	No public gatherings greater than 2 people	Public gatherings up to 2 households permitted if outdoors	Weddings with limited numbers	People can meet in extended groups with physical distancing	Mass gathering in line with public guidelines
	Funerals have limited numbers		Places of Worship open for private prayer	Places of worship reopen for extended groups with physical distancing	All ceremonies resume with improved hygiene
			Registration offices open for high priority tasks	Events such as Funerals, marriages are relaxed beyond close family	
Health / Social Care	Non-urgent health care services stopped	NHS services including primary & community services restart	Restarting chronic disease management services	Community Optometry reopens	Full range of health & Social services reinstated
		Phased resumption of GP services	Dental practices reopen for urgent care needs	Screening Service expanded	
		Restarting Urgent Elective procedures		Adult Flu Vaccinations	

Figure 0.1 - Morphology of HBEC & COPD-HBEC immortalised human lung epithelial cell line. Cells were seeded and grown to approx. 80 % confluence, in a 96-well clear bottom cell culture plate. Subsequently, representative images of a single cell passage were captured using an EVOS XL core bright field microscope. Cells illustrated at left) 10 x magnification, scale bar: 25 µm & B) 20 x magnification, scale bar: 50 µm.

Figure 0.2 – Mouse monoclonal isotype for Air-Liquid Interface Culture. HBEC cells were seeded onto transwell inserts and grown to confluence before the apical layer was aspirated and the basal layer medium was changed from expansion to differentiation medium and cultures were maintained for 21 days. Following this both apical and basal compartments were incubated with murine monoclonal isotype antibody and appropriate secondary antibody bound with 647 (magenta).

Figure 0.3 – Rabbit polyclonal isotype for air-liquid interface culture. HBEC cells were seeded onto transwell inserts and grown to confluence before the apical layer was aspirated and the basal layer medium was changed from expansion to differentiation medium and cultures were maintained for 21 days. Following this both apical and basal compartments were incubated with murine monoclonal isotype antibody and appropriate secondary antibody bound with Alexa Fluor 488 (yellow).

APPENDIX II

Poster Presentations

Irish Thoracic Society meeting: Air Pollutants in Urban and Semi-Rural Locations, Irish Journal of Medical Science, 188, 319. November 2019, Galway, Ireland.

European Respiratory Society meeting: European Respiratory Journal, 56, 1973, September 2020, Virtual.

Oral Presentations

BREATH annual conference: June 2019, Belfast, Northern Ireland.

The 35th International Conference on Geochemistry and Health. July 2019, Manchester, England, hosted by Society for Environmental Geochemistry and Health. **Outstanding Oral Presentation Award – 2019**

Environmental Protection Scotland (Ricardo): Air Quality Expert Advisory Group Meeting, August 2019, Glasgow, Scotland

BREATH annual conference: June 2020, Virtual, hosted by UWS. **Award for Excellence in Oral Presentation - 2020**

Environmental Protection Scotland: Triple Win Clean Air Day Webinar, October 2020, Virtual, hosted by EPS

BREATH annual conference: June 2021, Virtual, hosted by Dundalk Institute of Technology

Conferences / Meetings

Irish Thoracic Society meeting. November 2018, Belfast, Northern Ireland.

Scottish Air Quality Database and Website Annual Seminar, February 2019, Edinburgh Scotland

Lay abstract and Participant, Annual Learning and Teaching Conference, July 2019, University of the West of Scotland, Lanarkshire.

Other Publications

Humphrey, O.S., Middleton, D.R.S., Ahmad, S. et al. The Society for Environmental Geochemistry and Health (SEGH): building for the future of early career researchers. Environ Geochem Health 43, 2455–2458 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10653-020-00620-4> (Editorial, contributory author).

Learning Teaching Conference Lay abstract

BREATH Study

Air pollution & COPD within Semi-rural Areas

The Border and Regions Airways Training Hub (BREATH) is a collaboration between three research centres: UWS, DkIT and QUB. All partnership members are dedicated to investigating chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), raising public awareness and alleviating disease burden.

COPD is a condition induced by chronic exposure to irritating particles and gases, including tobacco smoke and air pollution. It encompasses two distinct, often concurring pulmonary disorders: emphysema (alveolar breakdown) and chronic bronchitis (inflammation of bronchi). Within areas of Scotland, the prevalence of COPD is almost two-fold higher than the national average. Furthermore, elevated ambient pollution levels correspond with rates of morbidity and mortality of COPD sufferers.

This BREATH project investigates the association between airborne pollutants (particulate matter, PM and gases, NO₂ & O₃) and COPD, primarily within semi-rural disease hotspots (Ayrshire and Dumfries & Galloway). These regions are not air quality management areas, but have insufficient monitoring to allow an accurate understanding of air quality dynamics. A network of low cost monitors will be deployed within these regions to assess air quality and metal ratios in PM to understand source apportionment. Based on field observations, PM and gaseous pollutants will then be applied to *in vitro* cell models. This will provide insight into the propensity of atmospheric particles and gases to induce or exacerbate COPD and help identify the most deleterious components present in these areas. Furthermore, data obtained during the study will be made available to local councils to inform their development of measures for managing air pollution.

Irish Thoracic Society, Poster Presentation

AIR POLLUTANTS IN URBAN AND SEMI-RURAL LOCATIONS

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Air pollution represents the greatest environmental threat to the global population, particularly for vulnerable groups e.g. chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Control of airborne xenobiotics within Britain is addressed by automatic air monitoring strategies to identify excessive levels of pollutants. However, these do not provide a comprehensive overview of the pollution profile within an area.

This study investigated metal composition within particulates, to enable source apportionment of contaminants, and detection of elements most influential to health impact. Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectroscopy was used to analyse air samples obtained from urban and semi-rural locations. Metal contaminants identified in the environmental studies are then investigated in parallel cell culture studies on lung epithelial cells, to assess their effect on cell viability and cytokine release.

Beryllium, iron and zinc were detected in samples derived from the urban site; sodium, potassium and magnesium as well as zinc and iron were detected from the semi-rural site. Cell cultures studies on these identified pollutants are now ongoing.

Results from the environmental studies suggest rural pollutants likely originate from anthropogenic sources, whereas semi-rural pollutants may additionally derive from biogenic sources. Identifying impact of these pollutants on cell function may help develop targeted approaches to improving air quality.

Society for Environmental Geochemistry and Health Conference, Oral Presentation

METAL RATIO ANALYSIS OF AMBIENT PARTICULATE MATTER

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Air pollution is currently considered the greatest environmental threat to the global population. In the UK alone ambient air pollution has been associated with an estimated 40,000 deaths and a cost to the economy of £20bn. It is well documented in epidemiological studies that this hazard is particularly problematic for vulnerable groups, such as those in early developmental stages, the elderly and those with pre-existing respiratory conditions such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Control of airborne xenobiotics within Britain is addressed by the Air Quality Strategy (AQS) which utilises Automatic Urban and Rural Network (AURN) monitoring stations to identify excessive levels of these pollutants. However, this system does not provide a comprehensive overview of the pollution profile within an area and additionally there are still many designated Air Quality Management Areas (AQMAs) in place throughout the country. Furthermore, some of the levels of pollutants which are deemed 'safe' by the AQS have been identified as hazardous to human health within a review by the World Health Organisation (WHO).

For these reasons, there is a requirement for further analysis of pollution levels through utilisation of cost effective monitoring networks and identification of the components within particulate matter (PM) to give an accurate outline of air quality within different areas. This study has a major focus on the metal composition within particulates, as this would allow for both source apportionment of the most abundant contaminants, and (when studied within the context of *in vitro* models) scope for recognition of the elements most influential to perceived health impact. Through examination of the components which comprise PM alone, and in conjunction with other gaseous pollutants, we can further understand biological influence and thereby set stringent limitations for the most detrimental toxins.

European Respiratory Society Meeting, Poster presentation

Cytotoxic Effect of Vehicular PM Metals Fe^{3+} & Zn^{2+} on Lung Epithelia

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Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease prevalence and exacerbations are associated with elevated levels of air pollutants such as particulate matter (PM). The study of metal components gives an indication of health effects encompassing whole PM exposure. Effect of metal components on the respiratory system is in early stages of investigation. This research focuses on common PM metals (zinc & iron) which originate from a common pollutant source (vehicular emissions¹) and their action on lung epithelial cell lines; A549 & BEAS-2B.

Absolute metal concentration of analytical grade metal salts (FeCl_3 & ZnCl_2) were applied to A549 and BEAS-2B. After 24 h exposure, cytotoxicity was assessed using MTT metabolic assay and Interleukin (IL-6) production was determined using ELISA.

Zinc displayed a greater epithelial cytotoxicity potential than iron ($\text{IC}_{50} \sim 10 \mu\text{g/ml}$ cf. $>100 \mu\text{g/ml}$) on A549 & BEAS-2B (Fig. 1), conversely, iron stimulation demonstrated greater IL-6 production than zinc. Cell culture studies are currently ongoing.

Figure 1: Fe^{3+} & Zn^{2+} ions displayed dose dependent cytotoxic effects on A549 (A) & BEAS-2B (B) at concentrations greater than $10 \mu\text{g/ml}$. Mean \pm SEM. ----- IC_{50} threshold. * $p < 0.05$; * $p < 0.001$. Significance determined using one-way ANOVA. $n=3$.**

Preliminary results indicate differential action of metals on lung epithelium. Identifying the impact of these pollutant components may help develop targeted approaches to improving air quality and overall lung health.

The 35th International Conference on Geochemistry and Health. July 2019, Manchester, England, hosted by Society for Environmental Geochemistry and Health. Outstanding Oral Presentation Award – 2019. Springer award prize-giving.

Content redacted due to informed consent for publication

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BREATH Conference 2020

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